

No More Pencils No More Books: Capabilities of Generative AI on Irish and UK Computer Science School Leaving Examinations

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ChatGPT Prompts and Output

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<https://www.examinations.ie/exammaterialarchive/>

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<https://www.cambridgeinternational.org/programmes-and-qualifications/cambridge-international-as-and-a-level-computer-science-9618/past-papers/>

(1)

**Leaving Certificate Examination 2022
Computer Science
Higher Level**

ChatGPT Prompts and Output

May 2023

Exam Papers and Marking Schemes:

<https://www.examinations.ie/exammaterialarchive/>

Section A

PROMPT

Question 1

What is the output of the following Python program?

```
1 def func(a):
2   a = a + 1
3   b = 15
4   print(a)
5   print(b)
6   return(a)
7
8 a = 5
9 b = 10
10 print(a)
11 b = func(a)
12 print(a)
13 print(b)
```

OUTPUT

There seems to be an indentation error in the function definition. Python relies on indentation to determine the structure of the code. Let me fix that and then explain the expected output.

The corrected code:

```
python Copy code

def func(a):
    a = a + 1
    b = 15
    print(a)
    print(b)
    return(a)

a = 5
b = 10
print(a)
b = func(a)
print(a)
print(b)
```

Here is the step-by-step execution of the Python script:

1. A function `func(a)` is defined. The function increments the input argument `a` by one, sets a local variable `b` to 15, prints both `a` and `b`, and then returns the incremented `a`.
2. Global variables `a` and `b` are defined and set to 5 and 10, respectively.
3. The value of global `a` (which is 5) is printed.
4. The function `func(a)` is called with global `a` as the argument. Inside the function, the input argument `a` (which is the same as the global `a`, i.e., 5) is incremented by one (making it 6), a local `b` is set to 15, then both `a` and `b` are printed.
5. The incremented value of `a` (which is 6) is returned from the function and assigned to global `b`.
6. The values of global `a` and `b` are printed. The global `a` remains 5 because the increment in the function didn't affect it (the function has its own separate `a`). The global `b` is now 6 because it was set to the value returned from `func(a)`.

The final output will be:

```
5
6
15
5
6
```

PROMPT

Question 2

Registers and RAM are both types of volatile memory.

(a) What is volatile memory?

OUTPUT

Volatile memory is computer memory that requires power to maintain the stored information. Unlike non-volatile memory (like hard drives or SSDs) that retains its data even when powered off, volatile memory loses its content when the power supply to the memory chip is cut off.

This is the kind of memory that a computer uses to store data that it is actively using. The most common examples are the computer's RAM (Random Access Memory) and processor cache. This memory is much faster than non-volatile memory and is used to temporarily store data that is being processed or used by the computer.

In the context of your question, both registers (which are small amounts of fast storage locations inside the processor) and RAM are indeed types of volatile memory. When your computer is turned off, any data stored in the registers or RAM is lost.

PROMPT

b)

Describe **two** differences between registers and RAM.

OUTPUT

Registers and RAM (Random Access Memory) are both forms of volatile memory used in a computer system. However, they are used differently and have several key differences.

1. **Location and Size:** Registers are part of the processor (CPU) itself and are extremely limited in number. The number of registers varies depending on the specific CPU architecture, but it's generally in the range of dozens to a few hundreds. On the other hand, RAM is a separate hardware component external to the CPU, and it can be much larger, often holding gigabytes of data.
2. **Speed and Usage:** Registers are faster to access than RAM. Because they are located within the CPU itself, data stored in registers can be accessed and processed almost instantly. This makes registers ideal for storing data that is being immediately processed. RAM, while slower than registers, is still much faster than non-volatile storage options like hard drives or SSDs. RAM is used for storing data that the computer might need in the near future, including running applications, active user interfaces, and data being actively edited or manipulated.

These differences mean that registers and RAM play different roles in the operation of a computer. The CPU uses registers for tasks requiring the fastest possible access to small amounts of data, like calculations and logic operations. Meanwhile, RAM is used for storing larger amounts of data that needs to be readily accessible, but not quite as fast as data in registers.

PROMPT

Question 3

In 1965 Gordon Moore, co-founder of Intel Corporation, predicted that the number of transistors on an integrated circuit will approximately double every two years. This prediction became known as Moore's Law and has turned out to be very accurate to the present day.

(a) Explain the terms transistor and integrated circuit.

OUTPUT

Transistor:

A transistor is a fundamental component of modern electronic devices and is often referred to as the building block of digital circuits. Essentially, it is a semiconductor device that can amplify or switch electronic signals and electrical power.

Transistors are made from semiconductor material, typically silicon, which can be doped (i.e., impurities are added intentionally) to achieve desired electronic properties. A transistor usually has three layers of semiconductor material and three terminals. The behavior of charge carriers (electrons and holes) in these layers and the voltage applied to these terminals allow the transistor to act as a switch or an amplifier.

In the context of computing and digital electronics, transistors are used as electronic switches. A tiny electric current or voltage at one terminal (the "base") can control a much larger current flowing between the other two terminals (the "collector" and the "emitter"). This forms the basis of much of modern electronics, including processors and memory chips.

Integrated Circuit (IC):

An integrated circuit, also known as a chip or microchip, is a set of electronic circuits on one small flat piece (or "chip") of semiconductor material, usually silicon. The integration of a large number of tiny transistors into a small chip was a huge improvement over the manual assembly of circuits using discrete electronic components.

ICs can be designed to perform a variety of functions, such as amplification, oscillation, logic operations, and even sophisticated digital computations in the case of microprocessors. They have become a foundational technology in the modern world and are used in a vast array of electronic devices, including computers, mobile phones, and home appliances.

The prediction you mentioned, known as Moore's Law, observed that the number of transistors that could be placed inexpensively on an integrated circuit was doubling approximately every two years, driving exponential increases in computing power. While this trend has been remarkably consistent for several decades, it's been showing signs of slowing down in recent years due to physical and economic constraints.

PROMPT

(b)

State **one** reason why Moore's Law might not remain accurate in the future.

OUTPUT

Moore's Law may not remain accurate in the future due to physical limitations of miniaturization. As transistors shrink and more are packed onto chips, we are approaching the atomic scale where the traditional rules of semiconductor physics start to break down.

Here are some reasons why this is a problem:

1. **Quantum effects:** As we approach the nanometer scale, quantum mechanical effects can start to dominate, causing unwanted electrical behaviors. Quantum tunneling, for instance, can cause electrons to pass through barriers, leading to leakage currents and power dissipation.
2. **Heat dissipation:** As more transistors are packed into a smaller area, effectively removing heat generated by the transistors becomes more difficult. Excessive heat can negatively affect the performance and reliability of the transistors.
3. **Manufacturing challenges:** The techniques used to create transistors and place them onto a silicon wafer become increasingly complex and costly as the scale decreases. The photolithographic techniques used to etch transistor structures into silicon are approaching their limits.
4. **Economic factors:** The cost of fabricating facilities for advanced chips has been increasing dramatically. There may come a point where it's no longer economically viable to continue shrinking transistor sizes.

Scientists and engineers are exploring various new technologies to overcome these challenges and continue increasing computational power. Examples include 3D stacking of transistors, new materials beyond silicon, quantum computing, and neuromorphic computing. However, the future of these technologies remains uncertain as of my knowledge cutoff in September 2021.

PROMPT

Question 4

An automatic garage door has three inputs:

- A, the master ON/OFF switch
- B, a sensor on the left hand side
- C, a sensor on the right hand side

Once the master switch has been set ON, either sensor can trigger the door. This scenario can be represented by the logical statement: $A \text{ AND } (B \text{ OR } C)$.

(a) Complete the truth table for the logical statement $A \text{ AND } (B \text{ OR } C)$.

A B C A AND (B OR C)

0 0 0 0

0 0 1 0

0 1 0 0

0 1 1 0

1 0 0 0

1 0 1 1

1 1 0 1

1 1 1 1

OUTPUT

Here is the completed truth table for the logical statement $A \text{ AND } (B \text{ OR } C)$:

A	B	C	A AND (B OR C)
0	0	0	0
0	0	1	0
0	1	0	0
0	1	1	0
1	0	0	0
1	0	1	1
1	1	0	1
1	1	1	1

This table represents the operation of the garage door. The door will only open if the master switch 'A' is on ('1') and either sensor 'B' or 'C' is triggered ('1'). All other conditions will result in the door remaining closed ('0').

PROMPT

(b)

Use the relevant gate symbols to draw the circuit diagram for this system.

OUTPUT

While I'm unable to draw images directly, I can explain how the circuit would look. 📄 👍 🗨️

Here are the gates you'll need:

1. An **AND gate** for the operation `A AND (B OR C)`. The AND gate has two inputs and one output. It outputs `1` only when both inputs are `1`, and `0` otherwise.
2. An **OR gate** for the operation `B OR C`. The OR gate also has two inputs and one output. It outputs `1` if at least one of its inputs is `1`, and `0` otherwise.

To draw the circuit diagram, follow these steps:

1. Start by drawing an OR gate for `B OR C`. The inputs to the OR gate are `B` and `C`.
2. Then, draw an AND gate for `A AND (B OR C)`. The inputs to the AND gate are `A` and the output from the OR gate.
3. The output from the AND gate represents the operation `A AND (B OR C)`.

In ASCII-art format, it might look something like this:

```
lua 📄 Copy code
B -----\
           \
            >---( OR gate )---\
C -----/
                               \
                                >---( AND gate )--- Output
A -----/
```

In the diagram above, the `>` symbol represents the input side of a gate and the `--` symbol represents a wire carrying a signal. The text `( OR gate )` and `( AND gate )` represent the OR and AND gates, respectively. The wire connections from B, C, and A to the gates represent the logical operations being performed.

PROMPT

Question 5

A chemical solution is said to be an acid if its pH level is less than 7, a base if its pH level is greater than 7, and neutral otherwise.

Figure 1 displays a flowchart of an algorithm that, for a given pH entered by the user, displays whether it is an acid, a base or neutral.

Complete the table below to indicate the text that should appear in the flowchart for the letters A-E.

Letter Missing Text

- A**
- B**
- C**
- D**
- E**

OUTPUT

I'm sorry, but without the figure of the flowchart, it is difficult to provide the missing text corresponding to the letters A-E. The flowchart should depict the algorithm which checks if a pH value is an acid, base, or neutral.

However, based on your description, here is a general idea of what the flowchart might be doing and the text that could be associated with the letters:

A: "Start" or "Enter pH level"

B: "Is pH < 7?"

C: "Is pH > 7?"

D: "Display 'The solution is an Acid.'"

E: "Display 'The solution is a Base.'"

There should also be some text for the neutral case, which is pH=7. Without seeing the specific flowchart, I can't assign this text to a letter, but it could be something like "Display 'The solution is Neutral.'"

Please provide the flowchart for a more accurate response.

PROMPT

Question 6

Figure 2 shows an example of the client-server model of computing.

Explain the client-server model of computing. In your answer you should make reference to the terms included in **Figure 2**.

OUTPUT

I'm sorry for any misunderstanding, but as an AI model developed by OpenAI, I currently lack the ability to view figures, images, or external files. However, I can certainly explain the client-server model of computing.

The client-server model is a distributed application structure that partitions tasks or workloads between the providers of a resource or service, called servers, and service requesters, called clients. Here is a general explanation:

1. **Server:** This is a computer or system that manages network resources. It's a central computer that hosts files and databases. It's more powerful and has a large storage capacity, high-speed processors, and large memory. It's also always running to process requests from clients.
2. **Client:** These are computers or devices that request services from the server. A client can be a personal computer, a tablet, a smartphone, or even another server. Clients usually have an interface for users to make requests to servers. They rely on servers to manage and store data.
3. **Network:** This is the medium that connects clients to servers. It could be a local network (like LAN) or a wide network (like the internet). Data is transferred between clients and servers through this network.
4. **Request:** A request is made by a client over the network to a server. This could be to retrieve data, store data, or perform a computation. For example, when you type a URL into your web browser, a request is made to the server that hosts the website.
5. **Response:** After a request is received and processed by the server, it sends a response back to the client. This could be the data requested, an acknowledgment of a completed operation, or a status error if the request could not be completed.

In a typical client-server model, multiple clients can communicate with the server at the same time. This model is widely used in the digital world. For instance, when you use a web browser to visit a site, your computer is the client, the website's hosting is the server, and HTTP/HTTPS is the protocol defining the rules for requests and responses.

PROMPT

Question 7

On 14 May 2021, the Health Service Executive (HSE) of Ireland suffered a major ransomware cyberattack which caused all of its IT systems nationwide to be shut down.

(a) Explain the term ransomware.

OUTPUT

Ransomware is a type of malicious software, or malware, that encrypts a victim's files. The attacker then demands a ransom from the victim to restore access to the data upon payment. The motive for ransomware attacks is nearly always monetary, and unlike other types of attacks, the victim is usually notified that an exploit has occurred and is given instructions for how to recover from the attack.

Typically, the attacker will demand the ransom be paid in a hard-to-trace digital currency, most often Bitcoin. Users are shown instructions for how to pay a fee to get the decryption key. The costs can range from a few hundred dollars to thousands, payable to cybercriminals in Bitcoin.

Ransomware can be spread through malicious e-mail attachments, infected software apps, infected external storage devices, and compromised websites, although a growing number of ransomware attacks use remote desktop protocol and other "direct" methods. A large number of ransomware attacks are also delivered via drive-by-download attacks on compromised websites.

Once the user's data is encrypted, the ransomware directs the user to pay the ransom to the attacker (usually via Bitcoin) in order to receive a decryption key. However, paying the ransom doesn't guarantee that the users will get the decryption key.

Ransomware attacks are increasingly common and they can be disruptive and costly, not just from the ransom payment, but also from the loss of data and the downtime for systems and networks.

PROMPT

(b)

State **two** measures individuals or companies can take to reduce the risk of a cyberattack.

OUTPUT

There are several measures that individuals or companies can take to reduce the risk of a cyberattack:

1. **Install and Update Security Software:** Use a robust antivirus software and firewall to protect your system from malware threats. Always keep the software updated to ensure it can recognize and protect against the latest threats.
2. **Regular Data Backup:** Regularly back up data on all systems, and ensure these backups are stored in a secure, off-site location. In case of a ransomware attack, this will allow you to restore your system to its state before the attack without paying the ransom. It's important to test backups to ensure they can be restored.
3. **Update and Patch Systems:** Regularly update and patch all systems, including operating systems and all software installed on your devices. Many cyberattacks exploit vulnerabilities in outdated systems and software.
4. **Educate Employees:** For businesses, it's vital to conduct regular training for employees about cybersecurity best practices. This includes awareness about phishing emails, suspicious links, and the importance of strong, unique passwords.
5. **Use Strong, Unique Passwords and Enable Two-Factor Authentication:** Use strong, unique passwords for all accounts and change them regularly. Enable two-factor authentication wherever possible for an extra layer of security.
6. **Limit Access:** Only provide system access to the required users and limit the privileges. The fewer people with access to your system, the fewer opportunities for a potential cyberattack.
7. **Implement Network Security Measures:** For businesses, measures such as intrusion detection systems (IDS), intrusion prevention systems (IPS), and network segmentation can help detect and prevent unauthorized access to your network.

Remember, no system can ever be 100% secure, but these measures can significantly reduce the risk of a cyberattack.

PROMPT

Question 8

Cloud computing has been described as the third wave of the digital revolution.

Outline **one** advantage and **one** disadvantage of cloud computing under the headings of both cost and impact on the environment.

OUTPUT

Cloud computing is indeed considered a key part of the digital revolution, changing the way businesses and individuals use and store data. Here are some of its advantages and disadvantages from cost and environmental perspectives:

Cost:

Advantage:

- **Reduced IT costs:** With cloud computing, businesses can reduce the cost of maintaining and managing their IT systems. Instead of purchasing expensive systems and equipment, they can reduce their budget by using the resources of their cloud computing service provider. Moreover, the cost of system upgrades, new hardware and software may be included in the contract, and businesses can scale their cloud solutions as per need, which provides cost flexibility.

Disadvantage:

- **Potential unexpected costs:** While cloud computing can be cost-effective, there are scenarios where it could lead to unexpected costs. For instance, data transfer costs can add up when moving data to and from the cloud. Also, if a business needs to scale up its operations significantly, additional resources in the cloud could come with substantial costs.

Impact on the environment:

Advantage:

- **Reduced energy consumption:** Cloud computing can be more energy-efficient than traditional IT infrastructure, leading to lower carbon emissions. Since businesses only use the server space they need, they don't waste energy on cooling and maintaining unused servers, as it often happens with traditional data centers.

Disadvantage:

- **Energy use and carbon footprint of data centers:** While individual businesses might reduce their carbon footprints, the data centers that provide cloud services consume a significant amount of energy. These massive data centers need to be powered and cooled, which can have a substantial environmental impact, especially if the energy used is derived from non-renewable sources.

PROMPT

Question 9

(a) Provide **two** examples of how machine learning can be used to benefit society.

OUTPUT

Machine Learning (ML), a subset of artificial intelligence, holds significant potential to benefit society in many ways. Here are two examples:

1. **Healthcare and Medical Diagnosis:** Machine learning can help doctors diagnose diseases more accurately. For instance, ML algorithms can analyze medical images (like MRI or X-ray scans) to detect abnormalities such as tumors, brain injuries, or heart diseases. These tools can sometimes spot things that human doctors might miss. Additionally, ML can predict disease outbreaks and pandemics by analyzing public health data, helping to better prepare and respond to such situations.
2. **Education:** Machine learning can personalize education to individual students' needs. By analyzing a student's performance, ML algorithms can adapt the learning materials to their strengths and weaknesses, optimizing the learning process. It can also help identify students who are at risk of dropping out or those who might need extra help.

Other examples include improving traffic management in smart cities, enhancing agricultural productivity through precision farming, reducing energy consumption in buildings, assisting in climate and weather predictions, aiding in disaster response and recovery, and many more. The potential applications are vast, and we're only just beginning to scratch the surface of what machine learning can do.

PROMPT

(b) Briefly the issue of 'bias' in relation to machine learning.

OUTPUT

"Bias" in machine learning refers to the tendency of an algorithm to consistently learn the wrong thing by not taking into account all the information in the input data. This can happen when the data used to train the algorithm is not representative of the reality it's supposed to model. This could lead to unfair, unethical, or harmful outcomes, particularly when machine learning is used in sensitive areas like hiring, criminal justice, or loan approval.

Here are a few points to consider:

1. **Data Bias:** If the data used to train the machine learning algorithm is skewed or unrepresentative of the whole population, the model may perform poorly or unfairly. For example, if a facial recognition system is trained mostly on images of light-skinned individuals, it might perform poorly when trying to recognize individuals with darker skin tones.
2. **Algorithmic Bias:** This occurs when the assumptions or methods used in an algorithm lead to unfair outcomes. For example, if a machine learning algorithm used in hiring is trained on the past hiring decisions of a company that has historically favored a particular gender, the algorithm might "learn" to continue that bias.
3. **Confirmation Bias:** If an algorithm is designed or tuned to overly favor certain outcomes, it could reinforce existing biases. For example, if a predictive policing algorithm is mainly deployed in low-income neighborhoods, it may "learn" that this is where crimes occur, leading to a cycle of over-policing in those areas.

Bias in machine learning is a significant concern because these systems are increasingly being used in decision-making processes. It's important to ensure that they are fair and that they don't reinforce existing social inequalities. This is an active area of research, and developers are exploring various methods to reduce and mitigate bias in machine learning algorithms.

PROMPT

Question 10

You have eight coins and a two pan scales. Both the coins and the scales are gold plated and the diameter and circumference of all the coins are exactly the same. The coins are worth €2 each, a total of €16.

- seven of the coins are genuine and weigh the same amount.
- one of the coins is fake and is heavier than the others.

(a) Explain a way that the fake coin can be found in the minimum number of weighings.

OUTPUT

The fake (heavier) coin can be found in a minimum of two weighings using a divide and conquer strategy:

First Weighing:

1. Divide the 8 coins into 3 groups: two groups of 3 coins each and one group of 2 coins.
2. Now, weigh the two groups of 3 coins against each other.

Possible outcomes:

- If the two groups of 3 coins balance, then the heavier coin is among the 2 unweighed coins.
- If they don't balance, the heavier side contains the fake coin.

Second Weighing:

Depending on the outcome of the first weighing:

- If the heavier coin is among the 2 unweighed coins, just weigh these two coins against each other. The heavier one is the fake coin.
- If the heavier coin is in one of the groups of 3, pick that group and divide it into 3 individual coins. Weigh any two of these coins against each other. If they balance, the unweighed coin is the fake one. If they don't balance, the heavier coin is the fake one.

Thus, in just two weighings, you can find the fake (heavier) coin.

PROMPT

(b) Outline briefly your use of abstraction to tackle this problem.

OUTPUT

Abstraction in problem-solving involves reducing a complex problem to its essential, simplified components. When applying abstraction to this problem, several details about the coins and the scale were ignored because they were not directly relevant to finding the solution.

1. **Physical characteristics of the coins:** The fact that the coins are gold-plated, their worth in euros, the diameter, and the circumference are all details that are not necessary for solving the problem. The important aspect is their weight, and specifically, the fact that one coin is heavier than the others.
2. **Scales characteristics:** Similarly, the fact that the scales are two-pan and gold-plated is not as important as the function it performs, i.e., comparing weights. It's not important what the scale looks like, how large it is, or what it's made of; we only care about its ability to show which of two groups of coins is heavier.
3. **Nature of the problem:** The specifics about how the coins ended up in this situation or why we want to find the heavier coin are not important. We are focusing solely on the problem of distinguishing the heavier coin with the minimum number of weighings.

By focusing on these core aspects and ignoring the extraneous details, we've used abstraction to simplify the problem and make it easier to solve.

PROMPT

Question 11

The reproduction rules for honey bees are quite remarkable. Females lay eggs and if an egg is fertilised by a male it will hatch as a female. Unfertilised eggs hatch as males.

The illustration below shows an ancestry tree for the male honey bee shown at the top of the tree. There are five generations shown.

(a) Draw and label **two** additional generations.

OUTPUT

In a text-based format like this, it's challenging to draw figures. However, I can describe how the tree would look like with two additional generations.

Male honeybees, also known as drones, are produced from unfertilized eggs, so they have only a mother and no father. Therefore, each male bee has exactly one parent in the previous generation.

Females honeybees, or queens and workers, are produced from fertilized eggs, so they have both a mother and a father. Therefore, each female bee has two parents in the previous generation.

Starting with a male bee (drone) in generation 1:

Generation 2 has one female parent (the mother of the drone).

Generation 3 has two bees: one male (the grandfather of the drone) and one female (the grandmother of the drone).

Generation 4 has three bees: two females (the great-grandmothers of the drone) and one male (the great-grandfather of the drone).

Generation 5 has five bees: three females (the 2x-great-grandmothers of the drone) and two males (the 2x-great-grandfathers of the drone).

Adding two more generations:

Generation 6 would have eight bees: five females (the 3x-great-grandmothers of the drone) and three males (the 3x-great-grandfathers of the drone). This is because each female bee from generation 5 would add one female and one male to the next generation, while the male bees only add a female to the next generation.

Generation 7 would have thirteen bees: eight females (the 4x-great-grandmothers of the drone) and five males (the 4x-great-grandfathers of the drone), following the same pattern.

So, as we add generations, the ancestry tree grows following a Fibonacci-like sequence where each number is the sum of the two preceding ones, starting from 1 (the drone itself). This pattern arises from the unique reproductive biology of honeybees.

PROMPT

(b) Describe any pattern emerging that could be used to model the number of bees in any particular generation.

OUTPUT

The pattern that emerges in the honey bee ancestry tree is similar to the Fibonacci sequence, where each number is the sum of the two preceding ones. This pattern arises from the fact that female bees (queens and workers) have both a mother and a father (two ancestors in the previous generation), whereas male bees (drones) have only a mother (one ancestor in the previous generation).

Starting with a single male drone, the pattern of total ancestors in each generation is:

- Generation 1 (drone himself): 1 bee
- Generation 2 (mother): 1 bee
- Generation 3 (grandparents): 2 bees
- Generation 4 (great-grandparents): 3 bees
- Generation 5 (2x-great-grandparents): 5 bees

So, for any generation n , the total number of bees in that generation is the sum of the number of bees in the previous two generations ($n-1$ and $n-2$).

This pattern is a variation of the Fibonacci sequence, but instead of starting with two 1s, it starts with 1 and 1. Nonetheless, the essential property is the same: each term is the sum of the two preceding terms.

Please note that this is a simplification and assumes perfect reproduction without any deaths, which is not likely in real-world scenarios. But as a mathematical model, it captures the unique reproductive biology of honey bees.

PROMPT

Question 12

The state transition diagram for a particular Turing machine is shown in **Figure 3** below. The initial state is S_0 and the initial tape contents is the binary number 0110 followed by a blank, represented by 'B'. The final state is S_3 .

Trace the computation of the Turing machine by filling in the blanks in the diagram below. The read/write head is currently reading a 0. You can assume that the read/write head is moved one place to the right at the end of each step.

Figure 3

OUTPUT

I'm sorry for any confusion, but as a text-based AI, I'm not able to directly view or interact with images, diagrams, or other visual content. If you can provide the state transition diagram in a text-based format, I'd be happy to help interpret it and trace the computation of the Turing machine.

The text-based format should include each state, the input for that state, the output for that state, and the next state for each possible input. For example, it could look something like this:

State S_0 :

- On input 0: Write 1, move right, go to state S_1
- On input 1: Write 0, move right, go to state S_2

State S_1 :

- On input 0: Write 1, move right, go to state S_0
- On input 1: Write 0, move right, go to state S_3

... and so on for each state.

Once you provide that information, I'd be happy to help you trace the computation.

Section B PROMPT

Question 13

K-9 Kennels is a small dog boarding business whose aim is to meet the needs of dog owners who often have difficulty in finding a safe and reliable place to leave their pets. Since it was established, owners John and Mary Chewit have worked tirelessly to grow the business, and in addition to boarding it now offers a range of other services including grooming, massage and training.

(a) Mary and John realise that they need an information system and have appointed the software company you work for to design and develop the system. An initial meeting has been arranged and your manager has asked you to attend.

(i) What is an information system?

OUTPUT

An information system (IS) is a combination of hardware, software, data, people, and procedures that work together to produce quality information. Its main function is to manage, process, and distribute information to support decision making, coordination, control, analysis, and visualization in an organization.

Components of an Information System include:

1. **Hardware:** Physical devices like computers, servers, networking equipment, and data storage devices.
2. **Software:** The programs and applications that run on the hardware, which can include operating systems, database management systems, and specific applications necessary for the organization's needs.
3. **Data:** Information that the system uses to produce useful output. This might include customer data, business transaction data, and analytical data.
4. **People:** The users and managers of the information system, who interact with the system to perform tasks and make decisions.
5. **Procedures:** The rules and guidelines for using the system, which help ensure that people use the system correctly and consistently.

So, in the context of K-9 Kennels, an information system might include hardware and software for tracking boarding reservations, grooming appointments, and training schedules, data about each dog and their owner, and procedures for staff members to update the system and use it to coordinate services.

PROMPT

(ii) Provide **two** examples of how an information system could benefit K-9 Kennels.

OUTPUT

1. **Improved Efficiency and Organization:** An information system can streamline and automate many of the tasks related to managing a dog boarding business. For instance, it could automate the process of booking appointments, tracking which dogs are in the kennel at any given time, scheduling grooming or massage services, and managing billing and payments. This automation can reduce the amount of time spent on administrative tasks, minimize errors, and allow staff to focus more on providing excellent care for the dogs.
2. **Better Customer Service:** An information system could provide better service to customers by providing them with an easy-to-use online interface where they can make reservations, see availability, pay for services, and even check in on their pets. The system could also send automatic reminders for upcoming appointments or training sessions, updates about their pets, or promotional information about new services. This kind of direct, digital engagement can enhance the customer experience and encourage repeat business.
3. **Data Analysis and Decision Making:** The information system could gather and analyze data about business operations, which John and Mary Chewit could use to make informed decisions. For example, they could identify peak boarding times, popular services, or trends in customer behavior. This information could guide decisions about staffing, pricing, service offerings, and business growth.

PROMPT

(iii) Identify **two** key stakeholders and their respective roles in relation to the new system.

OUTPUT

1. **Owners (John and Mary Chewit):** As the owners of K-9 Kennels, John and Mary Chewit are key stakeholders in the new information system. They are responsible for making high-level decisions about the system, such as its overall functionality, budget, and implementation timeline. They will also be key users of the system, using it to manage their business and make strategic decisions. They would also play a key role in communicating about the system to other stakeholders, such as employees and customers.
2. **Employees:** The employees of K-9 Kennels are also important stakeholders, as they will be primary users of the new information system. Their roles might include inputting data into the system, using the system to track and manage their work, and interacting with customers through the system. Their feedback will be important for identifying any issues or improvements to the system. They would also need to be trained on how to use the new system.

Other potential stakeholders could include the customers, who will interact with the system when they book services or receive updates about their pets, and the software development team, who will be responsible for designing, building, testing, and maintaining the system.

PROMPT

(iv) Outline briefly **two** topics relating to the project which you anticipate will be discussed at the initial meeting.

OUTPUT

1. **System Requirements:** One of the crucial topics to discuss in the initial meeting would be understanding the specific requirements for the information system. This would include discussions about the functionalities that John and Mary need, such as reservation management, customer information management, service tracking (like grooming, massage, and training), and billing. The discussion would also involve understanding their business processes to ensure the system fits seamlessly into their existing operations.
2. **Project Timeline and Budget:** Another key topic would be the development timeline and the budget. This includes clarifying the expected deadlines for different phases of the project, such as design, development, testing, and deployment. It also means discussing the budget for the project to ensure that the proposed system is financially feasible for K-9 Kennels, and to understand any cost constraints that might influence design and development decisions.

PROMPT

(v) John and Mary are unsure about whether their system should be a website or a mobile application. State whether you think John and Mary should opt for a web application or a mobile application. Provide two reasons for this choice.

OUTPUT

Based on the information provided, I would recommend a web application for John and Mary's K-9 Kennels business, primarily for the following reasons:

1. **Accessibility:** A web application is platform-independent and can be accessed from any device that has an internet connection and a web browser, be it a desktop, laptop, tablet, or mobile phone. This way, they can manage their business from the office computer and clients can access it from their preferred devices.
2. **Ease of Maintenance and Updates:** With a web application, any updates or modifications made to the system are instantly available to all users since the application is hosted on a server. This eliminates the need for users to manually update the application on their devices as would be necessary with a mobile application.

However, it's worth noting that these days, a responsive web design approach can be employed to build web applications, which ensures the web app works well on all device sizes, including mobile devices. This approach provides the convenience of a mobile application without its associated downsides. It's also important to consider the target user base and their preferences in this decision – if the majority of their customers prefer using mobile applications, a mobile app could be a suitable option despite the mentioned reasons.

PROMPT

(vi) Explain why the choice of software development process is important when it comes to designing and developing software systems.

OUTPUT

The choice of software development process is crucial for the design and development of software systems due to several reasons:

1. **Quality:** The chosen development process directly impacts the quality of the final product. A well-structured process includes clear guidelines for quality assurance, including regular testing and reviews to ensure the software meets its requirements and functions as expected.
2. **Budget Control:** The right software development process helps in better estimating the time and cost required for the project, enabling effective budget control. A process that fits well with the project's nature can avoid unnecessary expenses and delays.
3. **Risk Management:** Different development processes offer varying degrees of risk management. Some methods, like the Agile process, allow for frequent adjustments and iterations, reducing the risk of significant project failures.
4. **Collaboration and Communication:** The development process sets the framework for communication and collaboration among team members and with stakeholders. It ensures everyone involved understands their responsibilities and the progression of the project.
5. **Customer Satisfaction:** A development process that includes regular client feedback and adjustments can lead to a final product more closely aligned with the client's vision, leading to higher customer satisfaction.

In essence, the choice of software development process can significantly impact the project's success or failure, making it a critical decision in the software design and development phase.

PROMPT

b) Some weeks after the initial meeting John and Mary contact your company to request that an online store be included as part of the system. The store will be made up of two pages – a shop page and a checkout page.

(i) The shop page should allow visitors to browse items. When a visitor wishes to purchase an item, they should be able to click an 'Add to Cart' button.
Create a wireframe diagram to show the layout of the shop page. Your wireframe should include annotations outlining the purpose of the main elements.

OUTPUT

I'm an AI language model and, unfortunately, I'm unable to directly draw or create visual content such as diagrams or wireframes. However, I can describe what a typical wireframe for a shop page might look like:

1. **Navigation bar:** At the top of the page, there should be a navigation bar that includes links to the other pages of the website (such as home, services, about us, contact us, etc). It should also include a logo or the name of the business.
2. **Search bar:** The search bar should be prominently positioned near the top of the page. This allows visitors to quickly find specific items they're looking for.
3. **Item grid:** The majority of the page should be filled with a grid or list of items available for purchase. Each item should have a thumbnail image, a brief description, the price, and an 'Add to Cart' button.
4. **Shopping cart icon:** This should be visible on every page, but particularly on the shop page. It gives users an overview of the items they've added to their cart, and clicking it should take them to the checkout page. It's usually located in the top right corner of the page.
5. **Footer:** At the bottom of the page, there should be a footer containing other links, terms and conditions, privacy policy, and contact information.

To make this wireframe, you could use a digital design tool like Sketch, Adobe XD, or Balsamiq. These tools often provide templates and guides to help you create professional-looking wireframes.

PROMPT

(ii) Describe **two** user-centred design features you would use in the design of your system for John and Mary.

OUTPUT

User-centered design (UCD) is a design philosophy where the needs, wants, and limitations of the end user of a product are given extensive attention at each stage of the design process. Here are two UCD features that could be used in the design of the system for John and Mary:

1. **Easy Navigation:** The system should be designed with a straightforward and intuitive user interface. Users should be able to find what they're looking for easily, whether it's information about a specific service, the online store, or contact information. This could be achieved by incorporating a clear, concise menu in the header and a sitemap in the footer. A breadcrumb navigation could also be helpful to allow users to track their path or steps within the application.
2. **Personalization:** To enhance the user experience, the system could include personalized features such as recommending services or products based on the user's browsing history or preferences. For instance, if a user often orders dog grooming services, the system could highlight these services or offer related products, like premium shampoos or grooming tools. Personalization can make users feel valued and understood, which can promote user satisfaction and engagement.

In addition to these features, it would be important to incorporate accessibility features to ensure the system can be used by people with different abilities. This includes color contrasts for those with visual impairments, descriptive alt text for images, and keyboard navigation for those who can't use a mouse. It's also crucial to conduct user testing with real users to gather feedback and improve the system before the final implementation.

PROMPT

(iii) State **two** differences between wireframes and prototypes.

OUTPUT

JO

(iii) State two differences between wireframes and prototypes.

Wireframes and prototypes are both important elements of the design process, but they serve different purposes and contain different levels of detail:

1. **Level of Detail:** Wireframes are low-fidelity, simplified outlines of your product. They are like the blueprints of a building, showing where elements will be placed but not their exact look or functionality. Prototypes, on the other hand, are high-fidelity representations that simulate the interactions and functionality of the final product. They include more detail and often use colors, images, buttons, and even interactions.
2. **Functionality:** Wireframes primarily focus on layout and structure, not on functionality or aesthetics. They provide a visual guide of the page/screen structure and the placement of elements. Prototypes, however, are interactive and demonstrate functionality. They are used for user testing, as they offer a closer representation of the final product. You can click buttons, input data, navigate between different screens, etc., in a prototype.

These two stages of the design process allow designers and stakeholders to progressively refine and develop their ideas from a broad outline (wireframes) to a detailed, interactive model (prototype) before investing in the final development.

PROMPT

(iv) The checkout page will allow users to enter their delivery and payment details in order to finalise their order.

Provide **one** example of each of the following types of data that the system should collect on the checkout page.

1.

2.

String:

Integer:

Boolean:

OUTPUT

Sure, here are examples of these types of data the system should collect on the checkout page:

1. **String:** Customer's Full Name. This data is essential for delivery and order processing purposes.
2. **Integer:** The quantity of items being ordered. This is necessary to understand how many of a particular product the customer wants to purchase.
3. **Boolean:** Gift wrap option - Yes or No. This would be used to understand whether the customer wants the order to be gift wrapped or not.

PROMPT

Question 14

(a) A simplified version of the selection sort algorithm involves the use of two lists called `list1` and `list2`. At the start of the algorithm the elements in `list1` are unsorted, and `list2` is empty as shown.

```
list1:  
list2:
```

At the end of the algorithm `list1` is empty, and `list2` contains the elements that were in `list1` at the start, now sorted in *ascending* order.

```
list1:  
list2:
```

The algorithm is described by the following pseudo-code:

1. Let N be the number of elements in `list1`
2. Initialise an empty list of length N - call this `list2`
3. Repeat N times:
4. Select the smallest (minimum) element from `list1`
5. Move the smallest element from `list1` to `list2`
6. Stop

(i) Apply the algorithm to sort the list of integers [15, 28, 14, 21] showing the state of both lists after each pass of the algorithm. Pass #1 has been completed for you. You only need to fill in the numbers for passes 2, 3 and 4.

Initial State

```
list1:  
list2:
```

State after Pass #1

```
list1:  
list2:
```

State after Pass #2

```
list1:  
list2:
```

State after Pass #3

```
list1:  
list2:
```

State after Pass #4

```
list1:  
list2:
```

OUTPUT

Sure, let's walk through the steps of this simplified version of the selection sort algorithm with the given list [15, 28, 14, 21]:

Initial State:

list1: [15, 28, 14, 21]

list2: []

State after Pass #1:

list1: [15, 28, 21] (14 is removed as it is the smallest element)

list2: [14] (14 is moved to list2)

State after Pass #2:

list1: [28, 21] (15 is removed as it is the smallest element)

list2: [14, 15] (15 is moved to list2)

State after Pass #3:

list1: [28] (21 is removed as it is the smallest element)

list2: [14, 15, 21] (21 is moved to list2)

State after Pass #4:

list1: [] (28 is removed as it is the smallest and only remaining element)

list2: [14, 15, 21, 28] (28 is moved to list2)

By the end of pass 4, list1 is empty and list2 contains the original elements, now sorted in ascending order.

PROMPT

(ii) The algorithm sorts the list in ascending order. What changes would you need to make to the algorithm so that it sorts the list in *descending order*?

OUTPUT

To modify the algorithm to sort the list in descending order, you would need to alter step 4. Instead of selecting the smallest (minimum) element from list1, you would select the largest (maximum) element. Here is the modified algorithm:

1. Let N be the number of elements in list1.
2. Initialise an empty list of length N – call this list2.
3. Repeat N times:
4. Select the largest (maximum) element from list1.
5. Move the largest element from list1 to list2.
6. Stop.

With this modification, each pass of the algorithm will move the largest remaining element from list1 to list2, resulting in a sorted list in descending order.

PROMPT

(iii) Step 4 of the algorithm says to select the smallest (minimum) element from list1. Outline a method to find the smallest element in any list.

OUTPUT

To find the smallest element in a list, you can use a simple method that involves comparing each element in the list to a variable that keeps track of the smallest value found so far. The process is as follows:

1. Initialize a variable, for example "minElement", to the first value of the list. This variable will keep track of the smallest value we've encountered so far in our search.
2. Loop through the rest of the list, comparing each element with "minElement". If the current element in the list is less than "minElement", then we update "minElement" to be the current element.
3. Continue this process until we've looked at every element in the list. When the loop finishes, "minElement" will hold the smallest value in the list.

Here's a pseudo-code representation of the process:

pseudo

Copy code

```
let minElement = list1[0]

for each element in list1:
    if element < minElement:
        minElement = element

return minElement
```

This method assumes that the list has at least one element and that the elements are comparable (for example, they are all numbers or all strings).

PROMPT

(iv) Step 5 of the algorithm says to *move* the smallest element from `list1` to `list2`. Why would the algorithm not work if this step said to *copy* the smallest element from `list1` to `list2`?

OUTPUT

If the step indicated to copy the smallest element from `list1` to `list2` instead of moving it, the algorithm wouldn't work as intended because the smallest element would remain in `list1`. As a result, during the next iteration, the algorithm would identify the same element as the smallest again, leading to duplicates of the smallest element in `list2`. This means the sorting process would never progress beyond the smallest element, creating an infinite loop and not achieving the desired outcome of sorting the list.

The fundamental purpose of the sorting algorithm is to reorganize the elements in a certain order (in this case, ascending). If elements are just copied and not removed from the original list, the state of the original list doesn't change, and the algorithm cannot make progress towards the goal of sorting the elements. Thus, it's crucial to move (or remove and insert) the elements, not just copy them.

PROMPT

(v) The algorithm relies on two lists to complete the sort. Describe a selection sort algorithm that would sort a list 'in place' i.e. without the need for a second list.

OUTPUT

An in-place selection sort algorithm would sort the given list without requiring a separate list for storing the sorted elements. Here's a description of the in-place selection sort algorithm:

1. Iterate over each element of the list. The current element will act as a divider between the sorted and unsorted parts of the list. At the beginning, the sorted part is empty and the entire list is considered unsorted.
2. For each iteration, find the smallest element in the unsorted part of the list.
3. Swap this smallest element with the first element in the unsorted part of the list. Now, this smallest element is included in the sorted part, and the list divider moves one position to the right.
4. Repeat the process until the entire list is sorted.

By this method, the list is sorted in place, with a minimal amount of extra space needed (only for temporary storage during the swap operation). It's important to note that, while this method is space-efficient, selection sort, in general, is not considered an efficient algorithm for large lists due to its $O(n^2)$ time complexity.

PROMPT

(b)

A bookshelf is partially sorted, in alphabetic order, using the insertion sort algorithm as shown in **Figure 4** below.

(i) Fill in the empty boxes below to complete passes 3, 4, 5 and 6 of the insertion sort.

Initial List:

After Pass #1:

After Pass #2:

After Pass #3:

After Pass #4:

After Pass #5:

After Pass #6:

OUTPUT

I apologize for the misunderstanding, but as a text-based AI, I don't have the ability to see or manipulate visual content or fill in blank boxes directly. However, I can describe how to continue the insertion sort process based on a hypothetical initial list and passes. Here's a generic example:

Assuming that your initial list of books is as follows:

Initial List: ['F', 'E', 'D', 'C', 'B', 'A']

Here's how the list would look after each pass:

After Pass #1: ['E', 'F', 'D', 'C', 'B', 'A']

After Pass #2: ['D', 'E', 'F', 'C', 'B', 'A']

After Pass #3: ['C', 'D', 'E', 'F', 'B', 'A']

After Pass #4: ['B', 'C', 'D', 'E', 'F', 'A']

After Pass #5: ['A', 'B', 'C', 'D', 'E', 'F']

This example illustrates the insertion sort process, where each book (or element) is iteratively moved to its correct position in the sorted part of the list. If your list of books is different, please provide it, and I can adapt the example accordingly.

PROMPT

(ii) Explain how the insertion sort algorithm works.

OUTPUT

The Insertion Sort algorithm works by iteratively placing each element in the array (or list) in its appropriate position within the sorted portion of the array. Here's a step-by-step explanation:

1. **Selection:** The algorithm starts at the second element of the array. It considers this element as a "key". This key element is the one that the algorithm will attempt to move into its correct position.
2. **Comparison:** The key is compared to the elements before it in the array. If an element larger than the key is found, that element is moved one position to the right.
3. **Insertion:** This process continues until the algorithm encounters an element smaller than the key, or it reaches the start of the array. At that point, it inserts the key into the open position (which has been vacated by shifting the larger elements to the right).
4. **Iteration:** The algorithm then moves to the next element in the array and repeats the above process.

This continues until the algorithm has processed all the elements in the array. At that point, the array will be sorted in ascending order. The algorithm gets its name because it sorts the array by iteratively "inserting" each element into its correct position within the sorted part of the array.

In a nutshell, insertion sort builds a sorted list one element at a time, with the advantage that it can stop early if the list is partially sorted, making it an adaptive sorting algorithm. However, it has a poor average and worst-case time complexity ($O(n^2)$) which makes it less suitable for large datasets.

PROMPT

(iii) A list that is already reversed would be considered a good test case for the insertion sort algorithm. Describe **two** other test cases that could be used to test the insertion sort algorithm.

OUTPUT

1. **Random List:** A list with random numbers is a good test case for insertion sort. This scenario is one of the most common, as it doesn't imply any particular order in the elements. It allows the testing of the algorithm's robustness and effectiveness when dealing with unsorted input.
2. **Already Sorted List:** It may seem counter-intuitive, but a list that is already sorted (in ascending order) is a good test case for the insertion sort algorithm. It's beneficial to know how the algorithm handles a situation where no swaps or movements are required. In an optimal situation, the insertion sort should recognize this and avoid unnecessary operations, taking advantage of the sorted order to minimize its runtime. This test can help confirm whether the algorithm is adaptive, i.e., whether it can adjust its operation to the existing order of the input.

In both test cases, it would be beneficial to not only test with different lengths of lists but also with different types of data (if applicable) like integers, floating-point numbers, or strings. Furthermore, including duplicates and unique elements in the list could provide additional robustness to the testing.

PROMPT

(iv) "Big O" notation is used to describe the complexity of an algorithm. Discuss the algorithmic complexity of the insertion sort algorithm using "Big O" notation.

OUTPUT

The "Big O" notation is used to classify algorithms according to how their running time or space requirements grow as the input size increases. It provides an upper bound on the time complexity, offering a worst-case scenario insight.

In the case of the insertion sort algorithm:

1. **Best Case ($O(n)$):** The best-case scenario is when the input array is already sorted. In this case, the algorithm needs only to pass through the array once to confirm the order, so it runs in linear time, $O(n)$, where 'n' is the number of elements in the array.
2. **Average Case ($O(n^2)$):** If the input array is in a random order, on average, the algorithm has a quadratic time complexity, $O(n^2)$. This is because for each element, it may need to compare with all other elements before it, leading to a series of nested loops as it traverses.
3. **Worst Case ($O(n^2)$):** The worst-case scenario is when the input array is sorted in reverse order. In this situation, each element has to be compared with every other element before it, leading to a quadratic time complexity, $O(n^2)$.

Insertion sort is thus an efficient algorithm for small datasets or nearly sorted lists, but it becomes inefficient as the size of the input grows due to its quadratic time complexity.

PROMPT

Question 15

A check digit is a single digit number used to verify numbers such as barcodes, credit cards and International Standard Book Numbers (ISBNs), thereby helping to prevent data entry errors.

Check digits usually appear as the rightmost digit (position 1) of a number. For example, the check digit of the ISBN number, 1020041102 highlighted here is 2.

The general procedure used to verify ISBN numbers is as follows:

Step 1: Multiply each digit in the number by its own digit position.

Step 2: Add the 10 results together.

Step 3: Divide the total by 11.

Step 4: If the remainder is zero the ISBN number is deemed to be valid.

(a) Apply the above procedure to verify that the ISBN number 1020041102 is valid.

OUTPUT

Let's verify the ISBN number 1020041102 using the given procedure:

Step 1: Multiply each digit in the number by its own digit position.

From right to left, the positions are:

Position: 10 9 8 7 6 5 4 3 2 1

Number: 1 0 2 0 0 4 1 1 0 2

We multiply each digit by its position:

$$101 + 90 + 82 + 70 + 60 + 54 + 41 + 31 + 20 + 12$$

Step 2: Add the 10 results together.

This results in:

$$10 + 0 + 16 + 0 + 0 + 20 + 4 + 3 + 0 + 2 = 55$$

Step 3: Divide the total by 11.

55 divided by 11 is 5, with no remainder.

Step 4: If the remainder is zero, the ISBN number is deemed to be valid.

In this case, the remainder is not zero, which means that the ISBN number 1020041102 is not valid according to the given procedure. There seems to be a mistake because the ISBN number was said to be valid, but according to the procedure, it's not. Please double-check the ISBN number or the verification process.

PROMPT

(b) Given a 9-digit number, the Python program below can be used to find the number's check digit, that will be used as the 10th digit.

```
1 # A program to determine a check digit for a number
2 isbn = "102004110"
3 total = 0
4 for i in range(10, 1, -1):
5 total = total + int(isbn[10-i]) * i
6
7 check_digit = 11 - (total % 11)
8 print("The check digit for", isbn, "is", check_digit)
```

(i) Line 1 of the above program contains a comment.
State **two** reasons why programmers use comments.

OUTPUT

Programmers use comments for several reasons, two of which are:

1. **Code Explanation:** Comments are used to explain what a particular piece of code or section of code does. They help in understanding the purpose and functionality of the code. This is especially helpful when revisiting the code after a long time or when someone else is trying to understand your code.
2. **Documentation:** Comments are a form of documentation. They can be used to provide additional information like author of the code, creation date, last modification date, and more. They can also be used to explain the inputs, outputs, and algorithms used in the code. This helps in understanding the context and background of the code.

PROMPT

(ii) The program makes use of a number of variables and data types. Explain the terms variable and data type using one example of each from the code.

OUTPUT

A variable in programming refers to a storage location paired with an associated symbolic name, which contains some known or unknown quantity of information referred to as a value. The variable name is the usual way to reference the stored value. In the provided code, "total" is an example of a variable. It is initially set to 0, and then it is updated throughout the code to keep track of the cumulative total.

A data type refers to the kind of value a variable can hold. It determines what operations can be performed on the data. Python, being a dynamically-typed language, infers the data type based on the value assigned to the variable. In the code provided, the "isbn" variable is a string data type as it holds a sequence of characters. The "total" and "check_digit" variables are integers, as they hold whole numbers.

PROMPT

(iii) The program makes use of the Python int function.
Outline the purpose of the int function as it is used in the code.

OUTPUT

The `int()` function in Python is used to convert a value into an integer data type. In the given code, `int(isbn[10-i])` is used to convert the characters (digits in this case) from the string `isbn` into integer values.

Each character in the `isbn` string represents a digit, but since they are part of a string, Python treats them as characters, not numeric values. The `int()` function is used to change these characters into integers, so mathematical operations can be performed on them. In this case, each digit is being multiplied by its position in the `isbn` string, which would not be possible without converting the character to an integer first.

PROMPT

(iv) The range function on line 4 of the program generates a sequence of every integer from 10 down to 1 (but not including 1). Describe one way these integers are used in the program.

OUTPUT

In the program, the integers generated by the `range` function are used as multipliers to weigh each digit in the ISBN number according to its position.

Specifically, these integers are used within the for-loop to reverse-index the `isbn` string and multiply each digit by its corresponding position. For instance, the tenth digit (from the right) in the ISBN number is multiplied by 10, the ninth digit is multiplied by 9, and so on. This weighted sum is stored in the `total` variable.

This technique is part of the calculation process to determine the check digit for an ISBN number.

PROMPT

(c)

The Python program below shows an alternative implementation.

```
1 # A program to determine a check digit for a number
2 isbn = 102004110
3 isbn1 = isbn
4 total = 0
5 for i in range(2, 11):
6     digit = isbn % 10
7     total = total + digit*i
8     isbn = isbn//10
9
10 check_digit = 11 - (total % 11)
11 print("The check digit for", isbn1, "is", check_digit)
```

(i) Complete the trace table below to show the changing states of the variables during program execution.

i	digit	total	isbn
0			102004110
2	0	0	10200411
3	1	3	1020041
4	1	7	102004
5	4	27	10200
6	0	27	1020
7			
8			
9			
10			

OUTPUT

You've made a good start with the trace table. Here's the completed version:

i	digit	total	isbn
-	-	0	102004110
2	0	0	10200411
3	1	3	1020041
4	1	7	102004
5	4	27	10200
6	0	27	1020
7	2	41	102
8	0	41	10
9	1	50	1
10	1	60	0

In each iteration of the loop, the digit at the end of `isbn` is extracted using the modulo operation `isbn % 10`. This digit is then multiplied by `i` and added to `total`. The `isbn` is then truncated by one digit using the floor division operation `isbn // 10`.

This process continues until `isbn` is 0 (i.e., until all the digits have been processed). After the loop, the check digit is calculated as `11 - (total % 11)`.

PROMPT

(ii) What is the purpose of the variable called `isbn1` in the program?

OUTPUT

The `isbn1` variable is used to store the original value of the `isbn` variable. As the program executes, the `isbn` variable is manipulated and its value changes. By storing the original value in `isbn1`, the program can later reference the original `isbn` number, specifically in the print statement on line 11, where it prints out the original `isbn` and the calculated check digit. Without `isbn1`, the original `isbn` number would be lost after it is manipulated.

PROMPT

(iii) The program makes use of a number of arithmetic operators. State the purpose of each of the operators listed below.

OUTPUT

Certainly, I can explain what each of these operators do in Python. Note that the operators are being explained generally, and their specific application may vary depending on the context of the code.

1. `+` (Addition): The `+` operator is used to add two values together. If the operands are integers or floating-point numbers, the operation is arithmetic addition. If the operands are strings, `+` performs string concatenation.
2. `*` (Multiplication): The `*` operator is used to multiply two values together. It performs arithmetic multiplication.
3. `%` (Modulus): The `%` operator is used to find the remainder of the division of the number before the operator (the dividend) by the number after the operator (the divisor).
4. `//` (Integer Division): The `//` operator is used for integer division. It divides the dividend by the divisor and then rounds the result down to the nearest whole number to return an integer value. For example, `9 // 2` would return 4, not 4.5.
5. `-` (Subtraction): The `-` operator is used to subtract the value on its right from the value on its left.

PROMPT

(iv) Identify **two** key differences between the algorithms used in parts **(b)** and **(c)**.

OUTPUT

The two key differences between the algorithms used in parts (b) and (c) are:

1. **Data type of ISBN:** In part (b), the ISBN number is treated as a string, while in part (c), it's treated as an integer. This affects how the program interacts with the ISBN number. In part (b), the program accesses each digit as a separate character in the string and then converts it to an integer, whereas in part (c), the program manipulates the integer using mathematical operations to isolate each digit.
2. **Direction of Processing:** In part (b), the algorithm processes the digits from left to right (from the first digit to the last). It uses the decreasing sequence from 10 to 2 (exclusive) to assign weights for the calculation of the check digit. In contrast, part (c) processes the digits from right to left (from the last digit to the first). It uses an increasing sequence from 2 to 11 to assign weights. This is reflected in the different range parameters in the two algorithms.

These differences illustrate how the same problem can be approached in different ways in programming, often with minor differences in the details of the solution.

PROMPT

(v) Provide an example of **one** type of data entry error a check digit could be used to prevent.

OUTPUT

A check digit can be used to prevent transcription errors. A transcription error is a mistake that occurs when data is copied from one medium to another. For instance, when an ISBN number is manually typed into a system, a digit might be inadvertently omitted, inserted, or mistyped, or two successive digits might be transposed.

For example, if the ISBN "1020041102" were mistakenly entered as "1200041102" (where the first two digits have been transposed), the check digit verification process would fail, thereby alerting the person entering the data that an error has occurred. This form of error checking is particularly useful in situations where large amounts of data need to be manually entered into a system.

Section C PROMPT

Question 16

a)

The program simulates the rolling of a die 100 times.

The result of each roll (throw) is stored in a variable called `throw_result`. Each of the 100 results are appended to a list called `results` as they are generated.

The program also contains code to keep track of the number of times a one and a two are rolled. These are stored in a list called `frequencies`.

```
1 # Question 16(a)
2 # Examination Number:
3 from random import randint
4
5 print("Dice simulation program")
6 results = []
7 frequencies = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
8
9 # Loop 100 times
10 for i in range (100):
11     throw_result = randint(1,6) # store a random value between 1 and 6
12     results.append(throw_result) # append each value to results
13
14 # Start to build up a list of frequencies for each value thrown
15 if throw_result == 1:
16     frequencies[0] = frequencies[0] + 1
17 elif throw_result == 2:
18     frequencies[1] = frequencies[1] + 1
19
20 print()
21 print("Results:", results)
```

When the program is run, the output may look as follows:

(Your output will be different because the dice numbers are generated randomly.)

Dice simulation program

```
Results: [1, 4, 1, 4, 2, 3, 2, 2, 2, 4, 3, 1, 6, 1, 3, 3, 5,
1, 1, 3, 2, 2, 4, 1, 6, 4, 4, 5, 2, 2, 4, 2, 1, 2, 4, 2, 6, 6,
5, 4, 3, 5, 5, 1, 1, 6, 5, 1, 3, 3, 5, 3, 1, 5, 3, 5, 3, 2, 1,
1, 1, 1, 4, 2, 5, 6, 4, 3, 4, 6, 4, 5, 2, 5, 5, 3, 1, 5, 4, 3,
2, 2, 6, 2, 2, 3, 3, 2, 3, 1, 5, 2, 5, 4, 6, 4, 3, 5, 5, 2]
```

Make the following changes to the program:

(i) Currently the first line in the program output is *Dice simulation program*.

Change the program so that the first line in the output is *Dice simulation and analysis program*.

When the program is run the output may now look as follows:

Dice simulation and analysis program

```
Results: [1, 4, 1, 5, 3, 6, 2, 6, 6, 1, 3, 6, 4, 5, 1, 2, 5,
3, 5, 6, 5, 6, 5, 3, 3, 3, 4, 1, 2, 6, 1, 2, 4, 4, 6, 2, 4, 6,
5, 3, 4, 6, 4, 1, 4, 5, 6, 1, 1, 3, 5, 6, 6, 1, 2, 2, 5, 4, 3,
2, 6, 2, 2, 2, 1, 2, 3, 4, 3, 3, 4, 3, 1, 6, 4, 1, 2, 4, 1,
3, 4, 1, 5, 3, 3, 5, 4, 4, 1, 2, 4, 4, 5, 6, 5, 6, 1, 5, 3]
```

OUTPUT

Sure, to change the output message from "Dice simulation program" to "Dice simulation and analysis program", you only need to modify the print statement on line 5.

Here's the modified code:

```
python Copy code  
  
1 # Question 16(a)  
2 # Examination Number:  
3 from random import randint  
4  
5 print("Dice simulation and analysis program") # Changed output message here  
6 results = []  
7 frequencies = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]  
8  
9 # Loop 100 times  
10 for i in range(100):  
11     throw_result = randint(1,6) # store a random value between 1 and 6  
12     results.append(throw_result) # append each value to results  
13  
14     # Start to build up a list of frequencies for each value thrown  
15     if throw_result == 1:  
16         frequencies[0] = frequencies[0] + 1  
17     elif throw_result == 2:  
18         frequencies[1] = frequencies[1] + 1  
19  
20 print()  
21 print("Results:", results)
```

Now, when you run this program, the first line of the output will be "Dice simulation and analysis program". The rest of the program remains unchanged, so it will still simulate the dice rolls and store the results as before.

PROMPT

(ii)

Insert a new line of code at the end of the program to display the list of dice frequencies.

When the program is run the output may now look as follows:

Dice simulation and analysis program

```
Results: [1, 3, 5, 1, 5, 1, 2, 4, 2, 5, 5, 5, 6, 4, 1, 1, 6,
4, 2, 1, 2, 6, 5, 3, 6, 5, 3, 6, 3, 3, 2, 1, 4, 2, 3, 4, 6, 6,
3, 3, 6, 5, 6, 6, 6, 5, 3, 2, 1, 3, 3, 6, 1, 4, 2, 5, 6, 4, 2,
1, 6, 6, 6, 4, 2, 2, 4, 5, 6, 3, 2, 6, 2, 2, 3, 3, 3, 1, 5, 6,
3, 6, 2, 5, 5, 1, 4, 5, 4, 1, 5, 4, 6, 4, 4, 5, 3, 3, 1, 4]
```

```
Frequencies: [14, 15, 0, 0, 0, 0]
```

The frequencies list tells us that the number one has been rolled 14 times and the number two has been rolled 15 times.

The frequencies for the numbers three, four, five and six are not calculated by the program yet. This is the reason they are all zero.

OUTPUT

Sure, to display the list of dice frequencies at the end of the program, you only need to add a new print statement after the existing ones.

Here's the modified code:

python

Copy code

```
1 # Question 16(a)
2 # Examination Number:
3 from random import randint
4
5 print("Dice simulation and analysis program")
6 results = []
7 frequencies = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
8
9 # Loop 100 times
10 for i in range(100):
11     throw_result = randint(1,6) # store a random value between 1 and 6
12     results.append(throw_result) # append each value to results
13
14     # Start to build up a list of frequencies for each value thrown
15     if throw_result == 1:
16         frequencies[0] = frequencies[0] + 1
17     elif throw_result == 2:
18         frequencies[1] = frequencies[1] + 1
19
20 print()
21 print("Results:", results)
22 print("Frequencies:", frequencies) # Added this line to print frequencies
```

This new line (line 22) will print out the 'frequencies' list, which contains the frequencies of the numbers one and two being rolled. As per the existing logic in the program, it does not calculate frequencies for the numbers three, four, five, and six. Hence, those values are printed as zero.

PROMPT

(iii)

Complete the code to calculate the frequencies for the numbers three, four, five and six.

When the program is run the output may now look as follows:

Dice simulation and analysis program

Results: [2, 4, 6, 2, 1, 4, 1, 3, 1, 3, 3, 6, 5, 5, 4, 3, 2,
2, 2, 1, 3, 4, 4, 3, 4, 6, 4, 2, 3, 1, 3, 3, 1, 5, 3, 3, 6, 5,
4, 6, 1, 5, 3, 4, 2, 1, 6, 6, 5, 2, 6, 4, 5, 2, 2, 6, 6, 5, 5,
6, 2, 3, 5, 6, 4, 1, 6, 2, 2, 6, 2, 6, 3, 3, 4, 2, 5, 5, 5, 3,
1, 2, 3, 4, 2, 6, 2, 1, 5, 6, 6, 2, 5, 2, 3, 2, 5, 2, 2, 6]

Frequencies: [11, 23, 18, 13, 16, 19]

In this case the frequencies list tells us that the number one has been rolled 11 times, the number two has been rolled 23 times, the number three has been rolled 18 times, the number four has been rolled 13 times, the number five has been rolled 16 times and the number six has been rolled 19 times.

OUTPUT

To calculate the frequencies for the numbers three, four, five, and six, we need to add the equivalent conditional branches for these numbers in the if-elif structure within the loop.

Here's the completed code:

python

Copy code

```
1 # Question 16(a)
2 # Examination Number:
3 from random import randint
4
5 print("Dice simulation and analysis program")
6 results = []
7 frequencies = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
8
9 # Loop 100 times
10 for i in range(100):
11     throw_result = randint(1,6) # store a random value between 1 and 6
12     results.append(throw_result) # append each value to results
13
```

```
14 # Start to build up a list of frequencies for each value thrown
15 if throw_result == 1:
16     frequencies[0] = frequencies[0] + 1
17 elif throw_result == 2:
18     frequencies[1] = frequencies[1] + 1
19 elif throw_result == 3: # Added code for frequency of 3
20     frequencies[2] = frequencies[2] + 1
21 elif throw_result == 4: # Added code for frequency of 4
22     frequencies[3] = frequencies[3] + 1
23 elif throw_result == 5: # Added code for frequency of 5
24     frequencies[4] = frequencies[4] + 1
25 elif throw_result == 6: # Added code for frequency of 6
26     frequencies[5] = frequencies[5] + 1
27
28 print()
29 print("Results:", results)
30 print("Frequencies:", frequencies)
```

This updated code will now correctly calculate and print the frequencies for all numbers between one and six. The 'frequencies' list contains the frequency of each dice value from one to six, in that order.

PROMPT

(iv)

Comment out the line that displays the list of individual results.

When the program is run the output may now look as follows:

Dice simulation and analysis program
Frequencies: [17, 21, 17, 18, 11, 16]

OUTPUT

To stop displaying the list of individual results, you just need to add a comment symbol (#) before the line that prints the "Results". Here's how to do it:

python

Copy code

```
1 # Question 16(a)
2 # Examination Number:
3 from random import randint
4
5 print("Dice simulation and analysis program")
6 results = []
7 frequencies = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
8
9 # Loop 100 times
10 for i in range(100):
11     throw_result = randint(1,6) # store a random value between 1 and 6
12     results.append(throw_result) # append each value to results
13
```

```
14 # Start to build up a list of frequencies for each value thrown
15 if throw_result == 1:
16     frequencies[0] = frequencies[0] + 1
17 elif throw_result == 2:
18     frequencies[1] = frequencies[1] + 1
19 elif throw_result == 3: # Added code for frequency of 3
20     frequencies[2] = frequencies[2] + 1
21 elif throw_result == 4: # Added code for frequency of 4
22     frequencies[3] = frequencies[3] + 1
23 elif throw_result == 5: # Added code for frequency of 5
24     frequencies[4] = frequencies[4] + 1
25 elif throw_result == 6: # Added code for frequency of 6
26     frequencies[5] = frequencies[5] + 1
27
28 print()
29 #print("Results:", results) # Commented out this line
30 print("Frequencies:", frequencies)
```

Now when you run the program, it will only print out the "Frequencies" and not the individual "Results". The list of results is still being generated and used to calculate the frequencies, but it is not being displayed to the user.

PROMPT

(v)

Extend the program to display the frequency of each number in a tabular format as shown in the sample output here.

Dice simulation and analysis program
Frequencies: [15, 10, 25, 15, 15, 20]

Dice Frequency

```
-----  
1 15  
2 10  
3 25  
4 15  
5 15  
6 20
```

OUTPUT

To display the frequency of each number in a tabular format, you need to modify the print statement that prints the 'frequencies' list.

Here's how to do it:

python

Copy code

```
1 # Question 16(a)  
2 # Examination Number:  
3 from random import randint  
4  
5 print("Dice simulation and analysis program")  
6 results = []  
7 frequencies = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]  
8  
9 # Loop 100 times  
10 for i in range (100):  
11     throw_result = randint(1,6) # store a random value between 1 and 6  
12     results.append(throw_result) # append each value to results  
13
```

```

14 # Start to build up a list of frequencies for each value thrown
15 if throw_result == 1:
16     frequencies[0] = frequencies[0] + 1
17 elif throw_result == 2:
18     frequencies[1] = frequencies[1] + 1
19 elif throw_result == 3: # Added code for frequency of 3
20     frequencies[2] = frequencies[2] + 1
21 elif throw_result == 4: # Added code for frequency of 4
22     frequencies[3] = frequencies[3] + 1
23 elif throw_result == 5: # Added code for frequency of 5
24     frequencies[4] = frequencies[4] + 1
25 elif throw_result == 6: # Added code for frequency of 6
26     frequencies[5] = frequencies[5] + 1
27
28 print()
29 #print("Results:", results) # Commented out this line
30 print("Frequencies:", frequencies)
31 print("Dice Frequency")
32 print("----")
33 for i in range(6):
34     print(f"{i+1} {frequencies[i]}") # Print dice number and its frequen

```

In this code, a new loop has been added after printing the "Frequencies" list. This loop goes through each element of the 'frequencies' list and prints the dice number (i + 1) and its corresponding frequency. The f-string format is used to print the values in a formatted way.

PROMPT

(vi)

Extend the program so that it determines and displays the number that was rolled most often along with its frequency. For example, in the output below the number five was rolled most often (25 times). You can ignore the possibility of ties.

When the program is run the output may now look as follows:

```
Dice simulation and analysis program
Frequencies: [16, 14, 12, 20, 25, 13]
Dice Frequency
```

```
----
1 16
2 14
3 12
4 20
5 25
6 13
5 was rolled the most often (25 times)
```

OUTPUT

To find the number that was rolled most often, you can use Python's `max()` function to find the highest frequency, and the `index()` method to find the dice number corresponding to that frequency.

Here's how to extend the program:

```
python Copy code
1 # Question 16(a)
2 # Examination Number:
3 from random import randint
4
5 print("Dice simulation and analysis program")
6 results = []
7 frequencies = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
8
9 # Loop 100 times
10 for i in range(100):
11     throw_result = randint(1,6) # store a random value between 1 and 6
12     results.append(throw_result) # append each value to results
13
14     # Start to build up a list of frequencies for each value thrown
15     if throw_result == 1:
16         frequencies[0] = frequencies[0] + 1
17     elif throw_result == 2:
18         frequencies[1] = frequencies[1] + 1
```

```

19     elif throw_result == 3: # Added code for frequency of 3
20         frequencies[2] = frequencies[2] + 1
21     elif throw_result == 4: # Added code for frequency of 4
22         frequencies[3] = frequencies[3] + 1
23     elif throw_result == 5: # Added code for frequency of 5
24         frequencies[4] = frequencies[4] + 1
25     elif throw_result == 6: # Added code for frequency of 6
26         frequencies[5] = frequencies[5] + 1
27
28 print()
29 #print("Results:", results) # Commented out this line
30 print("Frequencies:", frequencies)
31 print("Dice Frequency")
32 print("----")
33 for i in range(6):
34     print(f"{i+1} {frequencies[i]}") # Print dice number and its frequency
35
36 most_frequent_number = frequencies.index(max(frequencies)) + 1
37 most_frequent_count = max(frequencies)
38 print(f"{most_frequent_number} was rolled the most often ({most_frequent_

```

This code calculates the most frequent number and its count after printing the dice frequencies. The `index()` method gives the index of the maximum value in the list, and we add 1 to it to get the dice number (since list indices start at 0). The `max()` function gives the maximum value in the list, which is the highest frequency.

PROMPT

(vii)
Extend the program to display a horizontal bar chart of the frequencies.
The number of asterisks (*) in each row should correspond to each frequency. For example, in the output below there are eight asterisks in row one because the frequency for the number one is eight.
Each asterisk (*) can be printed using the single statement: `print("*", end="")`
When the program is run the output may now look as follows:
Dice simulation and analysis program
Dice frequencies: [8, 12, 22, 26, 22, 10]
Dice Frequency

1 8
2 12
3 22
4 26
5 22
6 10
4 was rolled most often - 26 times

OUTPUT

To display a horizontal bar chart, you can add a new loop after printing the dice frequency table. This loop will iterate over each frequency, and for each frequency, it will print an asterisk '*' that many times. Here's how to extend the program:

python

Copy code

```
1 # Question 16(a)
2 # Examination Number:
3 from random import randint
4
5 print("Dice simulation and analysis program")
6 results = []
7 frequencies = [0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0]
8
9 # Loop 100 times
10 for i in range(100):
11     throw_result = randint(1,6) # store a random value between 1 and 6
12     results.append(throw_result) # append each value to results
13
14     # Start to build up a list of frequencies for each value thrown
15     if throw_result == 1:
16         frequencies[0] = frequencies[0] + 1
17     elif throw_result == 2:
18         frequencies[1] = frequencies[1] + 1
19     elif throw_result == 3: # Added code for frequency of 3
20         frequencies[2] = frequencies[2] + 1
```

```

21     elif throw_result == 4: # Added code for frequency of 4
22         frequencies[3] = frequencies[3] + 1
23     elif throw_result == 5: # Added code for frequency of 5
24         frequencies[4] = frequencies[4] + 1
25     elif throw_result == 6: # Added code for frequency of 6
26         frequencies[5] = frequencies[5] + 1
27
28 print()
29 #print("Results:", results) # Commented out this line
30 print("Frequencies:", frequencies)
31 print("Dice Frequency")
32 print("----")
33 for i in range(6):
34     print(f"{i+1} {frequencies[i]}") # Print dice number and its frequency
35
36 most_frequent_number = frequencies.index(max(frequencies)) + 1
37 most_frequent_count = max(frequencies)
38 print(f"{most_frequent_number} was rolled the most often ({most_frequent_count} times)")
39
40 # Print bar chart
41 for i in range(6):
42     print("*" * frequencies[i]) # Print '*' character as many times as the frequency

```

This code adds the bar chart after calculating the most frequent number and its count. For each frequency, it prints the "character that many times. The `print("*" * frequencies[i])` line does the printing: the " character is repeated `frequencies[i]` times, and the `end=""` argument ensures that a newline character is not automatically added to the end of the print.

(2)

**Leaving Certificate Examination 2021
Computer Science
Higher Level**

ChatGPT Prompts and Output

May 2023

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PROMPT

Question 1

What is the output of the following piece of Python code?

```
1 x = 3
2 print("x is", x)
3
4 y = x
5 x = x+4
6 print(x, y)
7
8 x = y*2
9 print(x, 2**y)
10
11 y = x-y-1
12 print("y is y")
```

OUTPUT

The output of the given Python code will be as follows:

```
csharp Copy code
x is 3
7 3
6 8
y is y
```

Here's a breakdown of the code execution:

1. Line 1: `x` is assigned the value `3`.
2. Line 2: The string "x is" and the value of `x` (3) are printed.
3. Line 4: `y` is assigned the value of `x` (3).
4. Line 5: `x` is updated to be `x + 4`, so `x` becomes `7`.
5. Line 6: The updated values of `x` (7) and `y` (3) are printed.
6. Line 8: `x` is updated to be `y \* 2`, so `x` becomes `6`.
7. Line 9: The updated value of `x` (6) and 2 raised to the power of `y` ($2^{**}3=8$) are printed.
8. Line 11: `y` is updated to be `x - y - 1`, but this calculation is not printed.
9. Line 12: The string "y is y" is printed.

PROMPT

Question 2

(a) Explain why data is stored in computers in binary format.

OUTPUT

(a) Data is stored in computers in binary format for several reasons:

1. **Simplicity:** Binary format is based on only two digits, 0 and 1. This simplicity makes it easier to build electronic components and circuits that represent and manipulate binary data. Binary logic can be implemented using simple electronic switches, such as transistors, which have two states: on (1) and off (0).
2. **Noise immunity:** Binary representation is less susceptible to noise and signal degradation compared to other numeral systems with more digits. In a binary system, a small fluctuation in voltage or current will not cause a significant change in the data interpretation, as it only needs to differentiate between two states.
3. **Efficient data storage and processing:** Binary format is efficient for storing and processing data in digital systems. Most modern computer architectures use binary arithmetic, logic, and addressing schemes, which are inherently more efficient when dealing with binary data.
4. **Easy conversion:** Binary format can be easily converted to other numeral systems, like decimal or hexadecimal, which are more human-readable. This makes it convenient for programmers and users to work with data in different formats as needed.
5. **Consistency:** Using a single format (binary) to represent all types of data (numbers, characters, instructions, etc.) allows for consistency and compatibility across different systems, devices, and platforms. This simplifies the design and implementation of hardware and software systems.

PROMPT

- (b) A single bit can be used to represent two pieces of information.
(i) How many unique pieces of information could be represented using four bits?

OUTPUT

(b) (i) With four bits, you can represent 2^4 unique pieces of information, because each bit has two possible states (0 or 1). Therefore, using four bits, you can represent 16 unique pieces of information.

PROMPT

- (ii) What is the minimum number of bits required to represent eight unique pieces of information?

OUTPUT

(ii) To find the minimum number of bits required to represent eight unique pieces of information, you can use the formula $2^n = x$, where 'n' is the number of bits and 'x' is the number of unique pieces of information.

In this case, $x = 8$. You need to find the smallest integer value of 'n' that satisfies the equation:

$$2^n = 8$$

$$2^3 = 8$$

So, the minimum number of bits required to represent eight unique pieces of information is 3.

PROMPT

Question 3

(a) State **two** differences between RAM and ROM.

OUTPUT

(a) Two differences between RAM (Random Access Memory) and ROM (Read-Only Memory) are:

1. Function and Usage:

- RAM is a volatile memory used to temporarily store data and program instructions that are currently in use or being processed by the computer. RAM allows read and write operations, meaning that data can be both stored and retrieved from it. When the power is turned off, the data stored in RAM is lost.
- ROM is a non-volatile memory that stores essential data, such as the BIOS (Basic Input/Output System) or firmware, which is required for a computer to boot up and function properly. ROM allows only read operations, meaning that the data stored in it can be accessed but not modified. The data stored in ROM remains intact even when the power is turned off.

2. Speed and Capacity:

- RAM is generally faster than ROM, allowing for quick data retrieval and storage, which is crucial for smooth computer operation. However, RAM typically has lower storage capacity compared to ROM.
- ROM is usually slower than RAM in terms of data access, but it often has a larger storage capacity. The larger capacity is useful for storing essential and permanent data, like firmware, that should not be easily altered or lost.

PROMPT

(b) Explain how increasing the amount of RAM on a computer might improve its performance.

OUTPUT

(b) Increasing the amount of RAM on a computer can improve its performance in several ways:

1. **Multitasking:** With more RAM, a computer can handle more applications or tasks simultaneously without slowing down. This allows users to switch between applications more quickly and efficiently, improving overall productivity and user experience.
2. **Faster data access:** RAM is much faster than other storage devices like hard drives or SSDs. When a computer has more RAM, it can store more data and program instructions in this fast memory, reducing the need to access slower storage devices for information. This results in quicker data access and faster execution of tasks.
3. **Reduced reliance on virtual memory:** When a computer runs out of RAM, it starts using virtual memory, which is a portion of the hard drive or SSD that temporarily acts as additional RAM. However, accessing virtual memory is significantly slower than accessing RAM. Increasing the amount of RAM reduces the need for virtual memory, thus avoiding performance degradation caused by using slower storage devices as memory.
4. **Improved application performance:** Some applications, particularly resource-intensive ones like video editing software, video games, or large-scale data processing applications, require a large amount of memory to function optimally. Increasing RAM can significantly improve the performance and responsiveness of such applications, allowing them to run more smoothly and handle larger data sets.
5. **Faster boot and load times:** With more RAM, a computer can cache more data and load applications and files more quickly. This results in faster boot times and reduced loading times for applications, improving the overall performance and user experience.

PROMPT

Question 4

You are asked to swap the values of two variables, x and y , which have already been initialised.

(a) Why does the method shown not work?

(b) Describe a method that does work.

```
x = y
```

```
y = x
```

OUTPUT

(a) The method shown does not work because it does not actually swap the values of x and y .

When you execute `x = y`, the original value of x is overwritten by the value of y . As a result, when you execute `y = x` in the next line, both x and y will end up holding the same value (the original value of y). The original value of x is lost in the process, and the values are not swapped.

(b) To correctly swap the values of x and y , you can use a temporary variable or the Pythonic tuple unpacking method:

Method 1 - Using a temporary variable:

```
makefile  Copy code
```

```
temp = x
x = y
y = temp
```

In this method, the original value of x is first stored in a temporary variable called 'temp'. Then, the value of y is assigned to x , and finally, the original value of x (stored in 'temp') is assigned to y , effectively swapping the values of x and y .

Method 2 - Pythonic tuple unpacking:

```
 Copy code
```

```
x, y = y, x
```

This method utilizes tuple unpacking in Python. The values of x and y are packed into a tuple `(y, x)` and then immediately unpacked, assigning the value of y to x and the value of x to y . This is an elegant and concise way to swap the values of two variables in Python without using a temporary variable.

PROMPT

(b) Describe a method that does work.

OUTPUT

To correctly swap the values of two variables, x and y, you can use a temporary variable or the Pythonic tuple unpacking method:

Method 1 - Using a temporary variable:

makefile

Copy code

```
temp = x
x = y
y = temp
```

In this method, the original value of x is first stored in a temporary variable called 'temp'. Then, the value of y is assigned to x, and finally, the original value of x (stored in 'temp') is assigned to y, effectively swapping the values of x and y.

Method 2 - Pythonic tuple unpacking:

Copy code

```
x, y = y, x
```

This method utilizes tuple unpacking in Python. The values of x and y are packed into a tuple `(y, x)` and then immediately unpacked, assigning the value of y to x and the value of x to y. This is an elegant and concise way to swap the values of two variables in Python without using a temporary variable.

PROMPT

Question 5

The flowchart in **Figure 1** is a representation of an algorithm.

(a) Using inputs of 7, 3 and 8 for n , complete the trace table showing the execution of the algorithm.

OUTPUT

Unfortunately, I cannot see the flowchart in Figure 1 since I am a text-based AI model and cannot process images. However, I can help you complete the trace table if you provide me with the algorithm as text or describe the steps of the algorithm.

PROMPT

(b) What output does the algorithm display?

OUTPUT

In order to determine the output that the algorithm displays, I would need more information about the algorithm itself. Please provide the algorithm as text or describe the steps of the algorithm, so I can help you analyze it and determine the output.

PROMPT

Question 6

You have been asked to assess an algorithm for a travel agent. The company gives discounts based on the number of people in a group.

The Python code below determines the type of discount to give based on the number of adults (`num_adults`) and the number of children (`num_children`) in a travelling group.

```
1 num_adults = int(input("Enter the number of adults: "))
2 num_children = int(input("Enter the number of children: "))
3
4 if num_adults > 1 and num_children > 0:
5     print("Family discount")
6 elif num_adults >= 10:
7     print("Large group discount")
8 elif num_adults >= 5:
9     print("Small group discount")
10 else:
11     print("No discount")
```

Describe **two** scenarios where the algorithm could be perceived to be unfair.

OUTPUT

Scenario 1:

A group of 9 adults and 1 child is booking a trip. According to the algorithm, this group would be eligible for the "Family discount" because there is more than 1 adult and at least 1 child (lines 4-5). However, this group is quite large with 10 people in total, and it might be perceived as unfair that they don't receive the "Large group discount" which requires 10 or more adults (lines 6-7).

Scenario 2:

A group of 4 adults and 6 children is booking a trip, making a total of 10 people in the group. In this case, the algorithm would again apply the "Family discount" because there is more than 1 adult and at least 1 child (lines 4-5). However, the group might perceive this as unfair because they are a group of 10 people in total, just like the scenario 1, but they don't receive the "Large group discount" (lines 6-7) or even the "Small group discount" (lines 8-9), which requires 5 or more adults.

PROMPT

Question 7

(a) Differentiate between HTTP and HTTPS.

OUTPUT

(a) HTTP (Hypertext Transfer Protocol) and HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) are both protocols used for transmitting data over the internet, particularly for accessing websites. They have some key differences:

1. Security:

- HTTP is an unencrypted protocol, which means that the data transmitted between the client (e.g., a web browser) and the server (e.g., a website) is sent in plain text. This makes it vulnerable to interception, tampering, or eavesdropping by malicious actors during transmission.
- HTTPS, on the other hand, uses encryption to secure the data transmitted between the client and the server. It leverages SSL (Secure Sockets Layer) or TLS (Transport Layer Security) protocols to encrypt the data, ensuring that any intercepted data would be unreadable without the appropriate decryption key. This provides an additional layer of security and privacy for users, particularly for sensitive data like login credentials, financial information, or personal details.

2. Port Numbers:

- By default, HTTP uses port 80 for communication between the client and the server.
- HTTPS, on the other hand, uses port 443 by default for secure communication.

3. URL Scheme:

- In the URL (Uniform Resource Locator) of a website, you can identify whether it uses HTTP or HTTPS by looking at the scheme part of the URL.
- For HTTP, the URL scheme will be "http://", for example, "<http://example.com>".
- For HTTPS, the URL scheme will be "https://", for example, "<https://example.com>".

4. Trust and Authentication:

- Websites using HTTPS typically have SSL/TLS certificates issued by a trusted Certificate Authority (CA). These certificates validate the authenticity and identity of the website, ensuring that users are connecting to a legitimate server and not a malicious one (e.g., in a phishing attack). Web browsers often display a padlock icon or a "secure" label in the address bar for HTTPS sites, indicating that the connection is secure and the website's identity has been verified.

PROMPT

(b) Explain how the TCP communication protocol provides reliable communication between computers.

OUTPUT

(b) TCP (Transmission Control Protocol) is a transport layer protocol that provides reliable communication between computers by implementing various features to ensure data is transmitted accurately and in order. The key features of TCP that contribute to reliable communication are:

1. **Connection-oriented communication:** TCP establishes a connection between the sender and receiver before data transmission begins. The process, known as the "three-way handshake," involves exchanging control packets to synchronize both ends and confirm that the connection is established. This ensures that there is an active communication channel between the two computers before any data is exchanged.
2. **Error checking:** TCP includes error-checking mechanisms to ensure that the data transmitted is accurate and error-free. Each transmitted packet includes a checksum, which is a value calculated based on the contents of the packet. The receiver checks the received packet against the checksum to verify data integrity. If an error is detected, the receiver can request the sender to retransmit the corrupted packet.
3. **Acknowledgements and retransmission:** In TCP, the receiver acknowledges the receipt of packets by sending back an acknowledgment (ACK) message to the sender. If the sender does not receive an ACK within a specified timeframe, it assumes that the packet was lost or corrupted during transmission and retransmits the packet. This ensures that all packets are eventually received by the destination, maintaining data integrity.
4. **Flow control:** TCP implements flow control to prevent overwhelming the receiver with data. The receiver specifies a "receive window," which indicates how much data it can accept at a time. The sender adjusts its data transmission rate based on the size of the receive window to ensure that the receiver is not overloaded with data.
5. **Congestion control:** TCP also incorporates congestion control mechanisms to prevent network congestion and optimize data transmission rates. By monitoring packet loss and round-trip time, TCP can estimate the level of congestion in the network and adjust its transmission rate accordingly. This helps maintain a balance between throughput and network congestion, ultimately contributing to the reliability of communication.
6. **Ordered data transfer:** Each TCP packet includes a sequence number, which allows the receiver to reassemble the packets in the correct order, even if they arrive out of order. This ensures that the transmitted data is reconstructed accurately at the destination.

By combining these features, TCP provides a reliable, accurate, and ordered communication channel between computers, ensuring data integrity and efficient data transmission.

PROMPT

Question 8

The Unicode representation for the 'thumbs up' emoji character, shown in **Figure 2**, is the hexadecimal number 1F44D.

(a) Explain why emoji characters are not represented using the American Standard Code for Information Interchange (ASCII).

OUTPUT

(a) Emoji characters are not represented using the American Standard Code for Information Interchange (ASCII) due to the limited character set and encoding capacity of ASCII.

ASCII was originally designed to represent the English alphabet, numbers, and basic punctuation marks, as well as a few control characters. It uses 7 bits to encode a character, which allows for a total of $2^7 = 128$ unique characters. This character set and encoding capacity were sufficient for the basic needs of early computer systems and communication in the English language.

However, with the increasing use of computers and the internet worldwide, the need for a more comprehensive and inclusive character encoding system became evident. Emoji characters, along with many other non-English characters, symbols, and scripts, cannot be represented using the limited 128-character set of ASCII.

Unicode was developed to address these limitations and provide a universal character encoding standard that can represent a vast array of characters, symbols, and scripts from different languages and cultures around the world. Unicode currently has the capacity to encode over a million unique characters (using up to 21 bits), which allows for the inclusion of emoji characters, like the 'thumbs up' emoji (with the hexadecimal number 1F44D), along with many other non-ASCII characters and symbols.

PROMPT

(b) Express the hexadecimal number 1F44D as a binary number. The first four bits have been completed for you.

OUTPUT

To convert the hexadecimal number 1F44D to a binary number, you need to convert each individual hexadecimal digit to its corresponding 4-bit binary representation. Here's the conversion:

1 (hex) = 0001 (binary)

F (hex) = 1111 (binary)

4 (hex) = 0100 (binary)

4 (hex) = 0100 (binary)

D (hex) = 1101 (binary)

So, the binary representation of the hexadecimal number 1F44D is:

0001 1111 0100 0100 1101

PROMPT

Question 9

(a) What is an operating system?

OUTPUT

(a) An operating system (OS) is a software program that serves as an intermediary between the computer hardware and the user. It manages the computer's resources, such as the CPU, memory, storage devices, and peripherals, and provides a platform for other software applications to run on. The main functions of an operating system include:

1. Managing hardware resources: The OS allocates and manages the computer's resources, such as the CPU, memory, and I/O devices, ensuring that each application receives the necessary resources to execute properly and efficiently.
2. Providing a user interface: Operating systems typically include a graphical user interface (GUI) or a command-line interface (CLI) to allow users to interact with the computer and manage tasks, files, and applications.
3. Managing files and directories: The OS organizes files and directories on the storage devices, providing users with a structured file system to store and retrieve data.
4. Process management: The OS is responsible for creating, scheduling, and terminating processes, as well as managing process communication and synchronization. This ensures that multiple applications can run concurrently and efficiently on the computer.
5. Security and access control: Operating systems implement security features and access control mechanisms to protect the computer and its data from unauthorized access or malicious actions.
6. Memory management: The OS is responsible for allocating and deallocating memory, as well as managing virtual memory, to ensure that applications have the necessary memory resources to function correctly.
7. Device management: The OS manages the communication between the computer and its peripheral devices, such as printers, keyboards, and mice, through the use of device drivers.
8. System stability and error handling: The OS ensures the overall stability of the system by handling errors, crashes, or hardware failures and providing mechanisms for recovery and maintenance.

PROMPT

(b) The diagram in **Figure 3** depicts some of the main layers of an operating system. Select any **two** layers and explain their function.

OUTPUT

Unfortunately, I cannot see the diagram in Figure 3 since I am a text-based AI model and cannot process images. However, I can explain the functions of some common layers found in operating system architecture. Please let me know if these are the layers you are referring to or provide a description of the layers in the diagram, and I can help you with your specific question.

1. **Hardware Layer:** This is the lowest layer of the operating system, consisting of the physical components of the computer, such as the CPU, memory, storage devices, and input/output devices. The hardware layer is responsible for executing instructions and processing data.
2. **Kernel Layer:** The kernel is the core component of the operating system, responsible for managing hardware resources, memory, processes, and device drivers. It operates in a privileged mode, providing a controlled interface between the hardware and other layers of the operating system.
3. **System Libraries and APIs (Application Programming Interfaces):** These are software libraries and interfaces that provide standardized functions and services for application developers. They act as a bridge between the kernel and user-level applications, allowing applications to access system resources, services, and functions without directly interacting with the kernel or hardware.
4. **User Interface Layer:** This layer includes the graphical user interface (GUI) or command-line interface (CLI) that enables users to interact with the computer and perform tasks. The user interface provides a means for users to launch applications, manage files, and configure system settings.
5. **Application Layer:** This layer consists of user-level software applications that run on the operating system. These applications can include productivity tools, web browsers, media players, and games, among others. The application layer interacts with the operating system through system libraries and APIs to access hardware resources and perform tasks.

Please let me know if you would like more information on any of these layers or if you need an explanation of different layers in the operating system architecture.

PROMPT

Question 10

(a) State **two** tasks that would be undertaken by a project manager in a software design process.

OUTPUT

(a) A project manager in a software design process is responsible for overseeing the development and ensuring the project's successful completion. Two tasks undertaken by a project manager include:

1. Project planning and scheduling: The project manager is responsible for creating a detailed project plan that outlines the scope, objectives, and milestones of the software development process. This involves setting deadlines, estimating the time and resources required for each task, and assigning tasks to team members. The project manager must also monitor the progress of the project, making adjustments to the schedule as needed to ensure the project stays on track.
2. Risk management: The project manager must identify potential risks that could impact the project's success, such as technical challenges, resource constraints, or budget overruns. They are responsible for developing strategies to mitigate these risks, monitoring the project for emerging risks, and taking corrective action when necessary to minimize the impact of risks on the project's success.

PROMPT

(b) Some programming roles require the knowledge of low-level programming. How does a low-level computer program differ from a high-level computer program?

OUTPUT

(b) Low-level and high-level programming languages differ in terms of their abstraction level, human-readability, and closeness to the underlying hardware. Here's a comparison between low-level and high-level computer programs:

1. **Abstraction level:** Low-level programming languages provide little abstraction from the computer hardware, requiring the programmer to interact directly with system resources, memory addresses, and hardware-specific instructions. High-level programming languages, on the other hand, provide a higher level of abstraction, allowing programmers to focus on the logic and functionality of their programs without worrying about the underlying hardware details.
2. **Human-readability:** Low-level programming languages, such as assembly language or machine code, use mnemonics and numeric codes that are less human-readable than high-level languages. High-level programming languages, like Python, Java, or C++, have more human-readable syntax, making it easier for programmers to write, read, and maintain the code.
3. **Closeness to hardware:** Low-level programs are closer to the underlying hardware, which can result in more efficient and faster code execution in some cases. However, this closeness also means that low-level programs are often hardware-specific and less portable between different systems. High-level programs are more portable as they are designed to be platform-independent, relying on compilers or interpreters to translate the code into machine-specific instructions during execution.
4. **Development and debugging:** Writing and debugging low-level programs can be more time-consuming and complex due to their direct interaction with hardware and limited abstraction. High-level programming languages usually offer built-in libraries, functions, and error-handling mechanisms that simplify the development and debugging process.

In summary, low-level computer programs directly interact with the hardware and have less abstraction, making them more difficult to read and write but potentially offering better control and performance. High-level computer programs provide more abstraction, are more human-readable, and are easier to develop and maintain but may not offer the same level of control and performance optimization as low-level programs.

PROMPT

Question 11

(a) State **two** benefits of computer modelling.

OUTPUT

(a) Computer modeling is the use of software and computational techniques to create a virtual representation of a real-world system or process. Two benefits of computer modeling include:

1. **Cost and time efficiency:** Computer modeling can save both time and money by simulating various scenarios, optimizing designs, or testing hypotheses without the need to create physical prototypes, conduct costly experiments, or carry out time-consuming trial-and-error processes. By identifying potential issues or evaluating alternatives in a virtual environment, computer modeling can help reduce the overall cost and time required for development, research, or problem-solving.
2. **Risk reduction and safety:** Computer modeling enables researchers, engineers, and decision-makers to simulate and analyze potentially hazardous or risky situations without exposing people, equipment, or the environment to harm. For example, in industries like aerospace, automotive, or nuclear power, computer models can be used to simulate and test system performance, component failure, or extreme conditions in a controlled, virtual environment. This can help identify potential weaknesses, improve safety measures, and reduce the risk of accidents or failures in real-world applications.

PROMPT

(b) Explain how agent-based modelling may have been used during the COVID-19 pandemic to influence public health policy.

OUTPUT

(b) Agent-based modeling (ABM) is a computational technique used to simulate the behavior of individual agents and their interactions within a system. During the COVID-19 pandemic, agent-based modeling may have been employed to inform public health policy in various ways:

1. **Simulating the spread of the virus:** ABM can be used to model the behavior and interactions of individuals within a population, accounting for factors such as social networks, mobility patterns, and demographic characteristics. By simulating the transmission dynamics of the virus, policymakers could estimate the potential impact of various interventions, such as social distancing, mask-wearing, or lockdown measures, on the spread of the virus.
2. **Evaluating the impact of public health interventions:** Using ABM, policymakers can test the effectiveness of different public health strategies under various scenarios, such as varying levels of compliance with social distancing measures, different vaccination strategies, or the introduction of new variants of the virus. This can help identify the most effective interventions, estimate their potential outcomes, and inform public health policy decisions.
3. **Predicting healthcare system capacity and resource allocation:** Agent-based modeling can be employed to simulate the strain on healthcare systems, such as the demand for hospital beds, intensive care units, or medical equipment, under different epidemic scenarios. This can help public health officials and policymakers allocate resources more effectively, plan for potential surges in cases, and identify areas where additional support may be needed.
4. **Informing vaccination strategies:** ABM can be used to explore the impact of different vaccination strategies on the course of the pandemic, such as prioritizing specific age groups, targeting high-risk populations, or implementing various vaccine distribution schemes. This information can help policymakers design and implement vaccination campaigns that maximize their impact on reducing the spread of the virus and minimizing the burden on healthcare systems.

By providing insights into the potential outcomes of different interventions and scenarios, agent-based modeling can support evidence-based decision-making and help public health officials develop and implement more effective policies during the COVID-19 pandemic.

PROMPT

Question 12

The following selection of data is taken from a table in a database used to store information about dogs.

dog_name breed dob microchip

```
rover labrador 22/11/2011 Y
fido poodle 02/02/2020 Y
fido jack russell 15/06/2015 N
champ greyhound 01/01/2010 Y
spot dalmation 24/08/2007 N
buddy rottweiler 21/10/2012 Y
```

(a) State why each of the following fields would **not** be good candidates for a primary key in the table shown above.

dog_name:

breed:

OUTPUT

dog_name: Dog_name would not be a good candidate for a primary key because it is not unique. Multiple dogs can have the same name, as shown in the example where two dogs have the name "fido".

breed: Breed would not be a good candidate for a primary key because it is not unique either. Multiple dogs can belong to the same breed, like the "labrador" or "poodle" in the given data.

PROMPT

(b) One owner can own many dogs. Explain how a foreign key could be introduced to improve the design of this database.

owner_id owner_name address dog_name breed dob microchip

```
1 Joe Murphy 1 main st. rover labrador 22/11/2011 Y
1 Joe Murphy 1 main st. fido poodle 02/02/2020 Y
2 Ada Traore 9 park ave. fido jack russell 15/06/2015 N
1 Joe Murphy 1 main st. champ greyhound 01/01/2010 Y
2 Ada Traore 9 park ave. spots dalmation 24/08/2007 N
3 James Tidy 7 bond st. buddy rottweiler 21/10/2012 Y
```

OUTPUT

To improve the design of this database, you can introduce a foreign key by creating a separate table for owners and then linking the dogs table to the owners table using the foreign key. This will help to maintain the relationships between owners and dogs more efficiently and eliminate data redundancy.

Create an Owners table:

owner_id | owner_name | address

```
1 | Joe Murphy | 1 main st.
2 | Ada Traore | 9 park ave.
3 | James Tidy | 7 bond st.
```

Modify the Dogs table to include the foreign key owner_id:

dog_id | dog_name | breed | dob | microchip | owner_id

```
1 | rover | labrador | 22/11/2011 | Y | 1
2 | fido | poodle | 02/02/2020 | Y | 1
3 | fido | jack russell | 15/06/2015 | N | 2
4 | champ | greyhound | 01/01/2010 | Y | 1
5 | spot | dalmation | 24/08/2007 | N | 2
6 | buddy | rottweiler | 21/10/2012 | Y | 3
```

Now, the owner_id in the Dogs table serves as a foreign key that refers to the primary key (owner_id) in the Owners table. This allows you to efficiently maintain the one-to-many relationship between owners and dogs, and avoid data redundancy.

Section B PROMPT

Question 13

Eircode is the postal address code system used in Ireland to uniquely identify every individual address in the country. An Eircode is a seven-character code made up of two parts – a threecharacter Routing Key and a four-character Unique Identifier.

The first character in the Routing Key must always be a letter, and the second and third characters must always be digits.

Every character in the Unique Identifier must be alpha-numeric i.e. either a letter or a number.

The format of the Eircode, A65 F4E2, is shown below in **Figure 4**.

(a) Explain why each of the following are not valid Eircodes.

(i) GA5 AOK1

(ii) X234 Y56

(iii) 8XT A43Y

OUTPUT

(i) GA5 AOK1

This Eircode is not valid because the second and third characters of the Routing Key are not both digits. According to the Eircode rules, the first character should be a letter, and the second and third characters should be digits. In this case, the second character is a letter ('A') instead of a digit.

(ii) X234 Y56

This Eircode is not valid because the Routing Key has more than three characters. The Routing Key should only have three characters: the first being a letter and the second and third being digits. In this case, the Routing Key has four characters ('X234').

(iii) 8XT A43Y

This Eircode is not valid because the first character of the Routing Key is a digit instead of a letter. According to the Eircode rules, the first character should be a letter, and the second and third characters should be digits. In this case, the first character is a digit ('8') instead of a letter.

PROMPT

(b) The intention of the Python code shown below is to implement a validation check for an Eircode.

```
1 def is_valid_eircode(test_eircode):
2
3 # This function checks whether 'test_eircode' is a valid Eircode or not
4 # It returns True if 'test_eircode' is a valid Eircode. False otherwise.
5
6 # Uses:
7 # s.isalpha() -> True if s contains alphabetic only; False otherwise
8 # s.isdigit() -> True if s contains digits only; False otherwise
9 # s.isalnum() -> True if s contains alpha-numeric only; False otherwise
10
11 if not test_eircode[0].isalpha():
12     return False
13
14 # if the second character isn't a digit or the third character isn't a
15 # digit the Eircode is invalid so return False
16 if ((not test_eircode[1].isdigit()) or (not test_eircode[2].isdigit())):
17     return False
18
19 if not test_eircode[-4:].isalnum():
20     return False
21
22 return True
```

(i) What is meant by the term 'validation check'?

OUTPUT

A validation check is a process or a set of rules used to verify whether the data entered into a system or provided as input meets certain criteria or conforms to a predefined format. The purpose of a validation check is to ensure that the data is accurate, consistent, and free of errors before it is processed, stored, or used by an application. By performing validation checks, a system can prevent invalid or incorrect data from causing problems or errors, and can provide feedback to the user if the input needs to be corrected or adjusted.

PROMPT

(ii) Outline briefly how a test case could be used to test the above code.

OUTPUT

A test case is a set of conditions, inputs, and expected outcomes used to verify whether a piece of code, function, or an entire system is functioning correctly. To test the above code using a test case, follow these steps:

1. Identify the input: Choose a specific Eircode value (`test_eircode`) that will be used as the input to the `is_valid_eircode()` function. This Eircode should represent a specific scenario you want to test, such as a valid Eircode, an Eircode with invalid characters, or an Eircode with an incorrect format.
2. Determine the expected outcome: Based on the chosen input, determine the expected outcome of the function. If the input Eircode is valid, the function should return `True`; if it is invalid, the function should return `False`.
3. Execute the test case: Call the `is_valid_eircode()` function with the chosen input Eircode and observe the returned value.
4. Compare the actual outcome with the expected outcome: Check if the returned value from the function matches the expected outcome. If the actual outcome matches the expected outcome, the test case has passed, indicating that the code is working correctly for that specific input. If the actual outcome does not match the expected outcome, the test case has failed, which may indicate an issue or bug in the code.
5. Repeat with additional test cases: To thoroughly test the code, create and execute multiple test cases that cover various scenarios, such as different valid and invalid Eircodes, edge cases, and boundary conditions. This will help ensure that the code is robust and can handle a wide range of inputs correctly.

PROMPT

(iii) Two types of testing that could be performed on the code are unit testing and system testing. Distinguish between these two types of testing.

OUTPUT

Unit Testing:

1. **Scope:** Unit testing focuses on testing individual components, functions, or modules in isolation from the rest of the system. The goal is to ensure that each small piece of code works correctly and as intended.
2. **Level:** Unit testing is considered a low-level testing approach, as it is performed early in the development process and targets specific parts of the code.
3. **Purpose:** The primary purpose of unit testing is to identify and fix bugs, errors, or issues at the code level before integrating the components with other parts of the system. This helps in creating reliable and efficient code.
4. **Test Execution:** Unit tests are typically written and executed by the developers themselves, using testing frameworks like JUnit, PyUnit, or NUnit, to automate the testing process.

System Testing:

1. **Scope:** System testing focuses on testing the entire integrated system as a whole, including all components, modules, and their interactions. The goal is to ensure that the system meets the specified requirements and works correctly when all parts are combined.
2. **Level:** System testing is considered a high-level testing approach, as it is performed later in the development process and targets the system as a whole.
3. **Purpose:** The primary purpose of system testing is to validate that the integrated system meets its functional, performance, security, and usability requirements. This helps in ensuring that the final product is of high quality and meets the needs of its users.
4. **Test Execution:** System tests are typically written and executed by a separate testing team or quality assurance (QA) team, who are responsible for verifying the system's functionality and performance. System tests may involve manual testing, automated testing, or a combination of both.

PROMPT

(iv) This Python code will show that the Eircode, *A99 SP@M A1OK*, is valid even though it is not. Why does the code indicate that this Eircode is valid?

OUTPUT

The given Python code does not correctly validate the Eircode due to the absence of an important check. While the code checks for the first character to be a letter and the second and third characters to be digits, it only checks if the last four characters are alpha-numeric, i.e., a combination of letters and numbers. However, it does not check for the presence of special characters or symbols.

In the example provided, the Eircode "A99 SP@M" is considered valid by the code because:

1. The first character is a letter.
2. The second and third characters are digits.
3. The last four characters are alpha-numeric.

However, the presence of the special character "@" in the Eircode makes it invalid, which is not being checked by the code. To fix this issue, the code should also check for the absence of special characters or symbols in the Eircode, ensuring that only letters and digits are present.

PROMPT

(v) After code has been changed it is important to conduct regression testing. Why is this important?

OUTPUT

Regression testing is important because it helps ensure that changes made to the code, such as bug fixes, modifications, or enhancements, have not introduced new issues or caused unintended side effects in the existing functionality. When code is changed or updated, there is a risk that these alterations might break previously working features or cause new problems to arise.

Regression testing involves re-running previously passed test cases on the modified code to verify that the previously working features still function correctly after the changes. This testing process helps maintain the quality and stability of the software, providing confidence that the code modifications have not adversely affected the overall system.

PROMPT

(c) The following questions are based on the code in part (b).

(i) Explain what the following code does:

```
11 if not test_eircode[0].isalpha():  
12 return False
```

OUTPUT

This code checks if the first character of the `test_eircode` string is an alphabetic letter or not. The expression `test_eircode[0].isalpha()` returns True if the first character (at index 0) of the `test_eircode` string is an alphabetic letter, and False otherwise. The `not` keyword negates the result of this expression. So, if the first character is not an alphabetic letter, the expression `not test_eircode[0].isalpha()` evaluates to True.

If the first character of `test_eircode` is not an alphabetic letter (i.e., the condition evaluates to True), the code executes the statement `return False`, which terminates the `is_valid_eircode()` function and returns False, indicating that the given Eircode is not valid. If the first character is an alphabetic letter, the code continues to the next checks.

PROMPT

(ii) Consider the following statement from line 16.

```
16 if ((not test_eircode[1].isdigit()) or (not test_eircode[2].isdigit())):
```

If we let P represent the possible boolean values for

test_eircode[1].isdigit() and Q represent the possible boolean values for

test_eircode[2].isdigit(), complete the truth table below for the

expression, **not P or not Q**.

P Q not P not Q not P or not Q

False False

False True

True False

True True

OUTPUT

Here is the truth table for the expression `not P or not Q`, where P represents the boolean values for `test\_eircode[1].isdigit()` and Q represents the boolean values for `test\_eircode[2].isdigit()`:

P	Q	not P	not Q	not P or not Q
False	False	True	True	True
False	True	True	False	True
True	False	False	True	True
True	True	False	False	False

This table shows all the possible combinations of boolean values for P and Q, and the resulting values for `not P`, `not Q`, and the final expression `not P or not Q`.

PROMPT

(iii) Using the same meanings for P and Q from part (ii) complete the truth table below for the expression, **not (P and Q)**.

P Q P and Q not (P and Q)

False False

False True

True False

True True

OUTPUT

Here is the truth table for the expression `not (P and Q)`, where P represents the boolean values for `test_eircode[1].isdigit()` and Q represents the boolean values for `test_eircode[2].isdigit()`:

P	Q	P and Q	not (P and Q)
False	False	False	True
False	True	False	True
True	False	False	True
True	True	True	False

This table shows all the possible combinations of boolean values for P and Q, and the resulting values for `P and Q`, and the final expression `not (P and Q)`.

PROMPT

(iv) Use your findings from parts (ii) and (iii) to re-write the statement on line 16, without changing its logical meaning.

```
16 if ((not test_eircode[1].isdigit()) or (not test_eircode[2].isdigit())):
```

OUTPUT

Based on the findings from parts (ii) and (iii), we can rewrite the statement on line 16 using the equivalent expression `not (P and Q)`. In this context, P and Q represent `test_eircode[1].isdigit()` and `test_eircode[2].isdigit()` respectively:

```
16 if not (test_eircode[1].isdigit() and test_eircode[2].isdigit()):
```

PROMPT

(v) Explain how the technique of string slicing could be used to provide an alternative to the statement on line 16.

```
16 if ((not test_eircode[1].isdigit()) or (not
test_eircode[2].isdigit())):
```

OUTPUT

String slicing can be used to extract a portion of a string. In this case, we can extract the second and third characters of the `test_eircode` and check if both characters are digits. Here's how the statement on line 16 can be rewritten using string slicing:

```
16 if not test_eircode[1:3].isdigit():
```

This line of code extracts the second and third characters from `test_eircode` using slicing (the slice `1:3` will include the characters at index 1 and 2, but not the one at index 3). The `isdigit()` function is then called on the resulting substring to check if both characters are digits. If they are not, the function will return `False`, making the condition `True` and triggering the `if` statement.

PROMPT

Question 14

(a) Consider a two-player game in which each player takes alternate turns at removing matchsticks from a board. The rules of the game are simple:

- at each turn a player must remove either one or two matchsticks
- the player who takes the last matchstick wins

Winning and losing positions are defined in terms of the number of matchsticks left on the board.

A winning position (W) is a position from which a player cannot lose if she/he makes all the optimal moves until the end of the game. For example, 2 is a winning position because if the player whose turn it is, makes the optimal move (i.e. removes the two remaining matchsticks) they will win that game.

A losing position (L) is a position from which a player cannot win (assuming that their opponent makes all the optimal moves until the game is over).

The win/loss table below depicts winning and losing positions for the scenarios where there are 0, 1, 2, 3 or 4 matchsticks left on the board.

No. of matchsticks remaining 0 1 2 3 4

Position (W or L) L W W L W

- (i) Explain why 3 is a losing position.

OUTPUT

3 is a losing position because no matter what move the current player makes, they will leave their opponent in a winning position. If the current player removes 1 matchstick, there will be 2 matchsticks left, which is a winning position for the opponent. If the current player removes 2 matchsticks, there will be 1 matchstick left, which is also a winning position for the opponent. In both cases, the opponent can make optimal moves to win the game, and the current player cannot prevent it, thus making 3 a losing position.

PROMPT

- (ii) Explain why 4 is a winning position.

OUTPUT

4 is a winning position because the current player can make an optimal move that puts their opponent in a losing position. If the current player removes 1 matchstick, there will be 3 matchsticks left, which is a losing position for the opponent. Since the opponent is now in a losing position, they cannot win the game, assuming the current player continues to make optimal moves. By making this move, the current player has ensured their victory, making 4 a winning position.

PROMPT

(iii) Calculate whether 5 and 6 are winning or losing positions and place your answers in the table below.

No. of matchsticks remaining 0 1 2 3 4 5 6

Position (W or L) L W W L W

OUTPUT

Let's analyze the positions for 5 and 6 matchsticks remaining:

5 matchsticks remaining:

- If the current player removes 1 matchstick, there will be 4 matchsticks left, which is a winning position for the opponent.
- If the current player removes 2 matchsticks, there will be 3 matchsticks left, which is a losing position for the opponent.

Since there is a move that puts the opponent in a losing position, 5 is a winning position (W).

6 matchsticks remaining:

- If the current player removes 1 matchstick, there will be 5 matchsticks left, which is a winning position for the opponent.
- If the current player removes 2 matchsticks, there will be 4 matchsticks left, which is also a winning position for the opponent.

Since all moves put the opponent in a winning position, 6 is a losing position (L).

No. of matchsticks remaining: 0 1 2 3 4 5 6

Position (W or L): L W W L W W L

PROMPT

(iv) Assume you are about to start a new game with 21 matchsticks. If your opponent offered you the choice of going first or second, which would you choose? Justify your answer.

OUTPUT

To determine the best choice, let's first determine whether 21 is a winning or losing position.

To find this, we can follow the pattern we observed previously:

7 matchsticks: W (1 or 2 matchsticks can be removed to leave the opponent with a losing position)

8 matchsticks: L (removing 1 or 2 matchsticks leaves the opponent with a winning position)

9 matchsticks: W

10 matchsticks: W

11 matchsticks: L

12 matchsticks: W

13 matchsticks: W

14 matchsticks: L

15 matchsticks: W

16 matchsticks: W

17 matchsticks: L

18 matchsticks: W

19 matchsticks: W

20 matchsticks: L

21 matchsticks: W

Since 21 matchsticks is a winning position (W), you should choose to go first. By going first, you can make the optimal moves to ensure you win, assuming you follow the winning strategy and your opponent makes no mistakes.

PROMPT

(v) What strategy would you recommend in a game that started off with 20 matchsticks? Justify your answer.

OUTPUT

In a game that starts with 20 matchsticks, the position is a losing position (L) as we determined in the previous answer. If it's your turn and there are 20 matchsticks on the board, the best strategy would be to force your opponent into another losing position, hoping that they make a mistake.

Here's a possible strategy:

1. Remove 1 matchstick on your first turn, leaving 19 matchsticks on the board. This puts the opponent in a winning position.
2. If your opponent makes an optimal move, they will try to leave you in a losing position. However, if they make a mistake, take advantage of it by making the optimal move to leave them in a losing position.

Essentially, your goal is to capitalize on any errors made by your opponent, as playing optimally from a losing position will not guarantee a win. Always try to leave your opponent in a losing position and hope for a mistake on their part.

PROMPT

(vi) Assume the rules of the game are amended so that players can remove 3 matches (as well as 1 or 2). Calculate whether or not each position in a game with 9 matchsticks is a winning or losing position and place your answers in the table below.

No. of matchsticks remaining 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Position (W or L) L

OUTPUT

In this amended version of the game, players can remove 1, 2, or 3 matchsticks on their turn.

To determine whether a position is a winning or losing position, we analyze the possible moves and the subsequent positions resulting from those moves.

No. of matchsticks remaining | 0 | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 | 8 | 9

Position (W or L) | L | W | W | W | L | W | W | W | L | W

Here's the reasoning behind each position:

- 0: L - No moves available, opponent wins.
- 1: W - Remove 1 matchstick, leaving 0 for the opponent.
- 2: W - Remove 2 matchsticks, leaving 0 for the opponent.
- 3: W - Remove 3 matchsticks, leaving 0 for the opponent.
- 4: L - Any move will leave the opponent with a winning position (1, 2, or 3 matchsticks remaining).
- 5: W - Remove 1 matchstick, leaving 4 for the opponent, which is a losing position.
- 6: W - Remove 2 matchsticks, leaving 4 for the opponent, which is a losing position.
- 7: W - Remove 3 matchsticks, leaving 4 for the opponent, which is a losing position.
- 8: L - Any move will leave the opponent with a winning position (5, 6, or 7 matchsticks remaining).
- 9: W - Remove 1 matchstick, leaving 8 for the opponent, which is a losing position.

PROMPT

(b) Consider a variation of the game described in part (a) with two key differences: the matchsticks are initially arranged into two separate piles on the board and a player can remove any number of matchsticks from a single pile on their go. We will call the two piles pile X and pile Y.

For example, in a game where pile X contains 10 matchsticks and pile Y contains 9 matchsticks, a player may decide to remove 9 matchsticks from pile Y on their go.

The player who removes the last matchstick(s) wins the game.

(i) Below is a partially completed diagram for an end game scenario in which it is player A's turn and there is only one matchstick left in pile X and two matchsticks left in pile Y (denoted by 1, 2).

The purpose of the diagram is to depict the eventual outcome for every possible move from this point in the game. The left-hand branch of the diagram has been completed covering all eventualities if player A removes 1 matchstick from pile X (denoted by AX1).

Complete the diagram to illustrate all possible moves and show who wins in each case.

OUTPUT

Here's the completed diagram showing all possible moves and the winner in each case:

Explanation:

- If player A removes 1 matchstick from pile X (AX1), it leaves (0, 2) for player B.
 - If player B removes 1 matchstick from pile Y (AY1), it leaves (0, 1) for player A. Player A removes the last matchstick and wins.
 - If player B removes 2 matchsticks from pile Y (AY2), it leaves (0, 0) for player A. Player B wins because they removed the last matchstick(s).
- If player A removes 2 matchsticks from pile X (AX2), it leaves (0, 1) for player B.
 - If player B removes 1 matchstick from pile Y (AY1), it leaves (0, 0) for player A. Player B wins because they removed the last matchstick(s).
 - If player B removes 2 matchsticks from pile Y (AY2), it is not possible since there's only 1 matchstick left in pile Y.

PROMPT

(iii) Based on the completed diagram which is player A's best move? Why?

OUTPUT

Player A's best move is to remove 1 matchstick from pile X (AX1). This move leads to the position (0, 2) for player B. In this case, no matter what player B does (whether they remove 1 or 2 matchsticks from pile Y), player A will have a chance to win the game. If player A removes 2 matchsticks from pile X (AX2) instead, player B can remove 1 matchstick from pile Y and win the game. By choosing the AX1 move, player A increases their chances of winning the game.

PROMPT

(iv) Describe a winning move from state (2, 3).

OUTPUT

In the state (2, 3), a winning move for player A would be to remove 1 matchstick from pile Y, resulting in the new state (2, 2). This move ensures that no matter what player B does, player A will have the opportunity to win the game.

If player B removes 1 matchstick from either pile, the piles will be (2, 1) or (1, 2), and player A can remove the remaining matchsticks in the other pile to win. If player B removes 2 matchsticks from either pile, the piles will become (0, 2) or (2, 0), and player A can remove both matchsticks from the non-empty pile to win the game.

PROMPT

(iv) Hence, or otherwise, describe a winning strategy from state (n, m) , where $n \neq m$.

OUTPUT

A winning strategy from state (n, m) , where $n \neq m$, would be to ensure that after every move by player A, the number of matchsticks in both piles remains unequal. This way, player A can always mimic player B's moves and maintain unequal piles.

To do this, when it's player A's turn, they should remove the difference between n and m matchsticks from the larger pile. After this move, the piles will have an equal number of matchsticks. Then, every time player B makes a move, player A should mimic that move on the other pile. This way, the piles will remain equal, and player A will always have a move to make.

Eventually, player B will be forced to make a move that results in an empty pile, and player A can remove all the remaining matchsticks in the other pile to win the game.

PROMPT	
(v)	Explain why (n, n, n) is a winning position in a game where 3 piles are used?
OUTPUT	
	<p>In a game with three piles, state (n, n, n) is a winning position because the current player can always force the piles to become unequal after their move, putting the opponent in a losing position.</p> <p>To achieve this, the current player can remove any number of matchsticks from one of the piles, as long as they don't remove all of the matchsticks from that pile. For example, if the piles are (n, n, n), the player can remove k matchsticks from the first pile, where $1 \leq k < n$, resulting in a state $(n-k, n, n)$.</p> <p>Now the piles are unequal, and the opponent is forced to make a move that will not result in equal piles again. The current player can continue to make moves that maintain the inequality of the piles, forcing the opponent to eventually take the last matchstick(s) from one of the piles, leaving the current player with the opportunity to remove all remaining matchsticks from the other two piles and win the game.</p>

PROMPT	
(c)	Explain the use of any one of decomposition, abstraction or pattern recognition in developing solutions to problems such as those in parts (a) and (b) . You may refer to the solutions you used in answering parts (a) and (b) .
OUTPUT	
	<p>In developing solutions to problems such as those in parts (a) and (b), the concept of decomposition can be particularly useful. Decomposition involves breaking down a complex problem into smaller, more manageable subproblems that can be solved independently. Once the subproblems are solved, their solutions can be combined to form a solution to the original problem.</p> <p>In the context of the matchstick games, decomposition was applied when analyzing different game states or positions (e.g., winning or losing positions) and determining the optimal moves for each state. By breaking down the problem into individual game states, we were able to evaluate each position and its possible moves independently. This approach allowed us to systematically explore the possible moves and outcomes, eventually leading to the identification of winning strategies and moves for various game states.</p> <p>By decomposing the problem into smaller parts, we simplified the analysis, making it easier to reason about the game and develop strategies to ensure victory.</p>

PROMPT

Question 15

(a) Charles Stark Draper is often credited with the invention of embedded systems. Embedded systems are a combination of hardware and software designed to perform a specific function. They are called 'embedded' because they are often used as part of a larger system. Many embedded systems use sensors to receive analogue or digital inputs. The input data which is often supplied in real time is then processed resulting in some sort of output. While not every embedded system will have a user interface, some are designed to meet the principles of universal design.

(i) Explain the terms hardware and software. Provide **two** examples of each.

OUTPUT

Hardware refers to the physical components of a computer or electronic system. These components include circuits, processors, memory devices, input/output devices, and other tangible parts that make up a computing system. Examples of hardware include:

1. Central Processing Unit (CPU): The CPU is responsible for executing instructions and performing calculations. It is often considered the "brain" of the computer.
2. Hard Disk Drive (HDD): The HDD is a storage device used for saving and retrieving digital information, such as operating systems, application programs, and user data.

Software, on the other hand, refers to the set of instructions, programs, or data that direct the operation of a computer or electronic system. Software is intangible and is stored on hardware devices like hard drives or memory chips. Examples of software include:

1. Operating Systems (OS): An OS is a software that manages computer hardware and provides a platform for other software to run. Examples include Windows, macOS, and Linux.
2. Application Programs: Application programs, or apps, are software designed for specific tasks or purposes, such as word processors (e.g., Microsoft Word), web browsers (e.g., Google Chrome), and image editors (e.g., Adobe Photoshop).

PROMPT

(ii) Provide **one** example of a digital sensor and **one** example of an analogue sensor.

OUTPUT

Digital Sensor: A digital sensor is a device that converts a physical quantity into a digital signal that can be easily processed by a computer or electronic system. An example of a digital sensor is a digital temperature sensor. Digital temperature sensors, like the DS18B20, measure temperature and convert the reading into a digital signal, which can be easily interpreted by a microcontroller or other digital systems.

Analogue Sensor: An analogue sensor is a device that produces a continuous output signal that is proportional to the physical quantity being measured. An example of an analogue sensor is a potentiometer. A potentiometer, also known as a variable resistor, is used to measure position or displacement. As the position of the wiper on the potentiometer changes, the resistance varies, and the output voltage changes proportionally, creating an analogue signal that can be further processed or converted to a digital signal using an analogue-to-digital converter (ADC).

PROMPT

(iii) Explain, with the aid of a diagram, the difference between digital and analogue input.

OUTPUT

Digital and analogue inputs are two different ways of representing and processing information from sensors or other input devices.

Analogue input is a continuous signal that varies over time and can take any value within a certain range. This type of signal represents the physical quantity being measured in a continuous form. In an analogue input signal, the amplitude of the signal varies continuously over time.

Digital input, on the other hand, is a discrete signal that can only take a finite number of values, typically just two (0 and 1). Digital input signals are usually obtained by sampling and quantizing analogue signals, so they represent the physical quantity being measured in a discrete form.

Here's a simple diagram illustrating the difference between analogue and digital input:

In the analogue input example, the signal smoothly varies over time. In the digital input example, the signal consists of discrete levels (0 and 1) with abrupt transitions between them.

PROMPT

(iv) In the context of embedded systems what is meant by the term 'real-time'?

OUTPUT

In the context of embedded systems, the term "real-time" refers to the ability of a system to process and respond to inputs or events within a specific time constraint. Real-time systems are designed to handle tasks and produce outputs with strict timing requirements, ensuring that the system can operate reliably and predictably under specific conditions.

In real-time embedded systems, the correctness of the system's output depends not only on the logical accuracy of the results but also on the time at which these results are produced. These systems often interact with the external environment and need to respond promptly to time-sensitive inputs, such as sensor data or user interactions, to ensure proper functioning and safety.

Examples of real-time embedded systems include automotive control systems, medical devices, industrial automation systems, and avionics systems, where timely processing and response to inputs are crucial for the overall performance and safety of the system.

PROMPT

(v) Describe **two** advantages of embedded systems over general purpose computer systems, such as desktop computers and laptops.

OUTPUT

1. Power efficiency and resource optimization: Embedded systems are designed for specific tasks and often have lower power consumption and resource requirements compared to general-purpose computer systems. They use specialized hardware and software components that are optimized for the particular function they perform, leading to more efficient use of resources like memory, processing power, and energy. This makes embedded systems suitable for applications where power supply is limited, such as battery-powered devices, or where power efficiency is a priority, such as IoT devices and industrial automation systems.
2. Size and form factor: Embedded systems are often smaller and more compact than general-purpose computer systems, as they are tailored to specific applications and do not require the broad range of components and peripherals found in desktop computers and laptops. This smaller form factor allows embedded systems to be integrated into various devices and systems, such as wearable devices, home appliances, and automotive systems, where space constraints are critical. The reduced size also contributes to the lower cost of embedded systems, making them more affordable for a wide range of applications.

PROMPT

(b) According to the description provided in part **(a)**, mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets could be considered to contain multiple embedded systems.

(i) Describe **two** examples of embedded systems on mobile devices.

OUTPUT

1. **GPS Receiver:** A Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver is an embedded system in mobile devices that allows users to determine their location using satellite signals. The GPS receiver processes the signals received from multiple GPS satellites, calculates the user's precise location (latitude, longitude, and altitude), and provides real-time navigation and location-based services. This embedded system is essential for various applications on mobile devices, such as maps, navigation, fitness tracking, and location-based recommendations.
2. **Camera System:** Mobile devices like smartphones and tablets often contain advanced camera systems, which are embedded systems in themselves. The camera system includes a combination of hardware components, such as the image sensor, lens, and image processor, as well as software algorithms for image processing, autofocus, exposure control, and other camera functions. These embedded systems enable users to capture high-quality photos and videos, apply filters and effects, and use augmented reality features in various applications. The camera system may also support facial recognition and biometric authentication features for improved security on the mobile device.

PROMPT

(ii) In the context of mobile devices distinguish clearly between the terms, 'user interface' and 'universal design'.

OUTPUT

User Interface (UI): The user interface refers to the design and layout of a mobile device's software and hardware components that facilitate user interaction. It includes the graphical elements, buttons, menus, and touch controls, as well as the way information is displayed and organized on the screen. The UI design aims to provide an intuitive, efficient, and aesthetically pleasing experience for the user while interacting with the device and its applications. A well-designed user interface takes into account the needs and preferences of the target audience and enables them to perform tasks with ease and minimal confusion.

Universal Design: Universal design is a design principle that aims to create products, environments, and systems that are accessible and usable by as many people as possible, regardless of their age, ability, or circumstances. In the context of mobile devices, universal design refers to the development of hardware and software features that cater to the diverse needs of users, including those with disabilities or other special requirements. Examples of universal design in mobile devices may include adjustable font sizes, screen magnification, high-contrast modes, voice recognition, and assistive technologies like screen readers for visually impaired users. By incorporating universal design principles, mobile devices can become more inclusive and accessible to a wider range of users.

PROMPT

(iii) State **two** principles of universal design. For each principle you should describe how it relates to the design of an embedded system of your choice.

OUTPUT

1. Flexibility in Use: This principle of universal design emphasizes designing products or systems that can accommodate a wide range of individual preferences and abilities. The system should be adaptable to different users, allowing them to interact with it in multiple ways, depending on their needs and circumstances.

Example: An embedded system in a smart thermostat can be designed with flexibility in use in mind. It could provide multiple methods of control, such as physical buttons, touch screen controls, and voice commands, to accommodate users with varying abilities. Additionally, it could offer customizable settings, such as temperature preferences, scheduling, and accessibility options (e.g., large fonts or high contrast mode for visually impaired users), making the system adaptable to different users' needs.

2. Tolerance for Error: This principle focuses on designing systems that minimize the potential for errors and negative consequences that may arise from unintended actions or misuse. A well-designed system should be able to handle errors gracefully, provide clear feedback to the user, and prevent accidental actions that could lead to undesirable results.

Example: In an embedded system for a medical device, such as an insulin pump, tolerance for error is crucial. The system could be designed to prevent accidental overdose by incorporating features like confirmation prompts before administering a dose, automatic dosage calculation based on user input, and clear visual and auditory feedback to confirm the user's actions. Additionally, it could include safeguards to prevent unauthorized access, as well as mechanisms to detect and alert users to potential malfunctions or errors in the device.

PROMPT

(c) The market for embedded systems is likely to continue to grow for the foreseeable future as they are seen as key drivers of current and emerging trends in computing such as the Internet of Things (IoT), smart homes, smart cities, drones and surveillance technology. Discuss the potential impact of embedded systems on society. In your answer you should provide evidence that you have considered alternative perspectives of any **two** stakeholders that you think are relevant.

OUTPUT

Embedded systems have the potential to greatly impact society in various ways, both positive and negative. In this discussion, we will consider the perspectives of two stakeholders: consumers and government agencies.

1. Consumers:

Positive impact: Embedded systems can lead to increased convenience and efficiency in daily life. They can improve the functionality of devices and appliances, making them more user-friendly and customizable. For example, smart homes can provide energy savings, security features, and automation of routine tasks, making life easier for homeowners. Embedded systems in wearable technology can help consumers track their health and fitness, allowing them to make informed decisions about their well-being.

Negative impact: On the other hand, there are concerns about privacy and security. As more devices become interconnected, there is a higher risk of data breaches and unauthorized access to sensitive information. Consumers may be hesitant to adopt new technologies due to fears of being monitored or having their personal data compromised. Additionally, the reliance on embedded systems and IoT devices could lead to a digital divide, where those who cannot afford or access the latest technology are left behind, further exacerbating social inequality.

2. Government agencies:

Positive impact: Embedded systems can support the development of smart cities, leading to improved infrastructure, energy efficiency, and public services. For instance, traffic management systems can optimize traffic flow, reducing congestion and emissions. Government agencies can also use embedded systems for surveillance, disaster management, and environmental monitoring, leading to increased public safety and efficient allocation of resources.

Negative impact: The increased surveillance capabilities provided by embedded systems and IoT devices can raise ethical concerns about government intrusion into citizens' privacy. There may be debates over the balance between security and privacy, with some arguing that pervasive monitoring could lead to a loss of individual freedom and civil liberties. Moreover, the implementation and maintenance of these systems can be costly and complex, which may strain government budgets and resources.

In conclusion, embedded systems have the potential to revolutionize many aspects of modern society, leading to increased efficiency, convenience, and safety. However, it is crucial to address the associated concerns of privacy, security, and social inequality to ensure that the benefits of these technologies are realized in a responsible and inclusive manner.

Section C PROMPT

Question 16

(a)

Enter your Examination Number in the space provided on **line 2** in your Python file.

The Python program shown below tests whether the strings stored in the variables **word1** and **word2** are anagrams of each other and displays YES if they are.

Two words are anagrams of each other if they both use exactly the same letters. For

example, the words LISTEN and SILENT are anagrams of one another. ELVIS and LIVES are also anagrams.

The function definition **is_anagram(w1, w2)** determines whether or not two words are anagrams of one another and will not be used until part (v).

```
1 # Question 16(a)
2 # Examination Number:
3
4 # function definition used in part (v)
5 def is_anagram(w1, w2):
6     if sorted(w1) == sorted(w2):
7         return True
8     else:
9         return False
10
11 word1 = input("Enter the first word: ")
12 word2 = "SILENT"
13
14 # test whether the sorted strings are the same as each other
15 # if the sorted strings are the same then they must be anagrams
16 if (sorted(word1) == sorted(word2)):
17     print("YES")
```

When the program is run, the user is prompted to enter a word. If the user enters the word LISTEN (in uppercase) the output should look as follows because LISTEN and SILENT are anagrams of each other.

```
Enter the first word: LISTEN
YES
```

Make the following changes to the program:

(i) Currently the value of the variable **word2** is hard-coded to SILENT. Modify the program so that it prompts the user to *'Enter the second word:'*, and then assign whatever value the user enters to the variable **word2**.

When the program is run the output may look as follows:

```
Enter the first word: LISTEN
Enter the second word: SILENT
YES
```

(ii) If both words entered are anagrams the program should display the first word followed by the phrase *'is an anagram of'* and then the second word.

When the program is run the output may look as follows:

```
Enter the first word: LISTEN
Enter the second word: SILENT
LISTEN is an anagram of SILENT
```

(iii) Extend the program so that if the words entered are not anagrams of each other the program displays the first word followed by the phrase *'is NOT an anagram of'* and then the second word.

When the program is run the output may look as follows:

```
Enter the first word: LIST
Enter the second word: ARRAY
LIST is NOT an anagram of ARRAY
```

(iv) The program currently treats words as case-sensitive. Modify the program so that the case of the words entered does not matter.

When the program is run the output may look as follows:

```
Enter the first word: Listen
Enter the second word: Silent
Listen is an anagram of Silent
```

(v) Extend the program to use the function `is_anagram` to determine whether or not the two words entered are anagrams of each other. You should not delete any code you wrote in previous parts. The program will now check twice if the words are anagrams of each other.

When the program is run the output may look as follows:

```
Enter the first word: Listen
Enter the second word: Silent
Listen is an anagram of Silent
Listen is an anagram of Silent
```

(vi) Anagrams of words can also be phrases. For example, *Moon starrer* is an anagram of *Astronomer*, and *Voices rant on* is an anagram of the two words, *Conversation* and *Conservation*. Note that the spaces in the phrases are ignored.

Extend the program so that it prompts the user to 'Enter a phrase:'. The program should display two additional messages to say whether or not **word1** is an anagram of the phrase and, whether or not **word2** is an anagram of the phrase.

Some example outputs are shown below. You could use this data to test your program.

```
Enter the first word: Listen
Enter the second word: Silent
Listen is an anagram of Silent
Listen is an anagram of Silent
Enter a phrase: Silence of the lambs
Listen is NOT an anagram of Silence of the lambs
Silent is NOT an anagram of Silence of the lambs
Enter the first word: conversation
Enter the second word: conservation
conversation is an anagram of conservation
conversation is an anagram of conservation
Enter a phrase: voices rant on
conversation is an anagram of voices rant on
conservation is an anagram of voices rant on
Enter the first word: Astronomer
Enter the second word: Moon
Astronomer is NOT an anagram of Moon
Astronomer is NOT an anagram of Moon
Enter a phrase: moon starrer
Astronomer is an anagram of moonstarer
Moon is NOT an anagram of moon starrer
```

OUTPUT

I will provide the updated Python code based on the requirements given in parts (i) to (vi):

```
python Copy code

# Question 16(a)
# Examination Number:

# function definition used in part (v)
def is_anagram(w1, w2):
    if sorted(w1) == sorted(w2):
        return True
    else:
        return False

word1 = input("Enter the first word: ").lower()
word2 = input("Enter the second word: ").lower()

# test whether the sorted strings are the same as each other
# if the sorted strings are the same then they must be anagrams
if (sorted(word1) == sorted(word2)):
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is an anagram of", word2.capitalize())
else:
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is NOT an anagram of", word2.capitalize())

# part (v)
if is_anagram(word1, word2):
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is an anagram of", word2.capitalize())

# part (vi)
phrase = input("Enter a phrase: ").lower().replace(" ", "")

if is_anagram(word1, phrase):
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is an anagram of", phrase.capitalize())
else:
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is NOT an anagram of", phrase.capitalize())

if is_anagram(word2, phrase):
    print(word2.capitalize(), "is an anagram of", phrase.capitalize())
else:
    print(word2.capitalize(), "is NOT an anagram of", phrase.capitalize())
```

This updated program incorporates all the requested changes and should produce the correct output as described in the question for each part.

Copy of the Output Code:

```
# Question 16(a)
# Examination Number:

# function definition used in part (v)
def is_anagram(w1, w2):
    if sorted(w1) == sorted(w2):
        return True
    else:
        return False

word1 = input("Enter the first word: ").lower()
word2 = input("Enter the second word: ").lower()

# test whether the sorted strings are the same as each other
# if the sorted strings are the same then they must be anagrams
if (sorted(word1) == sorted(word2)):
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is an anagram of", word2.capitalize())
else:
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is NOT an anagram of", word2.capitalize())

# part (v)
if is_anagram(word1, word2):
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is an anagram of", word2.capitalize())

# part (vi)
phrase = input("Enter a phrase: ").lower().replace(" ", "")

if is_anagram(word1, phrase):
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is an anagram of", phrase.capitalize())
else:
    print(word1.capitalize(), "is NOT an anagram of", phrase.capitalize())

if is_anagram(word2, phrase):
    print(word2.capitalize(), "is an anagram of", phrase.capitalize())
else:
    print(word2.capitalize(), "is NOT an anagram of", phrase.capitalize())
```

(3)

**A-Level Examination Paper 11 2021
Computer Science**

ChatGPT Prompts and Output

May 2023

Exam Papers and Marking Schemes:

<https://www.cambridgeinternational.org/programmes-and-qualifications/cambridge-international-as-and-a-level-computer-science-9618/past-papers/>

PROMPT

1 Anya scans an image into her computer for a school project.

(a) The scanned image is a bitmapped image.

(i) Complete the following table to describe the two terms about graphics.

Term Description

Pixel

.....
.....
.....

File header

.....
.....
.....

OUTPUT

Term: Pixel

Description:

A pixel (short for "picture element") is the smallest unit of a digital image or display. It is a single point in a graphic, represented by a specific color and brightness value. In a bitmapped image, the picture is composed of a grid of individual pixels, each of which contributes to the overall appearance of the image.

Term: File header

Description:

A file header is a section of data at the beginning of a file that contains important information about the file, such as its format, size, and other metadata. In the context of a bitmapped image, the file header stores details like the image's dimensions, color depth, compression type, and other properties required for the proper display and interpretation of the image by software applications.

PROMPT

(ii) The image is scanned with an image resolution of 1024×512 pixels, and a colour depth of 8 bits per pixel.

Calculate an estimate for the file size, giving your answer in mebibytes. Show your working.

Working

.....
.....
.....
.....

Answer mebibytes

OUTPUT

To calculate the file size, we need to multiply the image resolution by the color depth, and then convert the result to mebibytes.

Image resolution: 1024×512 pixels
Color depth: 8 bits per pixel

File size in bits = (Image resolution) $\times$ (Color depth)
File size in bits = $(1024 \times 512) \times 8$

Now, we will convert the file size from bits to bytes. There are 8 bits in a byte.

File size in bytes = File size in bits / 8
File size in bytes = $(1024 \times 512 \times 8) / 8$

Next, we will convert the file size from bytes to kibibytes (KiB). There are 1024 bytes in a kibibyte.

File size in kibibytes = File size in bytes / 1024
File size in kibibytes = $(1024 \times 512) / 1024$

Finally, we will convert the file size from kibibytes to mebibytes (MiB). There are 1024 kibibytes in a mebibyte.

File size in mebibytes = File size in kibibytes / 1024
File size in mebibytes = $512 / 1024$

Answer: 0.5 mebibytes Regenerate response

PROMPT

(b) The image is compressed using lossless compression. Identify **one** method of lossless compression that can be used to compress the image **and** describe how the method will reduce the file size.
Lossless compression method

.....
Description

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

OUTPUT

Lossless compression method: Run-length Encoding (RLE)

Description: Run-length encoding is a simple form of data compression that is particularly effective for images with large areas of the same color. The method works by replacing consecutive runs of the same color or data value with a single value and a count that indicates the length of the run. For example, if an image has a row with 10 consecutive red pixels, RLE would encode this as a single value for red and a count of 10. This compression technique reduces the file size by storing repetitive information more efficiently while still preserving the original quality of the image, as no data is lost during the compression process.

PROMPT

(c) One of the colours used in the image has the hexadecimal colour code:

#FC238A

FC is the amount of red, 23 is the amount of green and 8A is the amount of blue in the colour.

(i) Convert the hexadecimal code FC into denary.

.....

OUTPUT

To convert the hexadecimal code FC into denary, you can use the following method:

F = 15 (in hexadecimal)

C = 12 (in hexadecimal)

FC in denary = $(15 * 16^1) + (12 * 16^0)$

= $(15 * 16) + (12 * 1)$

= 240 + 12

= 252

So, the denary value of FC is 252.

PROMPT

(ii) The amount of green in binary is 00100011. This has the denary number 15 added to it to create a second colour.

Add the denary number 15 to the binary number 00100011 and give your answer in binary.

Perform the addition in binary. Show your working.

Working

.....

.....

.....

.....

Answer (in binary)

OUTPUT

To add the denary number 15 to the binary number 00100011, first convert 15 into binary and then perform binary addition.

15 in binary = 1111

Now add the two binary numbers:

00100011

• 00001111

00110010

So, the answer is 00110010 in binary.

PROMPT

(iii) Hexadecimal 23 in two's complement representation is 00100011. The denary number 10 needs to be subtracted from this value.

Subtract the denary number 10 from the two's complement representation 00100011.

Give your answer in binary. Show your working.

Working
.....
.....
.....
.....
.....
Answer (in binary)

OUTPUT

To subtract the denary number 10 from the two's complement representation 00100011, first convert 10 into binary and then perform binary subtraction (or addition using two's complement).

10 in binary = 1010

Now, find the two's complement of 1010:

1010

0101 (invert the bits)

- 0001 (add 1)

0110

Now add the two binary numbers (00100011 and the two's complement of 1010):

00100011

- 1110110

1 00011001 (discard the leftmost 1)

So, the answer is 00011001 in binary.

PROMPT

(d) Anya made sure that the image was not subject to any copyright before scanning it. Describe what is meant by **copyright**.

.....
.....
.....
.....

OUTPUT

Copyright is a legal protection granted to the creators of original works, such as literary, artistic, musical, and other intellectual property. It gives the copyright holder exclusive rights to reproduce, distribute, display, perform, or create derivative works based on the original work. This protection helps ensure that the creators are recognized for their efforts and can control the use of their work, preventing unauthorized copying or exploitation. Copyright laws vary by country but generally last for a specific duration, often the creator's lifetime plus a number of years after their death. Once the copyright term expires, the work enters the public domain, allowing it to be freely used, reproduced, and adapted by anyone without the need for permission from the copyright holder.

PROMPT

2 Bingwen's computer comes with an Operating System and utility software.

(a) Draw **one** line from each utility software to its correct description.

Utility software Description

Disk formatter

Defragmentation

Back-up

Disk repair

Scans software for errors and repairs the problems

Moves parts of files so that each file is contiguous in memory

Creates a copy of data that is no longer required

Sets up a disk so it is ready to store files

Creates a copy of data in case the original is lost

Scans for errors in a disk and corrects them

OUTPUT

Utility software Description

Disk formatter Sets up a disk so it is ready to store files

Defragmentation Moves parts of files so that each file is contiguous in memory

Back-up Creates a copy of data in case the original is lost

Disk repair Scans for errors in a disk and corrects them

PROMPT

(b) Identify **four** key management tasks that the Operating System will perform.

1

2

3

4

OUTPUT

1. Memory management: Allocating and deallocating memory resources for programs and processes, as well as managing memory access and protection.
2. Process management: Creating, scheduling, and terminating processes, managing process communication and synchronization, and handling process deadlocks.
3. File system management: Organizing, storing, and retrieving files and directories, as well as managing access control and file permissions.
4. Device management: Handling input/output operations, controlling and managing peripheral devices, and facilitating communication between devices and the operating system.

PROMPT

3 A processor has one general purpose register, the Accumulator (ACC), and several special purpose registers.

(a) Complete the following description of the role of the registers in the fetch-execute cycle by writing the missing registers.

The holds the address of the next instruction to be loaded. This address is sent to the

The holds the data fetched from this address.

This data is sent to the and the Control Unit decodes the instruction's opcode.

The is incremented.

OUTPUT

The Program Counter (PC) holds the address of the next instruction to be loaded. This address is sent to the Memory Address Register (MAR). The Memory Data Register (MDR) holds the data fetched from this address. This data is sent to the Instruction Register (IR) and the Control Unit decodes the instruction's opcode. The Program Counter (PC) is incremented.

PROMPT

(b) The following table shows part of the instruction set for a processor. The processor has one general purpose register, the Accumulator (ACC), and an Index Register (IX).

Instruction

Explanation

Opcode Operand

LDM #n Immediate addressing. Load the number n to ACC
LDD <address> Direct addressing. Load the contents of the location at the given address to ACC
LDI <address> Indirect addressing: The address to be used is at the given address. Load the contents of this second address to ACC
LDX <address> Indexed addressing. Form the address from <address> + the contents of the Index Register. Copy the contents of this calculated address to ACC
LDR #n Immediate addressing. Load the number n to IX
MOV <register> Move the contents of the accumulator to the given register (IX)
STO <address> Store contents of ACC at the given address
ADD <address> Add the contents of the given address to the ACC
INC <register> Add 1 to the contents of the register (ACC or IX)
CMP <address> Compare the contents of ACC with the contents of <address>
JPE <address> Following a compare instruction, jump to <address> if the compare was True
JPN <address> Following a compare instruction, jump to <address> if the compare was False
JMP <address> Jump to the given address
OUT Output to the screen the character whose ASCII value is stored in ACC
END Return control to the operating system
LSL #n Bits in ACC are shifted logically n places to the left. Zeros are introduced on the right hand end
LSR #n Bits in ACC are shifted logically n places to the right. Zeros are introduced on the left hand end
<address> can be an absolute address or a symbolic address
denotes a denary number, e.g. #123

The current contents of the main memory and selected values from the ASCII character set are shown.

Address Instruction ASCII code table (selected codes only)

200	LDD	365	ASCII code Character
201	CMP	366	65 A
202	JPE	209	66 B
203	INC	ACC	67 C
204	STO	365	68 D
205	MOV	IX	
206	LDX	365	
207	OUT		

208 JMP 200

209 END

...

365 1

366 3

367 65

368 66

IX 0

Complete the trace table for the program currently in main memory.

Instruction

address ACC

Memory address

IX Output

365 366 367 368

1 3 65 66 0

OUTPUT

Here's the completed trace table for the program currently in main memory:

Instruction address	ACC	Memory address	365	366	367	368	IX	Output
200		LDD 365	1	3	65	66	0	
201	1	CMP 366	1	3	65	66	0	
202	1	JPE 209	1	3	65	66	0	
203	2	INC ACC	1	3	65	66	0	
204	2	STO 365	2	3	65	66	0	
205	2	MOV IX	2	3	65	66	2	
206	2	LDX 365	2	3	65	66	2	
207	65	OUT	2	3	65	66	2	A
208	65	JMP 200	2	3	65	66	2	
200	65	LDD 365	2	3	65	66	2	
201	2	CMP 366	2	3	65	66	2	
202	2	JPE 209	2	3	65	66	2	
203	3	INC ACC	2	3	65	66	2	
204	3	STO 365	3	3	65	66	2	
205	3	MOV IX	3	3	65	66	3	
206	3	LDX 365	3	3	65	66	3	
207	66	OUT	3	3	65	66	3	B
208	66	JMP 200	3	3	65	66	3	

Please note that the output is shown in the "Output" column as the character representation (A, B) of the ASCII code stored in the ACC.

PROMPT

(c) (i) The Accumulator currently contains the binary number:

0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1

Write the contents of the Accumulator after the processor has executed the following instruction:

LSL #2

OUTPUT

After executing the LSL #2 instruction, the Accumulator's contents will be shifted 2 places to the left with zeros introduced on the right-hand end. The initial contents of the Accumulator are:

00110101

After shifting 2 places to the left:

11010100

So, the contents of the Accumulator after executing LSL #2 are:

11010100

PROMPT

(ii) The Accumulator currently contains the binary number:

0 0 1 1 0 1 0 1

Identify the mathematical operation that the following instruction will perform on the contents of the accumulator.

LSR #3

.....

OUTPUT

The LSR #3 instruction will perform a logical right shift on the contents of the Accumulator. It shifts the bits in the Accumulator 3 places to the right, with zeros introduced on the left-hand end. The initial contents of the Accumulator are:

00110101

After shifting 3 places to the right:

00001101

So, the LSR #3 instruction performs a logical right shift by 3 positions on the contents of the Accumulator.

PROMPT

4 Melinda and her friends set up a peer-to-peer network between their computers to share data.

(a) Describe the key features of a peer-to-peer network.

.....
.....

OUTPUT

A peer-to-peer (P2P) network is a type of network in which computers, also known as nodes or peers, share resources and data directly with one another without the need for a centralized server. The key features of a peer-to-peer network are:

1. **Decentralized architecture:** There is no central server or authority controlling the network. Each computer in the network acts as both a client and a server, allowing them to share resources and data directly with one another.
2. **Scalability:** P2P networks can easily expand as new nodes join the network, without the need for additional central servers or infrastructure.
3. **Resource sharing:** Each peer in the network can share its resources, such as storage, processing power, or bandwidth, with other peers, increasing the overall availability of resources in the network.
4. **Self-organization:** P2P networks can automatically reconfigure themselves as nodes join or leave the network, ensuring that the network remains functional and efficient.
5. **Redundancy and fault tolerance:** Since data is often stored and shared across multiple peers, P2P networks can provide a higher level of redundancy and fault tolerance compared to centralized systems.
6. **Data distribution:** P2P networks enable efficient distribution of large files by breaking them into smaller pieces and sharing them across multiple peers, which can then be downloaded and reassembled by other peers in the network.

PROMPT

(b) Describe **two** drawbacks to Melinda and her friends of using a peer-to-peer network.

1

.....
.....
.....

2

.....

OUTPUT

- 1. Security and privacy concerns: In a peer-to-peer network, data is shared directly between peers, which can expose the computers and their data to various security threats. This includes the risk of sharing infected files or malicious software, as well as potential privacy breaches due to unauthorized access to shared files and folders. Additionally, P2P networks are often associated with copyright infringement and illegal file sharing, which can lead to legal consequences for the users involved.
- 2. Uneven resource distribution and performance: Since each peer in the network contributes its own resources, such as processing power, storage, and bandwidth, the overall performance of the network can be heavily influenced by the individual capabilities of each participating computer. This can lead to uneven resource distribution and varying performance levels, with some peers potentially experiencing slower data transfers or limited access to shared resources if other peers in the network have limited resources or low bandwidth. Moreover, the performance of the network may suffer if a significant number of peers go offline or become unavailable, as this can lead to a decrease in the available resources and a disruption in data sharing.

PROMPT

c) Melinda connects her laptop to the internet through her router.

(i) Tick (3) **one** box in each row to identify whether the task is performed by the router or not.

Task Performed by router

Not performed by router

Receives packets from devices

Finds the IP address of a Uniform Resource Locator (URL)

Directs each packet to all devices attached to it

Stores the IP and/or MAC address of all devices attached to it

OUTPUT

Task Performed by

router

Not performed

by router

Receives packets from devices ✓

Finds the IP address of a Uniform Resource Locator (URL) ✓

Directs each packet to all devices attached to it ✓

Stores the IP and/or MAC address of all devices attached to it ✓

PROMPT

ii) Melinda mainly uses the internet to watch films and play computer games. Tick (3) **one** box to identify whether Melinda should connect to the router using a wired or wireless network **and** justify your choice.

Wired

Wireless

Justification

OUTPUT

Wired ✓

Wireless

Justification: A wired connection is typically more stable and provides faster speeds, which is important for activities like watching films and playing computer games that require a reliable and fast internet connection. Additionally, wired connections have lower latency, which can be crucial for online gaming.

PROMPT

(d) Melinda sends emails from her webmail account (email account accessed through a website).

Explain whether Melinda is using the internet, or the World Wide Web (WWW), or both.

.....

OUTPUT

Melinda is using both the internet and the World Wide Web (WWW). The internet is the global network of interconnected computer networks that allows devices to communicate and share information with each other. The World Wide Web is a system of interlinked hypertext documents, such as websites, that can be accessed through the internet using a web browser. When Melinda sends emails from her webmail account, she is accessing her email through a website (which is a part of the WWW) and sending the email via the internet.

PROMPT

5 Kiara has a washing machine and a refrigerator.
(a) She has an embedded system in her washing machine.
Describe what is meant by an **embedded system**, using the washing machine as an example.
.....

OUTPUT

An embedded system is a combination of hardware and software designed to perform a specific function within a larger system. It is called "embedded" because it is integrated into the device to control its functions and operations.

In the case of Kiara's washing machine, the embedded system manages various tasks such as controlling water temperature, spin speed, washing cycle duration, and other settings. The hardware components, like microcontrollers and sensors, work together with the software programmed to execute the specific functions required for the washing machine to operate efficiently and effectively. This embedded system allows the washing machine to perform its tasks automatically and optimally, based on the user's selected settings.

PROMPT

(b) The washing machine’s embedded system makes use of both Random Access Memory (RAM) and Read Only Memory (ROM).

State the purpose of RAM and ROM within the washing machine’s embedded system.

RAM

.....

ROM

OUTPUT

RAM: Random Access Memory is a type of volatile memory used in the washing machine's embedded system to store temporary data and information required during its operation. It holds data such as user-selected settings, sensor readings, and intermediate calculations. RAM allows the system to quickly access and modify this data as needed. However, the data stored in RAM is lost when the washing machine is turned off or loses power.

ROM: Read Only Memory is a type of non-volatile memory used in the washing machine's embedded system to store essential, permanent data and instructions, such as the firmware and pre-programmed settings. ROM retains its data even when the washing machine is turned off or loses power. The embedded system's microcontroller reads from ROM to execute the necessary instructions for the proper functioning of the washing machine, but the data in ROM cannot be easily modified or overwritten.

PROMPT

(c) The temperature in her refrigerator must be kept between 4 and 6 degrees Celsius. The microprocessor in the refrigerator turns on the cooling if the temperature is too high, and turns off the cooling if the temperature is too low. Explain why the system in the refrigerator is a control and not a monitoring system.

.....

.....

OUTPUT

The system in the refrigerator is a control system and not a monitoring system because it actively manages and regulates the temperature within the desired range (4-6 degrees Celsius). When the temperature rises above the upper limit or falls below the lower limit, the microprocessor takes corrective actions by turning on or off the cooling mechanism as necessary. This ensures that the temperature stays within the specified range.

A monitoring system, on the other hand, would only observe and report the temperature without taking any action to control or adjust it. It might provide alerts or notifications when the temperature goes outside the desired range but would not actively intervene to maintain the desired temperature levels within the refrigerator.

PROMPT	
<p>6 Each of the following algorithms performs data validation. State the type of validation check that each of the algorithms performs.</p> <p>(a)</p> <pre>INPUT x IF x < 0 OR x > 10 THEN OUTPUT "Invalid" ENDIF</pre> <p>.....</p>	
OUTPUT	
Range check	

PROMPT	
<p>(b)</p> <pre>INPUT x IF x = "" THEN OUTPUT "Invalid" ENDIF</pre> <p>.....</p>	
OUTPUT	
Presence check	

PROMPT	
<p>(c)</p> <pre>INPUT x IF NOT(x = "Red" OR x = "Yellow" OR x = "Blue") THEN OUTPUT "Invalid" ENDIF</pre> <p>.....</p>	
OUTPUT	
Lookup check	

PROMPT

7 Bobby and Kim are discussing databases.

(a) Bobby tells Kim that a file-based approach is usually better than a relational database.

Explain why Bobby is incorrect.

.....

OUTPUT

Bobby is incorrect because a relational database offers several advantages over a file-based approach. Some of these advantages include: 📄 👍 🗨

1. **Data consistency:** Relational databases ensure that the data is consistent across the entire database, whereas a file-based approach can lead to data redundancy and inconsistencies.
2. **Scalability:** Relational databases are more scalable and can handle a large amount of data, whereas file-based systems have limitations in terms of data storage and retrieval.
3. **Security:** Relational databases provide better security mechanisms, such as access control and data encryption, compared to file-based systems.
4. **Data integrity:** Relational databases enforce data integrity through constraints and relationships, ensuring that the data remains accurate and valid.
5. **Querying and data manipulation:** Relational databases offer powerful querying capabilities and allow for complex data manipulation using Structured Query Language (SQL), whereas file-based systems have limited query options.
6. **Concurrent access:** Relational databases allow multiple users to access and modify the data concurrently, while maintaining data consistency, which is more difficult to achieve in a file-based approach.

PROMPT

(b) Bobby has a shop that sells products to customers. His database will store data about his customers, their payment details, orders and the products he sells. Customers will have login details to access their accounts. The database will update customers' payment and login details without keeping any historical records.

(i) Give **one** example of each of the following relationships from Bobby's database.
one-to-one

.....
.....

one-to-many

.....
.....

many-to-many

.....

OUTPUT

one-to-one:

Customer login details and customer account.

Each customer has a unique set of login details associated with their account, and each account has one set of login details.

one-to-many:

Customer and orders.

One customer can place multiple orders, but each order is associated with only one customer.

many-to-many:

Products and orders.

A single order can contain multiple products, and each product can be part of multiple orders. This relationship is typically represented using a junction table (e.g., OrderItems) that links the two entities, storing the quantity of each product in each order.

PROMPT

(ii) Tick (3) **one** box to identify the relationship that cannot be directly implemented in a normalised relational database.

Relationship Tick (3)

one-to-one

one-to-many

many-to-many

OUTPUT

Relationship Tick (✓)

one-to-one

one-to-many

many-to-many ✓

Many-to-many relationships cannot be directly implemented in a normalized relational database. Instead, they are typically represented using a junction table (also known as an associative table or linking table) that links the two entities and stores additional information about the relationship.

PROMPT

(iii) Bobby wants to name his database `SHOPORDERS`.

Write a Data Definition Language (DDL) statement to define a new database with the name `SHOPORDERS`.

OUTPUT

To create a new database named `SHOPORDERS`, you can use the following Data Definition Language (DDL) statement:

sql

Copy code

```
CREATE DATABASE SHOPORDERS;
```

This SQL statement will create a new database with the name `SHOPORDERS`.

PROMPT

(c) A database has a data dictionary.
Give **three** items that are stored in a data dictionary.

- 1
- 2
- 3

OUTPUT

A data dictionary is a repository of metadata that stores information about a database's structure, objects, and organization. Three items that are typically stored in a data dictionary include:

- 1. Table definitions: This includes information about each table in the database, such as table names, column names, data types, constraints, and relationships with other tables.
- 2. Indexes: Information about the indexes created on the tables to improve query performance, including index names, associated tables, indexed columns, and index types (e.g., unique, clustered, or non-clustered).
- 3. Views: Descriptions of database views, which are virtual tables that present a specific subset or combination of data from one or more tables. This includes view names, the underlying SQL query or definition, and any associated access permissions.

PROMPT

8 Tick (3) **one** box in each row to identify the logic gate that each statement describes.

Statement AND NAND NOR XOR OR

The output is 1 only when both inputs are 1

The output is 1 only when both inputs are different

The output is 1 only when both inputs are 0

OUTPUT

Statement | AND | NAND | NOR | XOR | OR

The output is 1 only when both inputs are 1 | 3 | | | |

The output is 1 only when both inputs are different | | | | 3 |

The output is 1 only when both inputs are 0 | | | 3 | |

(4)

**A-Level Examination Paper 21 2021
Computer Science**

ChatGPT Prompts and Output

May 2023

Exam Papers and Marking Schemes:

<https://www.cambridgeinternational.org/programmes-and-qualifications/cambridge-international-as-and-a-level-computer-science-9618/past-papers/>

PROMPT

This is the INSERT

Note: An error occurs if a function call is not properly formed, or if the parameters are incorrect.

STRING Functions

LEFT(ThisString : STRING, x : INTEGER) RETURNS STRING

returns leftmost x characters from ThisString

Example: LEFT("ABCDEFGH", 3) returns "ABC"

RIGHT(ThisString : STRING, x : INTEGER) RETURNS STRING

returns rightmost x characters from ThisString

Example: RIGHT("ABCDEFGH", 3) returns "FGH"

MID(ThisString : STRING, x : INTEGER, y : INTEGER) RETURNS STRING

returns a string of length y starting at position x from ThisString

Example: MID("ABCDEFGH", 2, 3) returns "BCD"

LENGTH(ThisString : STRING) RETURNS INTEGER

returns the integer value representing the length of ThisString

Example: LENGTH("Happy Days") returns 10

LCASE(ThisChar : CHAR) RETURNS CHAR

returns the character value representing the lower case equivalent of ThisChar

Characters that are not upper case alphabetic are returned unchanged

Example: LCASE('W') returns 'w'

UCASE(ThisChar : CHAR) RETURNS CHAR

returns the character value representing the upper case equivalent of ThisChar

Characters that are not lower case alphabetic are returned unchanged

Example: UCASE('a') returns 'A'

TO_UPPER(ThisString : STRING) RETURNS STRING

returns a string formed by converting all characters of ThisString to upper case

Example: TO_UPPER("Error 803") returns "ERROR 803"

TO_LOWER(ThisString : STRING) RETURNS STRING

returns a string formed by converting all characters of ThisString to lower case

Example: TO_LOWER("JIM 803") returns "jim 803"

NUM_TO_STR(x : <data type>) RETURNS STRING

returns a string representation of a numeric value

Note: <data type> may be REAL or INTEGER

Example: NUM_TO_STR(87.5) returns "87.5"

STR_TO_NUM(x : <data type1>) RETURNS <data type2>

returns a numeric representation of a string

Note: <data type1> may be CHAR or STRING

Note: <data type2> may be REAL or INTEGER

Example: STR_TO_NUM("23.45") returns 23.45

IS_NUM(ThisString : STRING) RETURNS BOOLEAN

returns the value TRUE if ThisString represents a valid numeric value

Note: <data type> may be CHAR or STRING

Example: IS_NUM("12.36") returns TRUE

Example: IS_NUM("-12.36") returns TRUE

Example: IS_NUM("12.3a") returns FALSE

ASC(ThisChar : CHAR) RETURNS INTEGER

returns an integer value (the ASCII value) of ThisChar

Example: ASC('A') returns 65

CHR(x : INTEGER) RETURNS CHAR

returns the character whose integer value (the ASCII value) is x

Example: CHR(87) returns 'W'

NUMERIC Functions

INT(x : REAL) RETURNS INTEGER

returns the integer part of x

Example: INT(27.5415) returns 27

RAND(x : INTEGER) RETURNS REAL

returns a real number in the range 0 to x (not inclusive of x)

Example: RAND(87) could return 35.43

DATE Functions

Note: Date format is assumed to be DDMMYYYY unless otherwise stated.

DAY(ThisDate : DATE) RETURNS INTEGER

returns the current day number from ThisDate

Example: DAY(4/10/2003) returns 4

MONTH(ThisDate : DATE) RETURNS INTEGER

returns the current month number from ThisDate

Example: MONTH(4/10/2003) returns 10

YEAR(ThisDate : DATE) RETURNS INTEGER

returns the current year number from ThisDate

Example: YEAR(4/10/2003) returns 2003

DAYINDEX(ThisDate : DATE) RETURNS INTEGER

returns the current day index number from ThisDate where Sunday = 1, Monday = 2, Tuesday = 3 etc.

Example: DAYINDEX(12/05/2020) returns 3

SETDATE(Day, Month, Year : INTEGER) RETURNS DATE

returns a variable of type DATE

NOW() RETURNS DATE

returns the current date

OTHER Functions

EOF(FileName : STRING) RETURNS BOOLEAN

returns TRUE if there are no more lines to be read from file FileName

Note: This function will generate an ERROR if the file is not already open in READ mode

OPERATORS

&

Concatenates (joins) two strings

Example: "Summer" & " " & "Pudding" evaluates to "Summer Pudding"

Note: This operator may also be used to concatenate a character with a string

AND Performs a logical AND on two Boolean values

Example: TRUE AND FALSE evaluates to FALSE

OR Performs a logical OR on two Boolean values

Example: TRUE OR FALSE evaluates to TRUE

NOT Performs a logical NOT on a Boolean value

Example: NOT TRUE evaluates to FALSE

MOD Finds the remainder when one number is divided by another

Example: 10 MOD 3 evaluates to 1

DIV Finds the quotient when one number is divided by another

Example 10 DIV 3 evaluates to 3

Note: An error is generated if an operator is used with a value or values of an incorrect type.

PROMPT

1 (a) A program is being developed to help manage the membership of a football club.

Complete the following identifier table.

Example

value Explanation Variable name Data type

"Wong" The preferred name of the member joining the football club

FALSE

A value to indicate whether an existing member of the club lives at the same address

19/02/1983 When the member joined the football club

1345

The number of points a member has earned. Members of the club earn points for different activities.

OUTPUT

Value	Explanation	Variable name	Data type
"Wong"	The preferred name of the member joining the football club	preferredName	STRING
FALSE	A value to indicate whether an existing member of the club lives at the same address	sameAddress	BOOLEAN
19/02/1983	When the member joined the football club	joinDate	DATE
1345	The number of points a member has earned. Members of the club earn points for different activities.	pointsEarned	INTEGER

PROMPT

(b) Each pseudocode statement in the following table may contain an error due to the incorrect

use of the function or operator.

Describe the error in each case, or write 'NO ERROR' if the statement contains no error.

You can assume that none of the variables referenced are of an incorrect type.

Statement Error

Result 2 & 4

SubString MID("pseudocode", 4, 1)

IF x = 3 OR 4 THEN

Result Status AND INT(x/2)

Message "Done" + LENGTH(MyString)

OUTPUT

Statement	Error
Result 2 & 4	NO ERROR (although the result will be a string, not a number)
SubString MID("pseudocode", 4, 1)	NO ERROR
IF x = 3 OR 4 THEN	Error: Should be "IF x = 3 OR x = 4 THEN"
Result Status AND INT(x/2)	Error: Should be "Result = Status AND INT(x/2)"
Message "Done" + LENGTH(MyString)	Error: Should be "Message = "Done" & LENGTH(MyString)"

PROMPT

(c) The following data items need to be stored for each student in a group:

- student name (a string)
- test score (an integer).

State a suitable data structure and justify your answer.

Structure

.....
Justification

OUTPUT

Structure: Record (or Struct, depending on the programming language)

Justification: A record (or struct) is suitable because it allows you to group together multiple data items with different data types (in this case, a string for student name and an integer for test score) into a single data structure. This makes it easier to manage and manipulate the data related to each student as a single unit.

PROMPT

2 (a) Four program modules form part of a program for a library. A description of the relationship between the modules is summarised as follows:

Module name Description

`UpdateLoan()` • Calls either `LoanExtend()` or `LoanReturn()`

`LoanExtend()`

- Called with parameters `LoanID` and `BookID`
- Calls `CheckReserve()` to see whether the book has been reserved for another library user
- Returns `TRUE` if the loan has been extended, otherwise returns `FALSE`

`CheckReserve()`

- Called with `BookID`
- Returns `TRUE` if the book has been reserved, otherwise returns `FALSE`

`LoanReturn()`

- Called with parameters `LoanID` and `BookID`
- Returns a `REAL` (which is the value of the fine to be paid in the case of an overdue loan)

Draw a structure chart to show the relationship between the four modules and the parameters passed between them.

OUTPUT

Below is the structure chart representing the relationship between the four modules and the parameters passed between them.

In the structure chart, the `UpdateLoan()` module calls either `LoanExtend()` or `LoanReturn()`. `LoanExtend()` and `LoanReturn()` both take `LoanID` and `BookID` as parameters. `LoanExtend()` calls `CheckReserve()` with `BookID` as a parameter.

PROMPT

(b) The definition for module `LoanReturn()` is amended as follows:

Module name Description

`LoanReturn()`

Called with parameters `LoanID`, `BookID` and `Fine`

The module code checks whether the book has been returned on time and then assigns a new value to `Fine`

- `LoanID` and `BookID` are of type `STRING`
- `Fine` is of type `REAL`

Write the pseudocode header for the **amended** module `LoanReturn()`.

OUTPUT

In pseudocode, the header for the amended module `LoanReturn()` could look like this:

less

Copy code

```
PROCEDURE LoanReturn(LoanID: STRING, BookID: STRING, Fine: REAL)
```

Here, `PROCEDURE` is used to declare the function, followed by the name of the function (in this case, `LoanReturn`). Then, in the parentheses, the parameters are listed along with their data types. `LoanID` and `BookID` are declared as `STRING`, and `Fine` is declared as `REAL`. The data types are written after the parameter names, separated by colons.

PROMPT

(c) A program will:

- input 50 unique integer values
- output the largest value
- output the average of the values **excluding** the largest value.

Draw a program flowchart to represent the algorithm.

Variable declarations are **not** required.

It is not necessary to check that each input value is unique.

OUTPUT

Here's a flowchart representing the algorithm:

```
bash Copy code

1. Start
2. Initialize: largest = 0, sum = 0, count = 0
3. FOR i = 1 TO 50
  |
4.  | INPUT number
  |
5.  | IF number > largest THEN
  |  |
6.  |  | sum = sum + largest
  |  | count = count + 1
  |  |
7.  |  | largest = number
  |  |
8.  | ELSE
  |  |
9.  |  | sum = sum + number
  |  | count = count + 1
  |  |
10. | END IF
  |
11. END FOR
12. Calculate average: average = sum / count
13. OUTPUT largest, average
14. End
```

PROMPT

3 (a) A concert venue uses a program to calculate admission prices and store information about ticket sales.

A number of arrays are used to store data. The computer is switched off overnight and data

has to be input again at the start of each day before any tickets can be sold. This process is

very time consuming.

(i) Explain how the program could use text files to speed up the process.

OUTPUT

The program could use text files to speed up the process by storing the data in these files and reading from them when the program starts. This way, the data will be persisted across sessions, and there won't be a need to input the data again each day. Here's how this can be done:

1. When the data is input for the first time, the program should store the data in appropriate text files, organized in a way that makes it easy to read and write the data. For example, separate text files can be created for admission prices, ticket sales, and other relevant information.
2. When the program starts, it should check if the text files containing the data exist. If they do, the program should read the data from these files and store it in the appropriate arrays or data structures.
3. During the day, as changes are made to the admission prices or ticket sales, the program should update the corresponding text files accordingly to ensure the data is always up to date.
4. When the computer is switched off and turned back on the next day, the program will read the data from the text files, eliminating the need to input the data manually again. This will save time and reduce the chances of data entry errors.

PROMPT

(ii) State the characteristic of text files that allow them to be used as explained in **part (a)(i)**.

OUTPUT

The characteristic of text files that allows them to be used as explained in part (a)(i) is their ability to store data in a human-readable format that can be easily read and written by a program. Text files can be easily created, modified, and accessed using standard file input/output operations provided by most programming languages, making them a convenient choice for persisting data across sessions. Additionally, they can be opened and edited using any text editor, which makes it easy to view and modify the data if necessary.

PROMPT

(iii) Information about ticket sales will be stored as a booking. The booking requires the following data:

- name of person booking
- number of people in the group (for example a family ticket or a school party)
- event type.

Suggest how data relating to each booking may be stored in a text file.

.....

OUTPUT

To store data relating to each booking in a text file, you can use a structured format like CSV (Comma Separated Values) or TSV (Tab Separated Values). These formats are easily readable and can be processed by various software programs, including spreadsheet applications like Microsoft Excel or Google Sheets.

Here's a suggested structure for storing the booking information in a CSV file:

1. Create a text file with a ".csv" extension (e.g., "bookings.csv").
2. Define the header row in the file, which represents the column names, separated by commas:

```
name_of_person_booking,number_of_people_in_group,event_type
```

3. For each booking, add a new row to the file with the required data, separated by commas:

```
John Doe,4,Concert  
Jane Smith,2,Theater
```

In the example above, the first row represents the header, and the following rows represent individual bookings. The values are separated by commas, with each column representing a different piece of data (name of person booking, number of people in the group, and event type).

To store the data in a TSV file, follow the same structure but separate the values with tabs instead of commas.

Keep in mind that if any of the values (such as the name of the person booking) contain commas, you should wrap that value in double quotes to avoid confusion. For example:

```
ardulno  
"John Doe, Jr.",4,Concert
```

This structured text file format allows you to easily add, remove, or modify booking information while maintaining a human-readable and easily parsable format.

PROMPT

(b) A procedure `Preview()` will:

- take the name of a text file as a parameter
- output a warning message if the file is empty
- otherwise output the first five lines from the file (or as many lines as there are in the file if this number is less than five).

Write pseudocode for the procedure `Preview()`.

OUTPUT

Here is a pseudocode representation of the procedure `Preview()`:

vbnet

Copy code

```
PROCEDURE Preview(fileName: STRING)
  DECLARE lines: LIST OF STRING
  TRY
    OPEN file identified by fileName for READING AS file
    SET lines TO read first 5 lines from file
    IF length of lines IS 0 THEN
      OUTPUT "Warning: The file is empty."
    ELSE
      FOR EACH line IN lines DO
        OUTPUT line
      END FOR
    END IF
    CLOSE file
  CATCH file opening errors
    OUTPUT "Error: The file could not be found."
  END TRY
END PROCEDURE
```

This pseudocode takes a filename as input, opens the file, reads the first five lines (if they exist), and then outputs those lines. It also handles the case where the file is empty or does not exist. Please note that pseudocode does not have a strict syntax and can vary in style.

PROMPT

4 Study the following pseudocode. Line numbers are for reference only.

```
10 FUNCTION Convert(Name : STRING) RETURNS STRING
11
12 DECLARE Flag: BOOLEAN
13 DECLARE Index : INTEGER
14 DECLARE ThisChar : CHAR
15 DECLARE NewName : STRING
16
17 CONSTANT SPACECHAR = ' '
18
19 Flag TRUE
20 Index 1
21 NewName "" // formatted name string
22
23 WHILE Index <= LENGTH(Name)
24   ThisChar MID(Name, Index, 1)
25   IF Flag = TRUE THEN
26     NewName NewName & UCASE(ThisChar)
27   IF ThisChar <> SPACECHAR THEN
28     Flag FALSE
29   ENDIF
30   ELSE
31     NewName NewName & ThisChar
32   ENDIF
33   IF ThisChar = SPACECHAR THEN
34     Flag TRUE
35   ENDIF
36   Index Index + 1
37 ENDWHILE
38
39 RETURN NewName
40
41 ENDFUNCTION
```

(a) Complete the trace table below by dry running the function when it is called as follows:

Result Convert("in a Cup")

Note: The symbol '∇' has been used to represent a space character.

Use this symbol for any space characters in the trace table.

The first row has been completed for you.

Name	Flag	Index	NewName	ThisChar
------	------	-------	---------	----------

"in a Cup"				
------------	--	--	--	--

OUTPUT

The pseudocode is a function `Convert()` which transforms the input string `Name` by capitalizing the first character of each word. A 'word' in this context is defined as a sequence of characters separated by spaces. The `∇` symbol is used to represent a space character.

Below is the completed trace table for the function when called as `Convert("∇in∇a∇∇Cup")`.

Name	Flag	Index	NewName	ThisChar
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	True	1	""	∇
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	True	2	"I"	i
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	False	3	"In"	n
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	False	4	"In∇"	∇
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	True	5	"In∇A"	a
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	False	6	"In∇A∇"	∇
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	True	7	"In∇A∇∇"	∇
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	True	8	"In∇A∇∇C"	c
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	False	9	"In∇A∇∇Cu"	u
"∇in∇a∇∇Cup"	False	10	"In∇A∇∇Cup"	p

The function `Convert("∇in∇a∇∇Cup")` would return `"In∇A∇∇Cup"`. The 'words' separated by spaces ("`∇`") have their first letters capitalized. The multiple space characters between "A" and "Cup" are preserved.

PROMPT

b) The pseudocode for `Convert()` contains a conditional loop.

State a more appropriate loop structure.

Justify your answer.

Loop structure

.....

Justification

OUTPUT

Loop structure: For loop

Justification:

A more appropriate loop structure for the `Convert()` function is the "for loop" because the number of iterations is predetermined by the length of the input string (`Name`). Using a "for loop" simplifies the code by removing the need for the `Index` variable to be explicitly incremented and checked against the string length.

Here's an example of how the `Convert()` function could be rewritten using a "for loop":

```
vbnet Copy code
FUNCTION Convert(Name : STRING) RETURNS STRING
    DECLARE Flag: BOOLEAN
    DECLARE ThisChar : CHAR
    DECLARE NewName : STRING
    CONSTANT SPACECHAR = ' '

    Flag TRUE
    NewName "" // formatted name string

    FOR Index FROM 1 TO LENGTH(Name)
        ThisChar MID(Name, Index, 1)
        IF Flag = TRUE THEN
            NewName NewName & UCASE(ThisChar)
            IF ThisChar <> SPACECHAR THEN
                Flag FALSE
            ENDIF
        ELSE
            NewName NewName & ThisChar
        ENDIF
        IF ThisChar = SPACECHAR THEN
            Flag TRUE
        ENDIF
    ENDFOR

    RETURN NewName
ENDFUNCTION
```

Using the "for loop" structure, the code becomes more concise, easier to read, and less prone to errors related to manual incrementation of the loop index variable.

PROMPT

(c) Two changes need to be made to the algorithm.
Change 1: Convert to lower case any character that is not the first character after a space.
Change 2: Replace multiple spaces with a single space.
(i) Change 1 may be implemented by modifying one line of the pseudocode.
Write the modified line.
.....

OUTPUT

To implement Change 1 in the algorithm, you can modify line 31 in the pseudocode:

```
31 NewName NewName & LCASE(ThisChar)
```

PROMPT

(ii) Change 2 may be implemented by moving one line of the pseudocode.
Write the number of the line to be moved and state its new position.
Line number
New position

OUTPUT

To implement Change 2 in the algorithm, you can move line 35 to a new position:

Line number: 35

New position: Between lines 28 and 29, becoming the new line 29.

PROMPT

5 A global 2D array `Result` of type `INTEGER` is used to store a list of exam candidate numbers together with their marks. The array contains 2000 elements, organised as 1000 rows and 2 columns. Column 1 contains the candidate number and column 2 contains the mark for the corresponding candidate. All elements contain valid exam result data. A procedure `Sort()` is needed to sort `Result` into ascending order of mark using an efficient bubble sort algorithm. Write pseudocode for the procedure `Sort()`.

OUTPUT

Here's the pseudocode for the `Sort()` procedure using an efficient bubble sort algorithm:

```
less Copy code

Procedure Sort():
  DECLARE n: INTEGER
  DECLARE swapped: BOOLEAN
  DECLARE tempMark: INTEGER
  DECLARE tempCandidate: INTEGER

  n = 1000 // Number of rows in the Result array

  Repeat
    swapped = FALSE

    For i = 1 TO n-1
      If Result[i][2] > Result[i+1][2] Then
        // Swap marks
        tempMark = Result[i][2]
        Result[i][2] = Result[i+1][2]
        Result[i+1][2] = tempMark

        // Swap candidate numbers
        tempCandidate = Result[i][1]
        Result[i][1] = Result[i+1][1]
        Result[i+1][1] = tempCandidate

        swapped = TRUE
      End If
    End For

    n = n - 1
  Until swapped = FALSE

End Procedure
```

This pseudocode describes an optimized version of the bubble sort algorithm for sorting the 2D `Result` array based on the marks (column 2) in ascending order. It uses a "swapped" flag to keep track of whether any swaps were made in the previous iteration, allowing the loop to exit early if the array is already sorted.

PROMPT

6 The following diagram represents an Abstract Data Type (ADT) for a linked list.

A

The free list is as follows:

C D E $\emptyset$

$\emptyset$

(a) Explain how a node containing data value B is added to the list in alphabetic sequence.

OUTPUT

To add a node containing the data value B to the linked list in alphabetical sequence, follow these steps:

1. Create a new node with the data value B.
2. Iterate through the linked list, starting from the head node A, to find the appropriate position for the new node (in this case, between nodes A and C).
3. Keep track of the current node and the previous node while iterating through the list.
4. Once the appropriate position is found, update the pointers as follows:
 - a. Set the "next" pointer of the previous node (A) to point to the new node (B).
 - b. Set the "next" pointer of the new node (B) to point to the current node (C).

After performing these steps, the new node containing the data value B will be inserted into the linked list in alphabetical sequence:

A → B → C → D → E → $\emptyset$

PROMPT

(b) Describe how the linked list in **part (a)** may be implemented using variables and arrays.

OUTPUT

To implement the linked list from part (a) using variables and arrays, you can use parallel arrays to store the data values and the corresponding "next" pointers (indices).

1. Create two arrays:

- ``dataArray``: an array to store the data values of the nodes.
- ``NextArray``: an array to store the "next" pointers (indices) of the nodes.

2. Initialize the arrays:

- For the linked list $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow \emptyset$:

``dataArray``: ["A", "B", "C", "D", "E"]

``NextArray``: [1, 2, 3, 4, -1] (Using -1 to represent $\emptyset$, the end of the list)

3. Use a variable ``HeadIndex`` to store the index of the head node in the ``dataArray``. In this case, ``HeadIndex` = 0` (since "A" is at index 0).

To traverse the linked list, start from the head node (using ``HeadIndex``) and follow the "next" pointers (indices) stored in the ``NextArray``. For example, to go from node A to node B, look up the "next" pointer for A in the ``NextArray`` (1) and use it as the index in the ``dataArray`` to access the data value "B".

To insert or delete nodes, update the ``dataArray`` and ``NextArray`` accordingly, while ensuring that the "next" pointers in the ``NextArray`` are maintained correctly to preserve the order of the linked list.

PROMPT

7 A program is needed to take a string containing a full name and produce a new string of initials.

Some words in the full name will be ignored. For example, "the", "and", "of", "for" and "to" may all be ignored.

Each letter of the abbreviated string must be upper case.

For example:

Full name Initials

Integrated Development Environment IDE

The American Standard Code for Information Interchange ASCII

The programmer has decided to use a global variable `FNString` of type `STRING` to store the full name.

It is assumed that:

- words in the full name string are separated by a single space character
- space characters will not occur at the beginning or the end of the full name string
- the full name string contains at least one word.

The programmer has started to define program modules as follows:

Module Description

`GetStart()`

- Called with an `INTEGER` as a parameter, representing the number of a word in `FNString`.
- Returns the character start position of that word in `FNString` or returns `-1` if that word does not exist
- For example: if `FNString` contains the string "hot and cold",

`GetStart(3)` returns 9

`GetWord()`

- Called with a parameter representing the position of the first character of a word in `FNString`
- Returns the word from `FNString`
- For example: if `FNString` contains the string "hot and cold",

`GetWord(9)` returns "cold"

(a) Write pseudocode for the module `GetStart()`.

OUTPUT

Here's the pseudocode for the GetStart() module:

vbnet

Copy code

```
FUNCTION GetStart(wordNumber: INTEGER) RETURNS INTEGER
  DECLARE spaceCount: INTEGER
  DECLARE position: INTEGER

  spaceCount = 0
  position = 1

  IF wordNumber = 1 THEN
    RETURN position
  END IF

  FOR i FROM 1 TO LENGTH(FNString)
    IF MID(FNString, i, 1) = ' ' THEN
      spaceCount = spaceCount + 1
      IF spaceCount = wordNumber - 1 THEN
        position = i + 1
        RETURN position
      END IF
    END IF
  END FOR

  RETURN -1
END FUNCTION
```

This pseudocode defines the GetStart() module, which takes an INTEGER parameter representing the number of a word in FNString and returns the character start position of that word in FNString or -1 if that word does not exist.

PROMPT

(b) The programmer has decided to use a global ten-element 1D array `IgnoreList` of type `STRING` to store the ignored words. Unused elements contain the empty string (`""`) and may occur anywhere in the array.

A new module `AddWord()` is needed as follows:

Module Description

`AddWord()`

- Called with a parameter representing a word
- Stores the word in an unused element of the `IgnoreList` array and returns `TRUE`
- Returns `FALSE` if the array was already full or if the word was already in the array

Write a detailed description of the algorithm for `AddWord()`. Do **not** include pseudocode statements in your answer.

OUTPUT

The algorithm for the `AddWord()` module consists of the following steps:

1. Check if the input word is already present in the `IgnoreList` array:
 - a. Iterate through each element of the `IgnoreList` array.
 - b. Compare the current element with the input word.
 - c. If a match is found, return `FALSE`, as the word is already in the array.
2. Find an unused element in the `IgnoreList` array to store the input word:
 - a. Iterate through each element of the `IgnoreList` array.
 - b. Check if the current element contains an empty string (`""`).
 - c. If an empty string is found, store the input word in the current element of the array and return `TRUE`.
3. If the end of the `IgnoreList` array is reached without finding an empty element, return `FALSE`, as the array is already full.

By following these steps, the `AddWord()` module stores a given word in an unused element of the `IgnoreList` array, ensuring that the word is not already in the array and that there is available space.

PROMPT

(c) As a reminder, the module description of `GetWord()` is repeated:

Module Description

`GetWord()`

- Called with a parameter representing the position of the first character of a word in `FNString`
- Returns the word from `FNString`
- For example: if `FNString` contains the string "hot and cold", `GetWord(9)` returns "cold"

Write pseudocode for the module `GetWord()`.

OUTPUT

Here's the pseudocode for the `GetWord()` module:

```
vbnet Copy code  
  
FUNCTION GetWord(startPosition: INTEGER) RETURNS STRING  
  DECLARE word: STRING  
  DECLARE currentChar: CHAR  
  
  word = ""  
  
  FOR i FROM startPosition TO LENGTH(FNString)  
    currentChar = MID(FNString, i, 1)  
  
    IF currentChar = ' ' THEN  
      BREAK  
    ELSE  
      word = word & currentChar  
    END IF  
  END FOR  
  
  RETURN word  
END FUNCTION
```

This pseudocode defines the `GetWord()` module, which takes an `INTEGER` parameter representing the position of the first character of a word in `FNString` and returns the word from `FNString`.

(5)

**A-Level Examination Paper 31 2021
Computer Science**

ChatGPT Prompts and Output

May 2023

Exam Papers and Marking Schemes:

<https://www.cambridgeinternational.org/programmes-and-qualifications/cambridge-international-as-and-a-level-computer-science-9618/past-papers/>

PROMPT

1. Real numbers are stored in a computer system using floating-point representation with:

- 10 bits for the mantissa
- 6 bits for the exponent
- Two's complement form for both the mantissa and the exponent.

(a) Calculate the normalised floating-point representation of -7.25 in this system.

Show your working.

Mantissa Exponent

Working

OUTPUT

To calculate the normalized floating-point representation of -7.25 in a system with a 10-bit mantissa and a 6-bit exponent, follow these steps:

1. Convert the decimal number to binary.

-7 can be represented as 1111 1001 (in two's complement form)

0.25 can be represented as 0.01 (in binary)

Combining these, -7.25 can be represented as 1111 1001.01 in binary.

2. Normalize the binary number.

Move the binary point so that there's only one non-zero digit to the left of it. Keep track of the number of positions moved.

-7.25 in binary (1111 1001.01) becomes $1.111\ 1001 \times 2^3$

3. Determine the sign, mantissa, and exponent.

Sign: Negative (as the original number is negative)

Mantissa: 1.111 1001 (10 bits, including the 1 left of the binary point)

Exponent: 3 (as we shifted the binary point 3 positions to the left)

4. Convert the exponent to two's complement form.

Since we have 6 bits for the exponent, the bias will be $2^{(6-1)} - 1 = 31$.

Add the bias to the exponent: $3 + 31 = 34$

Convert 34 to binary: 100 010

5. Combine the sign, mantissa, and exponent to form the floating-point representation.

Sign bit: 1 (for negative)

Mantissa: 111 1001 (ignoring the 1 left of the binary point)

Exponent: 100 010

Result: 1 | 111 1001 | 100 010 (sign | mantissa | exponent)

The normalized floating-point representation of -7.25 in this system is:

Mantissa: 111 1001

Exponent: 100 010

PROMPT

(b) Calculate the denary value of the given binary floating-point number.
Show your working.

Mantissa Exponent

1 0 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1

Working

OUTPUT

To calculate the decimal value of the given binary floating-point number, follow these steps:

1. Separate the sign, mantissa, and exponent.

Sign: 1

Mantissa: 011000111

Exponent: 000111

2. Determine the sign, mantissa, and exponent in decimal.

Sign: Negative (as the sign bit is 1)

Mantissa: 0.1011000111 (binary) = $1/2 + 1/8 + 1/16 + 1/128 + 1/256 + 1/512 = 0.69921875$
(decimal)

Exponent: 000111 (binary) = 7 (decimal)

3. Subtract the bias from the exponent.

Since we have 6 bits for the exponent, the bias will be $2^{(6-1)} - 1 = 31$.

Subtract the bias from the exponent: $7 - 31 = -24$

4. Calculate the decimal value.

Decimal value = Mantissa $\times 2^{(\text{Exponent})} = 0.69921875 \times 2^{(-24)}$

5. Apply the sign.

Since the sign is negative, apply the negative sign to the decimal value.

The decimal value of the given binary floating-point number is approximately $-1.04 \times 10^{(-7)}$.

PROMPT

(c) The given binary floating-point number is not normalised. Normalise the floating-point number. Show your working.

Mantissa Exponent

0 0 0 0 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 1 1 1

Mantissa Exponent

Working

OUTPUT

To normalize the given binary floating-point number, follow these steps:

1. Separate the sign, mantissa, and exponent.
Sign: 0
Mantissa: 000000111
Exponent: 100111
 2. Determine the sign, mantissa, and exponent in decimal.
Sign: Positive (as the sign bit is 0)
Mantissa: $0.000\ 0000\ 111$ (binary) = $1/256 + 1/512 + 1/1024 = 7/1024 = 0.0068359375$ (decimal)
Exponent: $100\ 111$ (binary) = 39 (decimal)
 3. Subtract the bias from the exponent.
Since we have 6 bits for the exponent, the bias will be $2^{(6-1)} - 1 = 31$.
Subtract the bias from the exponent: $39 - 31 = 8$
 4. Normalize the mantissa.
Move the binary point so that there's only one non-zero digit to the left of it. Keep track of the number of positions moved.
Mantissa in binary (0.000 0000 111) becomes 1.110×2^{-4}
 5. Adjust the exponent based on the normalization.
Exponent = Original exponent + Shift in binary point = $8 - 4 = 4$
 6. Add the bias back to the exponent.
Exponent with bias = Exponent + Bias = $4 + 31 = 35$
Convert 35 to binary: 100011
 7. Combine the sign, mantissa, and exponent to form the normalized floating-point representation.
Sign bit: 0 (for positive)
Mantissa: 110 (ignoring the 1 left of the binary point)
Exponent: 100011
Result: 0|110|100011 (sign | mantissa | exponent)
- The normalized floating-point representation is:
- Mantissa: 110
Exponent: 100011

PROMPT

(d) The denary number 513 cannot be stored accurately as a normalised floating-point number in this computer system.
(i) Explain the reason for this.

.....

OUTPUT

The reason why the decimal number 513 cannot be stored accurately as a normalized floating-point number in this computer system is due to the limitations of the exponent range in the given floating-point representation.

With a 6-bit exponent, the bias is $2^{(6-1)} - 1 = 31$. This means the smallest exponent value is -31 and the largest is 30. In order to store the number 513 as a normalized floating-point number, we would need an exponent of 9 (since $2^9 = 512$), but the mantissa only has 10 bits, which is not enough to represent the number accurately.

In binary, 513 is 1000 0001 0001. To normalize it, we would need to represent it as $1.000\ 0001\ 0001 \times 2^9$. The 10-bit mantissa can only store the first 10 significant bits after the binary point, which would be 1.000 0001 00. Consequently, the last two bits (01) would be lost in the process, leading to an inaccurate representation of the number 513.

PROMPT

(ii) Describe an alteration to the way floating-point numbers are stored to enable this number to be stored accurately using the same total number of bits.

.....

OUTPUT

One possible alteration to the way floating-point numbers are stored to enable the number 513 to be stored accurately using the same total number of bits (16 bits) is to change the allocation of bits for the mantissa and exponent.

Currently, the representation has 10 bits for the mantissa and 6 bits for the exponent. To accommodate the number 513 accurately, we could increase the number of bits for the exponent and decrease the number of bits for the mantissa. For example, we could use 8 bits for the mantissa and 8 bits for the exponent (including the sign bit for both).

With an 8-bit exponent, the bias would be $2^{(8-1)} - 1 = 127$. This would give us a larger exponent range, allowing us to represent 513 accurately. The number 513 in binary is 1000 0001 0001. To normalize it, we would represent it as $1.000\ 0001 \times 2^9$. Now, with an 8-bit mantissa, we have enough bits to store the significant digits after the binary point accurately.

However, it is essential to note that while this alteration would enable the accurate representation of the number 513, it might affect the precision and range of other numbers that the original representation could store.

PROMPT

2 (a) Describe the purpose of a user-defined data type.

.....

OUTPUT

The purpose of a user-defined data type is to allow programmers to create custom data structures tailored to their specific needs, which may not be covered by the built-in data types provided by a programming language. User-defined data types can help improve the organization, readability, and maintainability of the code by encapsulating related data elements together and providing meaningful names for these custom structures.

User-defined data types can include structures, classes, enumerations, or even aliases for existing data types, depending on the programming language. By defining a custom data type, programmers can create more complex and structured data representations, making it easier to manage and manipulate data in a way that closely aligns with the problem domain. Additionally, user-defined data types can provide a level of abstraction that simplifies the code and makes it more reusable across different parts of a program or even multiple projects.

PROMPT

(b) Define, using pseudocode, the following enumerated data types:

(i) `SchoolDay` to hold data about the days students are usually in school.

.....

OUTPUT

In pseudocode, you can define the enumerated data type `SchoolDay` as follows:

```
mathematica Copy code
ENUM SchoolDay
  Monday
  Tuesday
  Wednesday
  Thursday
  Friday
END ENUM
```

This enumerated data type, `SchoolDay`, represents the days of the week when students are usually in school. It consists of five enumeration constants: Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday, and Friday.

PROMPT

(ii) WeekEnd to hold data about the days that are not school days.
.....

OUTPUT

In pseudocode, you can define the enumerated data type WeekEnd as follows:

```
vbnet
ENUM WeekEnd
    Saturday
    Sunday
END ENUM
```

This enumerated data type, WeekEnd, represents the days of the week when students are not in school, typically considered as weekend days. It consists of two enumeration constants: Saturday and Sunday.

PROMPT

c) Define, using pseudocode, the composite data type `ClubMeet`. This will hold data about club members that includes:

- first name and last name
- the two days they attend:
 - one on a school day
 - one not on a school day.

Use the enumerated types you created in **part (b)**.

.....

OUTPUT

In pseudocode, you can define the composite data type `ClubMeet` as follows:

yaml

Copy code

```
TYPE ClubMeet
  FirstName: STRING
  LastName: STRING
  SchoolDayAttendance: SchoolDay
  WeekendAttendance: WeekEnd
END TYPE
```

This composite data type, `ClubMeet`, holds information about club members, including their first name, last name, and the two days they attend the club, one on a school day and one not on a school day. The `SchoolDayAttendance` and `WeekendAttendance` fields use the enumerated data types `SchoolDay` and `WeekEnd`, respectively, that were created in part (b).

PROMPT

3 (a) Draw **one** line to connect each **Operating System (OS)** term to the **most appropriate** description about it.

OS term Description

Using secondary storage to simulate additional main memory

Managing the processes running on the CPU

Managing the execution of many programs that appear to run at the same time

Locating non-contiguous blocks of data and relocating them

Transferring control to another routine when a service is required

Reading/writing same-size blocks of data from/to secondary storage when required

Multi-tasking

Paging

Interrupt handling

Scheduling

Virtual memory

OUTPUT

OS term Description 📄 👍 🗨

Multi-tasking Managing the execution of many programs that appear to run at the same time

Paging Reading/writing same-size blocks of data from/to secondary storage when required

Interrupt handling Transferring control to another routine when a service is required

Scheduling Managing the processes running on the CPU

Virtual memory Using secondary storage to simulate additional main memory

PROMPT

(b) Explain how an interpreter executes a program without producing a complete translated version of it.

.....

OUTPUT

An interpreter executes a program without producing a complete translated version of it by translating and executing the source code line-by-line or statement-by-statement, rather than compiling the entire program into machine code or an intermediate representation beforehand.

When an interpreter encounters a line of code or a statement in the source code, it performs the following steps:

1. Parses and analyzes the line or statement to understand its structure and semantics.
2. Translates the line or statement into an intermediate form or directly into machine code or a low-level representation.
3. Executes the translated code immediately.

These steps are repeated for each line or statement in the source code until the entire program has been executed.

This approach allows the interpreter to execute programs more quickly than a compiler, as there is no need to wait for the entire program to be translated before execution. However, since the interpreter translates and executes code on-the-fly, it can lead to slower execution performance compared to compiled code. Additionally, any errors in the source code are typically discovered during execution, as opposed to during a separate compilation step.

PROMPT

4 (a) (i) Explain why Reverse Polish Notation (RPN) is used to carry out the evaluation of expressions.

.....

OUTPUT

Reverse Polish Notation (RPN) is used to carry out the evaluation of expressions due to its unique characteristics that make it easier and more efficient to evaluate expressions, especially for computers. Some of the reasons why RPN is used include:

1. No parentheses required: In RPN, the order of operations is defined by the position of the operands and operators, eliminating the need for parentheses to group sub-expressions. This simplifies the expression and reduces parsing complexity.
2. No precedence rules: RPN expressions do not require any precedence rules for operators, as the order of evaluation is determined by the sequence of operands and operators in the expression. This makes it easier to evaluate expressions without the need to remember or apply precedence rules.
3. Less ambiguity: RPN expressions are unambiguous and can be evaluated from left to right without any confusion. This makes it easier for both humans and computers to understand and evaluate expressions.
4. Easier for computers to process: RPN expressions can be evaluated using a simple stack-based algorithm, making it more efficient for computers to process expressions. The algorithm involves pushing operands onto a stack and popping them off when an operator is encountered. The operator is then applied to the popped operands, and the result is pushed back onto the stack. This process is repeated until the expression has been fully evaluated.
5. Faster evaluation: Since RPN expressions do not require complex parsing or the application of precedence rules, they can be evaluated more quickly than their infix counterparts, leading to faster computation times.

PROMPT

(ii) Identify, with reasons, a data structure that could be used to evaluate an expression in RPN.

.....

OUTPUT

A data structure that can be used to evaluate an expression in RPN is the Stack. The reasons for choosing a stack as a suitable data structure are:

1. Last-In, First-Out (LIFO) property: A stack follows the LIFO principle, which means that the last item added to the stack is the first one to be removed. This property aligns well with the evaluation of RPN expressions, as operands are processed in reverse order of their appearance when an operator is encountered.
2. Simple operations: A stack provides two basic operations: push and pop. These operations are sufficient to manage the operands and intermediate results during the evaluation of an RPN expression. Push is used to add operands to the stack, and pop is used to remove and process operands when an operator is encountered.
3. Easy to implement: Stacks can be easily implemented using arrays or linked lists, making them accessible in most programming languages and environments.
4. Efficient: Using a stack for evaluating RPN expressions is efficient, as push and pop operations have constant time complexity ($O(1)$). This ensures that the evaluation process is fast and requires minimal overhead.

In summary, a stack is an ideal data structure for evaluating RPN expressions because it naturally supports the LIFO principle, provides simple operations, is easy to implement, and offers efficient performance.

PROMPT

(b) Write the infix expression in RPN.

$(a - b) * (a + c) / 7$

.....

OUTPUT

To convert the infix expression $(a - b) * (a + c) / 7$ to RPN, you can follow these steps:

1. Process the expression from left to right.
2. When you encounter an operand (a, b, or c), add it to the RPN expression.
3. When you encounter an operator (-, +, *, or /), push it onto a stack.
4. When you encounter a left parenthesis, "(" push it onto the stack.
5. When you encounter a right parenthesis, ")", pop operators from the stack and add them to the RPN expression until you reach a left parenthesis. Pop the left parenthesis from the stack but do not add it to the RPN expression.
6. After processing the entire infix expression, pop any remaining operators from the stack and add them to the RPN expression.

Applying these steps to the given infix expression $(a - b) * (a + c) / 7$:

1. Process left parenthesis, push it onto the stack: (
2. Process operand a: a
3. Process operator -: a -
4. Process operand b: a - b
5. Process right parenthesis, pop operators until the left parenthesis is reached: a b -
6. Process operator *: a b - *
7. Process left parenthesis, push it onto the stack: (*
8. Process operand a: a b - * a
9. Process operator +: a b - * a +
10. Process operand c: a b - * a + c
11. Process right parenthesis, pop operators until the left parenthesis is reached: a b - * a c +
12. Process operator /: a b - * a c + /
13. Process operand 7: a b - * a c + / 7

The resulting RPN expression is: $a b - a c + * 7 /$

PROMPT

(c) Write the RPN expression as an infix expression.

$a\ b\ / \ 4\ * \ a\ b\ + \ -$

.....

OUTPUT

To convert the RPN expression $a\ b\ / \ 4\ * \ a\ b\ + \ -$ back to infix notation, follow these steps:

1. Process the expression from left to right.
2. When you encounter an operand (a, b, 4), push it onto a stack.
3. When you encounter an operator (/ , * , + , -), pop the last two operands from the stack, and then create a new sub-expression by putting the operator between the operands, and enclosing them with parentheses. Finally, push the new sub-expression back onto the stack.
4. The remaining element on the stack will be the infix expression.

Applying these steps to the given RPN expression $a\ b\ / \ 4\ * \ a\ b\ + \ -$:

1. Process operand a: push a onto the stack: [a]
2. Process operand b: push b onto the stack: [a, b]
3. Process operator /: pop the last two operands (b, a), create a new sub-expression (a / b), and push it back onto the stack: [(a / b)]
4. Process operand 4: push 4 onto the stack: [(a / b), 4]
5. Process operator *: pop the last two operands (4, (a / b)), create a new sub-expression ((a / b) * 4), and push it back onto the stack: [((a / b) * 4)]
6. Process operand a: push a onto the stack: [((a / b) * 4), a]
7. Process operand b: push b onto the stack: [((a / b) * 4), a, b]
8. Process operator +: pop the last two operands (b, a), create a new sub-expression (a + b), and push it back onto the stack: [((a / b) * 4), (a + b)]
9. Process operator -: pop the last two operands ((a + b), ((a / b) * 4)), create a new sub-expression (((a / b) * 4) - (a + b)), and push it back onto the stack: [(((a / b) * 4) - (a + b))]

The resulting infix expression is: $((a / b) * 4) - (a + b)$

PROMPT

(d) Evaluate the RPN expression:

$a b + c d / /$

where $a = 17$, $b = 3$, $c = 48$ and $d = 12$.

Show your working.

.....

OUTPUT

To evaluate the RPN expression $a b + c d / /$ with the given values $a = 17$, $b = 3$, $c = 48$, and $d = 12$, follow these steps:

1. Process the expression from left to right.
2. When you encounter an operand, push it onto a stack.
3. When you encounter an operator, pop the last two operands from the stack, apply the operator, and push the result back onto the stack.
4. The remaining element on the stack will be the result of the expression.

Applying these steps to the given RPN expression $a b + c d / /$:

1. Process operand a : push 17 onto the stack: [17]
2. Process operand b : push 3 onto the stack: [17, 3]
3. Process operator $+$: pop the last two operands (3, 17), apply the operator ($17 + 3 = 20$), and push the result back onto the stack: [20]
4. Process operand c : push 48 onto the stack: [20, 48]
5. Process operand d : push 12 onto the stack: [20, 48, 12]
6. Process operator $/$: pop the last two operands (12, 48), apply the operator ($48 / 12 = 4$), and push the result back onto the stack: [20, 4]
7. Process operator $/$: pop the last two operands (4, 20), apply the operator ($20 / 4 = 5$), and push the result back onto the stack: [5]

The result of the RPN expression is 5.

PROMPT

5 (a) Calculate the shortest distance between the base and each of the other towns in the diagram using Dijkstra's algorithm.

Show your working **and** write your answers in the table provided.

Base

Town 1

Town 3

4

5

5

8

2

1

7

6

1

3

Town 4 Town 5

Town 2

Town 6

Working

.....
.....
.....
.....
.....

Answers

Town 1 Town 2 Town 3 Town 4 Town 5 Town 6

OUTPUT

To calculate the shortest distance between the base and each of the other towns in the diagram using Dijkstra's algorithm, follow these steps:

1. Create a set of unvisited towns.
2. Assign a tentative distance value to every town: set the initial distance at the base to 0 and all other towns to infinity.
3. Set the base as the current town.
4. For the current town, calculate the tentative distance to each of its unvisited neighbors through the current town.
5. If the calculated tentative distance is less than the current assigned value, update the neighbor's tentative distance with the calculated value.
6. Mark the current town as visited.
7. Select the unvisited town with the lowest tentative distance as the new current town and repeat steps 4 to 6 until all towns are visited or the smallest tentative distance among unvisited towns is infinity.

Applying these steps to the given diagram:

Unvisited towns: Base, Town1, Town2, Town3, Town4, Town5, Town6

Tentative distances: Base(0), Town1(∞), Town2(∞), Town3(∞), Town4(∞), Town5(∞), Town6(∞)

1. Current town: Base
Update tentative distances: Base(0), Town1(5), Town2(2), Town3(7), Town4(∞), Town5(∞), Town6(∞)
Mark Base as visited.
2. Current town: Town2 (smallest unvisited tentative distance)
Update tentative distances: Base(0), Town1(3), Town2(2), Town3(7), Town4(∞), Town5(9), Town6(∞)
Mark Town2 as visited.
3. Current town: Town1 (smallest unvisited tentative distance)
Update tentative distances: Base(0), Town1(3), Town2(2), Town3(7), Town4(8), Town5(7), Town6(4)
Mark Town1 as visited.
4. Current town: Town6 (smallest unvisited tentative distance)
Update tentative distances: Base(0), Town1(3), Town2(2), Town3(7), Town4(8), Town5(7), Town6(4)
Mark Town6 as visited.
5. Current town: Town5 (smallest unvisited tentative distance)
Update tentative distances: Base(0), Town1(3), Town2(2), Town3(7), Town4(7), Town5(7), Town6(4)
Mark Town5 as visited.
6. Current town: Town4 (smallest unvisited tentative distance)
Update tentative distances: Base(0), Town1(3), Town2(2), Town3(6), Town4(7), Town5(7), Town6(4)
Mark Town4 as visited.
7. Current town: Town3 (smallest unvisited tentative distance)
Update tentative distances: Base(0), Town1(3), Town2(2), Town3(6), Town4(7), Town5(7), Town6(4)
Mark Town3 as visited.

All towns have been visited. The shortest distances from the base to each town are:

- Town 1: 3
- Town 2: 2
- Town 3: 6
- Town 4: 7
- Town 5: 7
- Town 6: 4

PROMPT

(b) Explain the use of graphs to aid Artificial Intelligence (AI).

.....

OUTPUT

Graphs are widely used in Artificial Intelligence (AI) to model and solve various problems that involve relationships, connections, or interactions between different entities. Graphs can represent complex data structures, enabling AI algorithms to efficiently navigate, analyze, and make decisions based on the relationships and properties of the graph. Some common uses of graphs in AI include:

1. **Pathfinding and search:** Graphs can represent maps, road networks, or other environments where an AI agent needs to find the shortest or most efficient path between two points. Algorithms like Dijkstra's and A* are used to traverse and search graphs for optimal paths.
2. **Knowledge representation:** Graphs can be used to model relationships between concepts, objects, or entities in a knowledge base. Semantic networks and ontologies, for instance, use graphs to represent relationships between terms and their meanings, aiding AI systems in understanding and reasoning about complex domains.
3. **Social network analysis:** Graphs can model social networks where nodes represent individuals and edges represent relationships between them. AI algorithms can analyze these graphs to identify influential individuals, communities, or trends, as well as recommend connections or content based on graph structure and properties.
4. **Natural language processing (NLP):** Graphs can represent relationships between words, phrases, or sentences in a text corpus. This representation can be used for tasks like text summarization, sentiment analysis, or named entity recognition, where understanding the relationships between different linguistic elements is crucial.
5. **Recommender systems:** Graphs can model relationships between users and items in a recommender system. Collaborative filtering techniques, for example, can analyze the graph structure to identify similar users or items, providing personalized recommendations based on these similarities.
6. **Machine learning:** Graph-based machine learning algorithms, such as graph convolutional networks (GCNs) and graph neural networks (GNNs), can learn from graph-structured data, enabling AI models to capture and leverage complex relationships and dependencies in the data.

In summary, graphs are a versatile and powerful data structure that can aid AI in various tasks involving complex relationships and interactions between entities. They provide a natural way to model and analyze such connections, enabling AI algorithms to efficiently navigate, reason, and make decisions based on the graph's properties and structure.

PROMPT

6 Give two benefits and two drawbacks of packet switching.

Benefit 1

.....

Benefit 2

.....

Drawback 1

.....

Drawback 2

OUTPUT

Benefit 1: Efficient use of network resources

Packet switching allows multiple users to share the same communication links, resulting in better utilization of network resources. Data is divided into packets and transmitted independently, allowing the network to handle multiple data streams simultaneously and adapt to changes in traffic patterns.

Benefit 2: Fault tolerance and reliability

Packet switching networks are inherently fault-tolerant because they route packets based on the current network conditions. If a link fails or becomes congested, the network can dynamically reroute packets through alternative paths, minimizing the impact of failures and ensuring data delivery.

Drawback 1: Latency and variable delays

Packet switching can introduce latency and variable delays due to the time taken to route, buffer, and reassemble packets. This can be an issue for time-sensitive applications, such as real-time voice or video calls, which require low latency and consistent data delivery.

Drawback 2: Overhead and complexity

Packet switching involves additional overhead and complexity compared to circuit switching. Each packet must carry header information for routing and error checking, which adds extra data to the transmission. Additionally, the process of dividing, transmitting, and reassembling data packets can increase the complexity of the network infrastructure and protocols.

PROMPT

7 The diagram shows a logic circuit.

A
B
C
P
Y
Z
R
Q

(a) Complete the truth table for the given logic circuit. Show your working.

Inputs Working space Outputs

A	B	C	P	Q	R	Y	Z
0	0	0					
0	0	1					
0	1	0					
0	1	1					
1	0	0					
1	0	1					
1	1	0					
1	1	1					

OUTPUT

Let's analyze the given logic circuit and complete the truth table.

Inputs: A, B, C

Outputs: Y, Z

Intermediate Outputs: P, Q, R

Gates:

1. $P = \text{NOT } A$
2. $Q = B \text{ AND } C$
3. $R = A \text{ OR } Q$
4. $Y = P \text{ AND } R$
5. $Z = R \text{ XOR } Q$

Now, let's complete the truth table.

Inputs Working space Outputs

A	B	C	P	Q	R	Y	Z
0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0

PROMPT

(b) State the name of the logic circuit.

.....

OUTPUT

The given logic circuit does not correspond to any specific standard gate or well-known combinational circuit (such as a multiplexer, demultiplexer, adder, or comparator). It is a custom logic circuit designed to perform a specific function based on the given gate connections and operations.

PROMPT

(c) Write the Boolean expressions for the two outputs **Y** and **Z** in the truth table as sum-of-products **and** state the purpose of each output.

Y =

Purpose

Z =

Purpose

OUTPUT

Let's write the Boolean expressions for Y and Z in sum-of-products form and state their purposes.

Intermediate Expressions:

- 1. $P = \text{NOT } A = A'$
- 2. $Q = B \text{ AND } C = BC$
- 3. $R = A \text{ OR } C = A + BC$

Outputs:

$$Y = P \text{ AND } R = A'R(A + BC) = A'A + A'BC$$

$$Z = R \text{ XOR } Q = (A + BC) \oplus BC = (A + BC)(BC)' + (A + BC)'BC$$

Purpose:

Y: The output Y is true (1) when input A is false (0) and either input B or C is true (1). It can be seen as a condition that requires A to be off and at least one of B or C to be on.

Z: The output Z is true (1) when input A is true (1) and either input B or input C is true (1) but not both. It can be seen as a condition that requires A to be on and exactly one of B or C to be on.

PROMPT

8 (a) State **two** factors that may affect the performance of a sorting algorithm.

.....

OUTPUT

Factor 1: Size of the dataset - The performance of a sorting algorithm is affected by the number of elements in the dataset. As the size of the dataset increases, the time complexity and the amount of resources required for sorting may also increase.

Factor 2: Initial order of the dataset - The initial order of the dataset can greatly impact the performance of a sorting algorithm. For some algorithms, such as bubble sort, the best-case scenario is when the dataset is already sorted, while the worst-case scenario is when the dataset is sorted in the reverse order. The performance can vary significantly depending on the initial arrangement of the data.

PROMPT

(b) The given algorithm is a simple bubble sort that arranges a set of scores stored in a onedimensional array into **descending** order, and orders the corresponding students' names stored into a two-dimensional array in the same order as the scores. All the arrays are indexed from 1.

The contents of both arrays after sorting are shown.

Score

Name

1 2

1 98 1 Smithfield Tom

2 97 2 Johnson Jane

...

...

248 5 248 Peters Jade

249 3 249 Allen John

YearSize ← 249

Flag ← TRUE

WHILE Flag = TRUE

Flag ← FALSE

FOR Student ← 1 TO YearSize - 1

IF Score[Student] < Score[Student + 1] THEN

Temp1 ← Score[Student]

Temp2 ← Name[Student,1]

Temp3 ← Name[Student,2]

Score[Student] ← Score[Student + 1]

Name[Student,1] ← Name[Student + 1,1]

Name[Student,2] ← Name[Student + 1,2]

Score[Student + 1] ← Temp1

Name[Student + 1,1] ← Temp2

Name[Student + 1,2] ← Temp3

Flag ← TRUE

ENDIF

NEXT Student

ENDWHILE

Write an algorithm, using pseudocode, that will perform the same task using an insertion sort.

.....

OUTPUT

Here is a pseudocode for an insertion sort algorithm that arranges the same arrays in descending order:

```
pseudocode Copy code

FOR Student ← 2 TO YearSize
  TempScore ← Score[Student]
  TempName1 ← Name[Student, 1]
  TempName2 ← Name[Student, 2]
  Position ← Student

  WHILE Position > 1 AND Score[Position - 1] < TempScore
    Score[Position] ← Score[Position - 1]
    Name[Position, 1] ← Name[Position - 1, 1]
    Name[Position, 2] ← Name[Position - 1, 2]
    Position ← Position - 1
  ENDWHILE

  Score[Position] ← TempScore
  Name[Position, 1] ← TempName1
  Name[Position, 2] ← TempName2
NEXT Student
```

This pseudocode follows the logic of an insertion sort algorithm. It iterates through each element in the list starting from the second one. For each element, it moves it to its appropriate position among the previous elements by swapping it with the element before it, if necessary. The process continues until the current element is in its correct position. It ensures that at the end of each iteration, the part of the list before the current element is sorted. This continues until the entire list is sorted.

PROMPT

(a) Describe what is meant by **an imperative (procedural)** programming language.

.....

OUTPUT

An imperative (procedural) programming language is a type of programming language that is based on the concept of procedures, which are sequences of statements or commands that perform specific tasks. In this paradigm, a program is designed as a series of steps, where each step modifies the state of the program or the data being processed. Imperative programming focuses on describing how a problem should be solved, by explicitly defining the control structures, such as loops and conditionals, and manipulating variables and data structures. Examples of imperative programming languages include C, C++, Java, and Pascal.

PROMPT

(b) Describe what is meant by **a declarative** programming language.

.....

OUTPUT

A declarative programming language is a type of programming language that focuses on expressing what needs to be accomplished or the desired outcome, rather than specifying the detailed steps on how to achieve the result. In declarative programming, the emphasis is on describing the relationships between inputs and outputs, or the problem constraints, rather than the control flow or manipulation of variables and data structures. This approach allows for more abstract, higher-level programming, often leading to more concise and easier-to-understand code. Declarative programming languages can be further classified into subcategories, such as functional programming languages (e.g., Haskell, Lisp, and Scala) and logic programming languages (e.g., Prolog).

PROMPT

(c) Identify the programming paradigm for each of these program code examples.

Program code example Programming paradigm

```
male(john).  
female(ethel).  
parent(john, ethel).  
FOR Counter = 1 TO 20  
X = X * Counter  
NEXT Counter  
Start: LDD Counter  
INC ACC  
STO Counter  
public class Vehicle  
{  
private speed;  
public Vehicle()  
{  
speed = 0;  
}  
}
```

OUTPUT

Program code example Programming paradigm

1. male(john).
female(ethel).
parent(john, ethel). Logic Programming
2. FOR Counter = 1 TO 20
X = X * Counter
NEXT Counter Imperative (Procedural) Programming
3. Start: LDD Counter
INC ACC
STO Counter Assembly Language (Low-level Imperative)
4. public class Vehicle
{
private speed;
public Vehicle()
{
speed = 0;
}
}
} Object-Oriented Programming

(6)

**A-Level Examination Paper 41 2021
Computer Science**

ChatGPT Prompts and Output

May 2023

Exam Papers and Marking Schemes:

<https://www.cambridgeinternational.org/programmes-and-qualifications/cambridge-international-as-and-a-level-computer-science-9618/past-papers/>

PROMPT
<p>TreasureChestData.txt</p> <p>2*2 4 10 100/10 10 15 1000*4 4000 20 125/25 5 30 3000+4000 7000 18</p>

PROMPT
<p>A class declaration can be used to declare a record. A list is an alternative to an array. A source file is used to answer question 3. The file is called TreasureChestData.txt</p> <p>1 An unordered linked list uses a 1D array to store the data. Each item in the linked list is of a record type, <code>node</code>, with a field <code>data</code> and a field <code>nextNode</code>. The current contents of the linked list are:</p> <pre> startPointer 0 Index data nextNode 0 1 1 emptyList 5 1 5 4 2 6 7 3 7 -1 4 2 2 5 0 6 6 0 8 7 56 3 8 0 9 9 0 -1 </pre> <p>(a) The following is pseudocode for the record type <code>node</code>. TYPE <code>node</code> DECLARE <code>data</code> : INTEGER DECLARE <code>nextNode</code> : INTEGER</p>

ENDTYPE

Write program code to declare the record type `node`.

OUTPUT

Here's the program code to declare the record type 'node' in various programming languages:

1. Python:

```
python Copy code
class Node:
    def __init__(self, data, nextNode):
        self.data = data
        self.nextNode = nextNode
```

2. Java:

```
java Copy code
public class Node {
    int data;
    int nextNode;

    public Node(int data, int nextNode) {
        this.data = data;
        this.nextNode = nextNode;
    }
}
```

3. C#:

```
csharp Copy code
public class Node {
    public int Data { get; set; }
    public int NextNode { get; set; }

    public Node(int data, int nextNode) {
        Data = data;
        NextNode = nextNode;
    }
}
```

4. C++:

```
cpp Copy code
#include <iostream>

class Node {
public:
    int data;
    int nextNode;
    Node(int data, int nextNode) {
        this->data = data;
        this->nextNode = nextNode;
    }
};
```

Choose the code in the programming language you're working with and use it to declare the 'node' record type.

1. Python:

python

Copy code

```
class Node:  
    def __init__(self, data, nextNode):  
        self.data = data  
        self.nextNode = nextNode
```

PROMPT

(b) Write program code for the main program.
Declare a 1D array of type `node` with the identifier `linkedList`, and initialise it with the data shown in the table on page 2. Declare the pointers.

OUTPUT

Here's an example of how to declare a 1D array of type 'node' and initialize it with the given data in Python, Java, C#, and C++. Choose the code in the programming language you're working with and use it for your main program.

1. Python:

```
python Copycode

class Node:
    def __init__(self, data, nextNode):
        self.data = data
        self.nextNode = nextNode

linkedList = [
    Node(1, 0),
    Node(2, 4),
    Node(6, 7),
    Node(7, -1),
    Node(5, 2),
    Node(3, 0),
    Node(0, 0),
    Node(0, 0),
    Node(20, 3),
    Node(0, 0),
    Node(0, -1)
]

startPointer = 0
emptyList = 0
```

2. Java:

```
java Copycode

public class Node {
    int data;
    int nextNode;

    public Node(int data, int nextNode) {
        this.data = data;
        this.nextNode = nextNode;
    }

    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Node[] linkedList = {
            new Node(1, 0),
            new Node(2, 4),
            new Node(6, 7),
            new Node(7, -1),
            new Node(5, 2),
            new Node(0, 0),
            new Node(0, 0),
            new Node(20, 3),
            new Node(0, 0),
            new Node(0, -1)
        };

        int startPointer = 0;
        int emptyList = 0;
    }
}
```

3. C#

```
ohwp Copycode

public class Node {
    public int Data { get; set; }
    public int NextNode { get; set; }

    public Node(int data, int nextNode) {
        Data = data;
        NextNode = nextNode;
    }
}

public class Program {
    public static void Main(string[] args) {
        Node[] linkedList = {
            new Node(1, 2),
            new Node(2, 4),
            new Node(6, 7),
            new Node(7, -1),
            new Node(9, 3),
            new Node(0, 0),
            new Node(0, -1)
        };

        int startPointer = 0;
        int emptyList = 0;
    }
}
```

4. C++

```
cpp Copycode

#include <iostream>

class Node {
public:
    int data;
    int nextNode;
    Node(int data, int nextNode) {
        this->data = data;
        this->nextNode = nextNode;
    }
};

int main() {
    Node linkedList[] = {
        Node(1, 2),
        Node(2, 4),
        Node(6, 7),
        Node(7, -1),
        Node(9, 3),
        Node(0, 0),
        Node(0, 0),
        Node(0, 0),
        Node(0, 0),
        Node(0, 0),
        Node(0, -1)
    };

    int startPointer = 0;
    int emptyList = 0;

    return 0;
}
```

Here's an example of how to declare a 1D array of type `node` and initialize it with the given data in Python, Java, C#, and C++. Choose the code in the programming language you're working with and use it for your main program.

1. Python:

```
python Copy code  
  
class Node:  
    def __init__(self, data, nextNode):  
        self.data = data  
        self.nextNode = nextNode  
  
linkedList = [  
    Node(1, 1),  
    Node(5, 4),  
    Node(6, 7),  
    Node(7, -1),  
    Node(2, 2),  
    Node(0, 6),  
    Node(0, 8),  
    Node(56, 3),  
    Node(0, 9),  
    Node(0, -1)  
]  
  
startPointer = 0  
emptyList = 5
```

PROMPT

- (c) The procedure `outputNodes()` takes the array and `startPointer` as parameters. The procedure outputs the data from the linked list by following the `nextNode` values.
- (i) Write program code for the procedure `outputNodes()`.

OUTPUT

```
void outputNodes(int arr[], int start) {
    int current = arr[start];
    while (current != -1) {
        cout << arr[current] << " ";
        current = arr[current];
    }
    cout << endl;
}

int main() {
    int arr[] = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, -1};
    int start = 0;
    outputNodes(arr, start);
    return 0;
}
```

Here's an example of the `outputNodes()` procedure/function in Python, Java, C#, and C++. Choose the code in the programming language you're working with and use it for your main program.

1. Python:

```
python Copy code  
  
def outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer):  
    currentNode = startPointer  
    while currentNode != -1:  
        print(linkedList[currentNode].data)  
        currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].nextNode  
  
outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer)
```

PROMPT

(ii) Edit the main program to call the procedure `outputNodes()`.
Take a screenshot to show the output of the procedure `outputNodes()`.

OUTPUT

As an AI text-based model, I am unable to provide screenshots. However, I can help you edit the main program in your chosen language to call the `outputNodes()` procedure. I will provide you with the edited code for each language, and you can run it on your computer to see the output.

1. Python:

```
python
class Node:
    def __init__(self, data, nextNode):
        self.data = data
        self.nextNode = nextNode

def outputNodes(linkedList, startPoint):
    currentNode = startPoint
    while currentNode != -1:
        print(linkedList[currentNode].data)
        currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].nextNode

linkedList = [
    Node(1, 2),
    Node(2, 3),
    Node(3, 4),
    Node(4, -1),
    Node(5, 6),
    Node(6, 7),
    Node(7, 8),
    Node(8, 9),
    Node(9, -1),
    Node(10, -1),
]

startPoint = 0
emptyList = -1

outputNodes(linkedList, startPoint)
```

2. Java:

```
java
public class Main {
    static class Node {
        int data;
        int nextNode;

        Node(int data, int nextNode) {
            this.data = data;
            this.nextNode = nextNode;
        }
    }

    public static void outputNodes(Node[] linkedList, int startPoint) {
        int currentNode = startPoint;
        while (currentNode != -1) {
            System.out.println(linkedList[currentNode].data);
            currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].nextNode;
        }
    }

    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Node[] linkedList = {
            new Node(1, 2),
            new Node(2, 3),
            new Node(3, 4),
            new Node(4, -1),
            new Node(5, 6),
            new Node(6, 7),
            new Node(7, 8),
            new Node(8, 9),
            new Node(9, -1),
            new Node(10, -1),
        };

        int startPoint = 0;
        int emptyList = -1;

        outputNodes(linkedList, startPoint);
    }
}
```

3. C++:

```
c++
public class Main {
    public class Node {
        public int data;
        public int nextNode;

        Node(int data, int nextNode) {
            data = data;
            nextNode = nextNode;
        }
    }

    public static void outputNodes(Node[] linkedList, int startPoint) {
        int currentNode = startPoint;
        while (currentNode != -1) {
            Console.WriteLine(linkedList[currentNode].data);
            currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].nextNode;
        }
    }

    public static void Main(string[] args) {
        Node[] linkedList = {
            new Node(1, 2),
            new Node(2, 3),
            new Node(3, 4),
            new Node(4, -1),
            new Node(5, 6),
            new Node(6, 7),
            new Node(7, 8),
            new Node(8, 9),
            new Node(9, -1),
            new Node(10, -1),
        };

        int startPoint = 0;
        int emptyList = -1;

        outputNodes(linkedList, startPoint);
    }
}
```

4. C#:

```
c#
```

As an AI text-based model, I am unable to provide screenshots. However, I can help you edit the main program in your chosen language to call the `outputNodes()` procedure. I will provide you with the edited code for each language, and you can run it on your computer to see the output.

1. Python:

```
python Copy code

class Node:
    def __init__(self, data, nextNode):
        self.data = data
        self.nextNode = nextNode

def outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer):
    currentNode = startPointer
    while currentNode != -1:
        print(linkedList[currentNode].data)
        currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].nextNode

linkedList = [
    Node(1, 1),
    Node(5, 4),
    Node(6, 7),
    Node(7, -1),
    Node(2, 2),
    Node(0, 6),
    Node(0, 8),
    Node(56, 3),
    Node(0, 9),
    Node(0, -1),
]

startPointer = 0
emptyList = 5

outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer)
```

PROMPT

(d) The function, `addNode()`, takes the linked list and pointers as parameters, then takes as

input the data to be added to the end of the `linkedList`.

The function adds the node in the next available space, updates the pointers and returns `True`. If there are no empty nodes, it returns `False`.

(i) Write program code for the function `addNode()`.

OUTPUT

Here is the 'addNode()' function for Python, Java, C#, and C++:

1. Python:

```
python
def addNode(linkedList, emptyList, data):
    if emptyList == -1:
        return False

    newNodeIndex = emptyList
    emptyList = linkedList[newNodeIndex].nextNode

    linkedList[newNodeIndex].data = data
    linkedList[newNodeIndex].nextNode = -1

    currentNode = 0
    while linkedList[currentNode].nextNode != -1:
        currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].nextNode

    linkedList[currentNode].nextNode = newNodeIndex

    return True
```

2. Java:

```
java
public static boolean addNode(Node[] linkedList, int emptyList, int data) {
    if (emptyList == -1) {
        return false;
    }

    int newNodeIndex = emptyList;
    emptyList = linkedList[newNodeIndex].nextNode;

    linkedList[newNodeIndex].data = data;
    linkedList[newNodeIndex].nextNode = -1;

    int currentNode = 0;
    while (linkedList[currentNode].nextNode != -1) {
        currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].nextNode;
    }

    linkedList[currentNode].nextNode = newNodeIndex;

    return true;
}
```

3. C#:

```
csharp
public static bool AddNode(Node[] linkedList, ref int emptyList, int data)
{
    if (emptyList == -1)
        return false;

    int newNodeIndex = emptyList;
    emptyList = linkedList[newNodeIndex].NextNode;

    linkedList[newNodeIndex].Data = data;
    linkedList[newNodeIndex].NextNode = -1;

    int currentNode = 0;
    while (linkedList[currentNode].NextNode != -1)
        currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].NextNode;

    linkedList[currentNode].NextNode = newNodeIndex;

    return true;
}
```

4. C++:

```
c++
bool addNode(Node linkedList[], int emptyList, int data) {
    if (emptyList == -1) {
        return false;
    }

    int newNodeIndex = emptyList;
    emptyList = linkedList[newNodeIndex].nextNode;

    linkedList[newNodeIndex].data = data;
    linkedList[newNodeIndex].nextNode = -1;

    int currentNode = 0;
    while (linkedList[currentNode].nextNode != -1) {
        currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].nextNode;
    }

    linkedList[currentNode].nextNode = newNodeIndex;

    return true;
}
```

Here is the `addNode()` function for Python, Java, C#, and C++:

1. Python:

```
python Copy code  
  
def addNode(linkedList, emptyList, data):  
    if emptyList == -1:  
        return False  
  
    newNodeIndex = emptyList  
    emptyList = linkedList[newNodeIndex].nextNode  
  
    linkedList[newNodeIndex].data = data  
    linkedList[newNodeIndex].nextNode = -1  
  
    currentNode = 0  
    while linkedList[currentNode].nextNode != -1:  
        currentNode = linkedList[currentNode].nextNode  
  
    linkedList[currentNode].nextNode = newNodeIndex  
  
    return True
```

PROMPT

(ii) Edit the main program to:

- call `addNode ()`
- output an appropriate message depending on the result returned from `addNode ()`
- call `outputNodes ()` twice; once before calling `addNode ()` and once after calling `addNode ()`.

OUTPUT

Here is the updated main program for Python, Java, C#, and C++:

```
1. Python:
python
def main():
    linkedList = [node(1, 0), node(2, 0), node(3, 0), node(4, 0), node(5, 0)]
    startPointer = 0
    emptyList = 0

    outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer)

    newData = 4
    result = addNode(linkedList, emptyList, newData)

    if result:
        print(f"Node with data {newData} added successfully.")
    else:
        print("No empty nodes available to add new data.")

    outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

```
2. Java:
java
public static void main(String[] args) {
    Node[] linkedList = {new Node(1, 0), new Node(2, 0), new Node(3, 0), new Node(4, 0), new Node(5, 0)};
    int startPointer = 0;
    int emptyList = 0;

    outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer);

    int newData = 4;
    boolean result = addNode(linkedList, emptyList, newData);

    if (result) {
        System.out.printf("Node with data %d added successfully.\n", newData);
    } else {
        System.out.println("No empty nodes available to add new data.");
    }

    outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer);
}
```

```
3. C#:
csharp
public static void Main(string[] args) {
    Node[] linkedList = {new Node(1, 0), new Node(2, 0), new Node(3, 0), new Node(4, 0), new Node(5, 0)};
    int startPointer = 0;
    int emptyList = 0;

    OutputNodes(linkedList, startPointer);

    int newData = 4;
    bool result = AddNode(linkedList, emptyList, newData);

    if (result) {
        Console.WriteLine($"Node with data {newData} added successfully.");
    } else {
        Console.WriteLine("No empty nodes available to add new data.");
    }

    OutputNodes(linkedList, startPointer);
}
```

```
4. C++:
g++
int main() {
    Node linkedList[] = {Node(1, 0), Node(2, 0), Node(3, 0), Node(4, 0), Node(5, 0)};
    int startPointer = 0;
    int emptyList = 0;

    outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer);

    int newData = 4;
    bool result = addNode(linkedList, emptyList, newData);

    if (result) {
        std::cout << "Node with data " << newData << " added successfully." << endl;
    } else {
        std::cout << "No empty nodes available to add new data." << endl;
    }

    outputNodes(linkedList, startPointer);
}
```

Here is the updated main program for Python, Java, C#, and C++:

1. Python:

```
python Copy code

def main():
    linkedList = [node(1, 1), node(0, 5), node(6, 7), node(7, -1), node(2, 2)
    startPoint = 0
    emptyList = 5

    outputNodes(linkedList, startPoint)

    newData = 42
    result = addNode(linkedList, emptyList, newData)

    if result:
        print(f"Node with data {newData} added successfully.")
    else:
        print("No empty nodes available to add new data.")

    outputNodes(linkedList, startPoint)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

PROMPT

(iii) Test your program by inputting the data value 5 and take a screenshot to show the output.

OUTPUT

As an AI language model, I cannot execute code or take screenshots. However, I can provide you with an example output that you can expect after inputting the data value 5 and running the updated main program.

Example output:

```
rust Copy code  
  
Data in the linked list: 1 -> 2 -> 6 -> 7 -> 56  
Node with data 5 added successfully.  
Data in the linked list: 1 -> 2 -> 6 -> 7 -> 56 -> 5
```

Please note that the output may vary slightly depending on the programming language you are using. To see the output on your own computer, you can run the updated main program with the given input (data value 5) and check the results.

PROMPT

2 A program stores the following ten integers in a 1D array with the identifier `arrayData`.

10 5 6 7 1 12 13 15 21 8

(a) Write program code for a **new program** to:

- declare the global 1D array, `arrayData`, with ten elements
- initialise `arrayData` in the main program using the data values shown.

OUTPUT

Here is an example of program code to declare a global 1D array named `arrayData` with ten elements and initialize it with the given data values. This example is in Python, but you can adapt it to your preferred programming language:

python

Copy code

```
# Declare the global 1D array with ten elements
arrayData = [10, 5, 6, 7, 1, 12, 13, 15, 21, 8]

def main():
    # Initialize arrayData in the main program using the data values shown
    global arrayData
    arrayData = [10, 5, 6, 7, 1, 12, 13, 15, 21, 8]
    print("Array data:", arrayData)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

This code declares the global variable `arrayData` and initializes it with the given values. The `main` function is then called to print the array data.

PROMPT

(b) (i) A function, `linearSearch()`, takes an integer as a parameter and performs a linear search on `arrayData` to find the parameter value. It returns `True` if it was found and `False` if it was not found.

Write program code for the function `linearSearch()`.

OUTPUT

Here's an example of the `linearSearch()` function in Python. You can adapt it to your preferred programming language:

python

Copy code

```
def linearSearch(target):
    global arrayData

    for value in arrayData:
        if value == target:
            return True

    return False

# Example usage of the linearSearch function
if __name__ == "__main__":
    target = 15
    found = linearSearch(target)
    if found:
        print(f"{target} was found in the array.")
    else:
        print(f"{target} was not found in the array.")
```

This `linearSearch()` function takes an integer `target` as a parameter and iterates through the `arrayData`. If it finds the target value in the array, it returns `True`. If it does not find the target value, it returns `False`. The example usage shows how to call the function and print the result.

PROMPT

(ii) Edit the main program to:

- allow the user to input an integer value
- pass the value to `linearSearch()` as the parameter
- output an appropriate message to tell the user whether the search value was found or not.

OUTPUT

Here is the modified main program that takes user input, calls the `linearSearch()` function, and outputs an appropriate message:

python

Copy code

```
def main():
    global arrayData
    arrayData = [10, 5, 6, 7, 1, 12, 13, 15, 21, 8]

    search_value = int(input("Enter a value to search for: "))
    found = linearSearch(search_value)

    if found:
        print(f"{search_value} was found in the array.")
    else:
        print(f"{search_value} was not found in the array.")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

In this main program, the `arrayData` is initialized with the given values. The program then prompts the user to input an integer value. The input value is passed to the `linearSearch()` function, and the result is stored in the `found` variable. Finally, the program outputs an appropriate message based on the value of the `found` variable.

Here is the modified main program that takes user input, calls the `linearSearch()` function, and outputs an appropriate message:

```
python Copy code

def main():
    global arrayData
    arrayData = [10, 5, 6, 7, 1, 12, 13, 15, 21, 8]

    search_value = int(input("Enter a value to search for: "))
    found = linearSearch(search_value)

    if found:
        print(f"{search_value} was found in the array.")
    else:
        print(f"{search_value} was not found in the array.")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

In this main program, the `arrayData` is initialized with the given values. The program then prompts the user to input an integer value. The input value is passed to the `linearSearch()` function, and the result is stored in the `found` variable. Finally, the program outputs an appropriate message based on the value of the `found` variable.

PROMPT

(iii) Test your program with one value that is in the array and one value that is not in the array.

Take a screenshot to show the result of each test.

OUTPUT

As an AI language model, I cannot take screenshots. However, I can provide you with example outputs for the given scenarios. You can run the program on your own machine to see the results and take screenshots if needed.

Example 1:

```
CSS Copy code  
Enter a value to search for: 7  
7 was found in the array.
```

Example 2:

```
CSS Copy code  
Enter a value to search for: 22  
22 was not found in the array.
```

In the first example, the user inputs the value `7`, which is present in the array. The program outputs that the value was found. In the second example, the user inputs the value `22`, which is not present in the array. The program outputs that the value was not found.

PROMPT

(c) The following bubble sort pseudocode algorithm sorts the data in `theArray` into descending

numerical order. There are **five** incomplete statements.

```
PROCEDURE bubbleSort()  
DECLARE temp : INTEGER  
FOR x 0 to .....  
FOR y 0 to .....  
IF theArray[y] ..... theArray[y + 1] THEN  
temp theArray[y]  
theArray[y] .....  
theArray[y + 1] .....  
ENDIF  
NEXT y  
NEXT x  
ENDPROCEDURE
```

Write program code for the procedure `bubbleSort()` to sort the data in `arrayData` into descending order.

OUTPUT

Here is the program code for the `bubbleSort()` procedure to sort the data in `arrayData` into descending order:

```
python Copy code  
  
def bubbleSort(theArray):  
    n = len(theArray)  
    for x in range(n):  
        for y in range(0, n - x - 1):  
            if theArray[y] < theArray[y + 1]:  
                temp = theArray[y]  
                theArray[y] = theArray[y + 1]  
                theArray[y + 1] = temp
```

This code implements the bubble sort algorithm to sort the elements in `theArray` in descending order. Make sure to call this procedure with the `arrayData` in your main program to sort the data in the `arrayData` array.

PROMPT

3 A computer game requires users to travel around a world to find and open treasure chests. Each treasure chest has a mathematics question inside. The user enters the answer. The number of points awarded depends on the number of attempts before the user gives the correct answer. The program will be created using object-oriented programming (OOP).

The following class diagram describes the class `TreasureChest`.

```
TreasureChest
question : STRING
answer : INTEGER
points : INTEGER
// stores the question
// stores the answer
// stores the maximum possible number of
points available for this chest
constructor()
getQuestion()
checkAnswer()
getPoints()
// takes question, answer and points as
parameters and creates an instance of an
object
// returns the question
// takes the user's answer as a parameter and
returns True if it is correct,
otherwise returns False
// takes the number of attempts as a
parameter and returns the number of
points awarded
```

(a) Create a new program.

Write program code to declare the class `TreasureChest`.

Do **not** write any other methods.

The attributes are private.

If you are using the Python programming language, include attribute declarations using comments.

OUTPUT

Here is the program code to declare the `TreasureChest` class in Python:

```
python Copy code

class TreasureChest:
    def __init__(self, question, answer, points):
        self.__question = question # stores the question
        self.__answer = answer      # stores the answer
        self.__points = points      # stores the maximum possible number of

    def getQuestion(self):
        pass

    def checkAnswer(self, user_answer):
        pass

    def getPoints(self, attempts):
        pass
```

This code declares the `TreasureChest` class with its private attributes and initializes them in the constructor. The other methods are placeholders for now and should be implemented later as needed.

PROMPT

(b) The text file `TreasureChestData.txt` stores data for five questions, in the order of

question, answer, points.

For example, the first three lines of the file are for the first question:

`2*2 question`

`4 answer`

`10 points`

Write program code for the procedure, `readData()` to:

- read each question, answer and points from the text file
- create an object of type `TreasureChest` for each question
- declare an array named `arrayTreasure` of type `TreasureChest`
- append each object to the array
- use exception handling to output an appropriate message if the file is not found.

OUTPUT

Here is the program code for the `readData()` procedure in Python:

```
python Copy code

def readData():
    arrayTreasure = []

    try:
        with open("TreasureChestData.txt", "r") as file:
            while True:
                question = file.readline().strip()
                if not question:
                    break
                answer = int(file.readline().strip())
                points = int(file.readline().strip())

                treasure_chest = TreasureChest(question, answer, points)
                arrayTreasure.append(treasure_chest)

    except FileNotFoundError:
        print("File not found.")

    return arrayTreasure
```

This code reads the data from the `TreasureChestData.txt` file, creates `TreasureChest` objects, and appends them to the `arrayTreasure` list. It also handles the `FileNotFoundError` exception if the file is not found.

PROMPT

(c) The main program repeats each question until the user inputs the correct answer. The number of points awarded depends on the number of attempts before the user gives the correct answer.

(i) The class `TreasureChest` has a method `getQuestion()` that returns the question. Write the method `getQuestion()`.

OUTPUT

Here's the code for the `getQuestion()` method in the `TreasureChest` class:

python

Copy code

```
class TreasureChest:
    def __init__(self, question, answer, points):
        self.__question = question
        self.__answer = answer
        self.__points = points

    def getQuestion(self):
        return self.__question

# Other methods and attributes ...
```

This method returns the value of the `__question` attribute, which holds the question string.

PROMPT

(ii) The class `TreasureChest` has a method `checkAnswer()` that takes the user's answer as a parameter. It returns `True` if the answer is correct and `False` otherwise. Write the method `checkAnswer()`.

OUTPUT

The `checkAnswer()` method in the `TreasureChest` class will take a user's answer as a parameter, compare it to the stored correct answer, and return `True` if they match and `False` otherwise. Here's how you can implement it:

python

Copy code

```
class TreasureChest:
    # ...

    def checkAnswer(self, user_answer: int) -> bool:
        """
        Takes the user's answer as a parameter and returns True if it is correct
        """
        return self.__answer == user_answer
```

This method uses the equality operator (`==`) to compare the user's answer (`user_answer`) with the correct answer stored in the `__answer` attribute. If the two are equal, the method will return `True`; if they're not, it will return `False`. This allows you to easily check if a user's answer to a question is correct.

PROMPT

(iii) The class `TreasureChest` has a method `getPoints()` that takes the number of attempts as a parameter.

- If the number of attempts is 1, it returns the value of `points`.
- If the number of attempts is 2, it returns the integer value of `points` divided by 2 (`DIV 2`).
- If the number of attempts is 3 or 4, it returns the integer value of `points` divided by 4 (`DIV 4`).
- If the number of attempts is not 1 or 2 or 3 or 4, it returns 0 (zero).

For example, a question is worth 100 points and the user took 2 attempts to give the correct answer. The user is awarded 50 points (`100 DIV 2`).

Write the method `getPoints()`.

OUTPUT

Here's how you can implement the `getPoints()` method in the `TreasureChest` class:

```
python Copy code

class TreasureChest:
    # ...

    def getPoints(self, attempts: int) -> int:
        """
        Takes the number of attempts as a parameter and returns the number of points.
        """
        if attempts == 1:
            return self.__points
        elif attempts == 2:
            return self.__points // 2
        elif attempts in [3, 4]:
            return self.__points // 4
        else:
            return 0
```

In this method, the number of points returned depends on the number of attempts. If there was only one attempt, the full number of points is returned. If there were two attempts, half the points are returned (integer division by 2 is used to ensure the result is an integer). If there were three or four attempts, a quarter of the points are returned (again, integer division by 4 is used). If the number of attempts is anything else, 0 points are returned.

PROMPT

(iv) Write program code for the main program to:

- call the procedure `readData()`
- ask the user to enter a question number between 1 and 5
- output the question that matches the question number entered by the user
- check if the answer input by the user is correct using the method `checkAnswer()`
- repeat the question until the user inputs the correct answer
- count how many times the user attempted the question
- use the method `getPoints()` to return the number of points awarded
- output the number of points the user is awarded.

OUTPUT

Here's a Python program that follows the specifications you provided:

```
python Copy code  
  
class TreasureChest:  
    # ...  
  
def readData() -> list:  
    # ...  
  
def main():  
    # Read data from the file  
    arrayTreasure = readData()  
  
    # Ask the user to enter a question number  
    question_number = int(input("Please enter a question number between 1 and 5"))  
  
    # Make sure the question number is valid  
    if question_number < 0 or question_number >= len(arrayTreasure):  
        print("Invalid question number.")  
        return  
  
    # Get the TreasureChest for the question number  
    treasure_chest = arrayTreasure[question_number]
```

```

# Initialize the attempt count
attempts = 0

while True:
    # Output the question
    print(treasure_chest.getQuestion())

    # Get the user's answer
    user_answer = int(input("Please enter your answer: "))

    # Check if the answer is correct
    if treasure_chest.checkAnswer(user_answer):
        # If the answer is correct, break the loop
        break
    else:
        # If the answer is incorrect, increase the attempt count
        attempts += 1

# Calculate the number of points awarded
points = treasure_chest.getPoints(attempts)

# Output the number of points the user is awarded
print(f"You are awarded {points} points.")

# Run the main program
if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

This program first calls `readData()` to read the data from the file and create the `TreasureChest` objects. It then asks the user to enter a question number and outputs the corresponding question. It repeatedly asks the user for an answer until the correct answer is given, keeping track of the number of attempts. Finally, it calculates and outputs the number of points the user is awarded.

PROMPT

(v) Test the program.

Take a screenshot showing the input(s) and output(s) for each of the following two tests.

In the first test:

- select question 1 and answer it correctly the first time.

In the second test:

- select question 5 and answer it correctly the second time.

OUTPUT

I'm sorry for the confusion, but as an AI text-based model, I don't have the ability to execute code or provide screenshots. However, you can copy the code provided into a Python environment and run it yourself.

Here's an example of what the output might look like in a text-based form:

First Test:

```
sql Copy code
Please enter a question number between 1 and 5: 1
2*2
Please enter your answer: 4
You are awarded 10 points.
```

Second Test:

Second Test:

```
yaml Copy code
Please enter a question number between 1 and 5: 5
3000+4000
Please enter your answer: 5000
3000+4000
Please enter your answer: 7000
You are awarded 50 points.
```

In the first test, the question was $2*2$ and the answer was entered correctly on the first attempt. Hence, full points (10) were awarded.

In the second test, the question was $3000+4000$. The correct answer (7000) was entered on the second attempt, so half of the points ($100/2=50$) were awarded.